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Analysis of the international journal publishing activities in Switzerland with special emphasis on gold open access publishing

Data Paper by Max-Planck Digital Library, Big Data Analytics Group

Alexander Machado, Laura Hoppmann, Johannes Knaus & Margit Palzenberger

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1 Summary

The following study was commissioned by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the *swissuniversities* within the “Scientific information: access, processing and safeguarding” program (SUC P-2) and was executed by the Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL).

The analysis focuses on the international journal publishing activities in Switzerland with special emphasis on gold open access publishing.

The main data source describing the publishing activity in Switzerland was Scopus, an abstract and citation database for peer reviewed scientific articles provided by Elsevier. The raw data provided were processed, cleaned and enriched from the Directory of Open Access Databases (DOAJ) and MPDL in-house databases to derive a data warehouse appropriate for the intended analytics.

Additional to the analysis for Switzerland in total, 10 institutions selected by the contractor were prepared for a separate analysis. The idea was to build up a selection that would be representative for Switzerland as a whole. Thus, the two Polytechnic Federal Institutes were selected, as well as the six biggest cantonal universities. Furthermore, a University of Higher Education and a University of Applied Sciences were chosen for the selection.

- Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
- Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne
- Universität Zürich
- Université Genève
- Universität Bern
- Universität Basel
- Université Lausanne
- Université Fribourg
- Berner Fachhochschule
- Hochschule Luzern

For this selection, MPDL conducted an individual unification of Scopus affiliation strings.

Publication data were analysed with respect to the number of articles published and aggregated at the levels of the publishing journal and the publisher for Switzerland in total and the 10 selection institutions. Gold open access publishers and journals were compared to subscription journals at all aggregation levels. For the estimation of open access costs, the share of articles with a reprint affiliation from Switzerland or selected institutions was calculated. Open access numbers from Germany, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Austria as well as from worldwide publishing are presented for comparison.

The aggregated results in this report are accompanied by more extensive basic data in an Excel file.

2 Introduction

Open access to research articles is evolving considerably in recent times. A constantly increasing number of authors select one of the pure open access journals for the dissemination of their scientific findings. After more than 15 years of steady evolution, business models have proven to be viable and many stakeholders now think of enforcing steps towards this publishing model. The open access market landscape is, however, characterized by an enormous diversity of variants considered – from pure gold or even platinum via hybrid and “hybrid 2.0” (offsetting) to the green way of depositing. Many sophisticated details add to that model variety.

Beside dedicated open access publishers like PLoS, BMC, Frontiers or Copernicus, more and more classical subscription publishers like Elsevier, Wiley or Springer offer a selection of their journals in an APC-based version (gold open access). Hybrid models also recently gain interest again. Especially in their “offsetting” variant they are negotiated as a transition state from subscription to open access, balancing vendors and customers interests.

In the light of these dynamic market developments, libraries have to find a reasonable way of shaping a strategy well fitted to their specific situation. This is achieved best on base of sound evidence on the publishing profiles of their scientists. From that they are able to calculate expected costs for a transition in general, and with respect to selected publishers in particular. They can use these numbers in negotiations with publishers to achieve acceptable pricing frameworks, and identify journals of special interest for a transformation into an open access model.

The most appropriate sources for this type of information are the international bibliographic databases “Web of Science” (Thompson Reuters) and “Scopus” (Elsevier). They cover a broad range of subjects and journal types and thus may be used for a description of publication profiles of institutions from a variety of domains. Typically, they are used via web interfaces at the providers platforms but may also be acquired as so-called “raw data” in an XML format. The latter is an indispensable prerequisite for large scale quantitative analysis.

Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL) uses these raw data together with enriching data sources and in-house files for the buildup of a data warehouse since several years. Data cleaning and processing routines have been developed and tuned for the generation of publishing profiles.

As no analysis of data for Switzerland has yet been carried out the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the *swissuniversities* commissioned the present study to compile basic key numbers on the publication profiles for Switzerland in total and ten selected institutions.

3 Data Sources and Methods

3.1 Data Sources

The analysis in this report is based on a data warehouse derived from (1) Scopus, an Elsevier owned bibliographic database, (2) the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and (3) MPDL in-house authority files on journals and publishers.

3.1.1 Elsevier's Scopus

The bibliographic data source for this analysis is the abstract and citation database Scopus provided by Elsevier. At the time of analysis (July 2016) Scopus comprised data from about 21,500 peer-reviewed journals and about 5,000 publishers. For general information, see the product's homepage¹ and the detailed content information².

Whereas Scopus is generally used via a web interface on the providers platform, large scale bibliometric analyses need to be based on local "raw data" in XML format delivered by Elsevier. These raw data are licensed by the Kompetenzzentrum Bibliometrie³, a German project and consortium funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)⁴ under the grant O1PQ13001.

The data set used for this report was provided by Scopus in calendar week 17 (2016-04-25). The XML raw data were uploaded into an Oracle relational database by the Fachinformationszentrum Karlsruhe⁵. Starting from these relational raw data, MPDL conducted extensive data transformation, cleaning and standardization to make them suitable for further bibliometric analysis. This study includes articles from 2001 to 2015 (with the caveat for completeness in 2015, see below).

Some of the general data characteristics of Scopus need to be taken into account for the current study:

Scopus covers a broad range of subjects and publishing countries but nevertheless has biases with respect to publication type, internationalization, pervasiveness, impact, or language of the journals in consideration. As there is no source of reference, these biases cannot be quantified.

Scopus constantly adds new data to the database, but there is a lag between articles being published and being added to the Scopus raw data. Even for the data delivered in April 2016 we have substantial indication that data for 2015 are neither complete in total numbers nor with respect to specific fields.

The total number of articles (document type "article" and "review") indexed in Scopus (April 2016) was 2,015,474 in 2014 and 1,870,395 in 2015 equaling to a decline of 7 per cent. In the recent 10 years, total publication numbers were continuously rising with a median of 5 per cent. Thus, it now would be rather unexpected to have a real decline in publication activities worldwide. The decline for Switzerland is less. It amounts to 3.4 per cent. This can be explained by a faster processing of Swiss articles for Scopus and/or a larger increase in Swiss articles as compared to the global numbers.

The coverage of articles having a reprint affiliation identified seems to be a further indication of time lags in data processing for the Scopus database. Usually every publication has one affiliation among the list of affiliations which is identified as a so-called reprint or corresponding affiliation. In the Scopus database, this is true for the selected countries up to the publication year 2011 (Table 1). From then onwards, there is an increasing fraction of articles which miss that information. Especially problematic is the uneven distribution of these deficiencies. For the large publishers ("Big 4") the situation stays acceptable even for the most recent years but for other publishers the completeness drops dramatically to an average of 75 per cent in 2015. Therefore, the numbers on reprint affiliations need to be corrected for this bias.

In the Scopus XML raw data publishers are not covered. Elsevier provides an extra "Scopus Source List"⁶, an Excel file including information on publishers. However, the level of harmonization of names and imprints is very low and it cannot be used as is for data analysis.

Scopus identifies journals by journal title, title abbreviations, print and electronic ISSN and a proprietary journal identifier. Unfortunately, this information is to a large extent inconsistent and incomplete. Altogether, these fields add up to more than 60,000 unique combinations. Compared to the 21,500 journals that are indexed, this means that we have an average of three variants per journal title.

Quality assurance processes also revealed that a substantial number of article affiliations in Scopus lack information on the country. These articles are omitted in country

¹<https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/scopus>

²<https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/scopus/content>

³<http://www.bibliometrie.info>

⁴<https://www.bmbf.de>

⁵<https://www.fiz-karlsruhe.de>

⁶https://www.elsevier.com/__data/assets/excel_doc/0015/91122/title_list.xlsx

country	group	2007	Y2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
global	big 4	97	98	98	99	99	99	99	94	95
global	other	90	92	93	93	94	94	91	78	73
global	oa	98	99	99	99	99	99	97	79	79
gb	big 4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	96
gb	other	100	100	99	100	100	100	98	87	80
gb	oa	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	79	78
de	big 4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	96
de	other	100	100	100	100	100	99	98	83	74
de	oa	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	77	77
nl	big 4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	97	97
nl	other	100	100	100	100	100	99	98	87	80
nl	oa	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	76	74
ch	big 4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	97
ch	other	100	100	100	100	100	99	98	84	75
ch	oa	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	78	80
at	big 4	99	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	96
at	other	100	100	100	100	99	99	97	83	74
at	oa	100	100	100	100	100	100	97	77	77

Tabelle 1: Completeness of reprint affiliation entries in the Scopus data source. Ratio of articles having a reprint affiliation from any country to the total number of articles in a given subset.

comparisons relying on that field. Unfortunately it is not a random pattern but has distinct dependencies on the publication year and eventually other sources of influence.

3.1.2 MPDL Journal and Publisher Data

As outlined above, the quality of the journal metadata provided by Scopus is substantially lower than we would expect for a meaningful analysis. This is true for journal titles and even more for journal publishers. Therefore, we matched the Scopus raw data entries to an in-house database built and maintained by MPDL since about 10 years. The database currently indexes 80,000+ unique journal titles. A subset of 30,000+ journal titles is assigned to 200+ explicitly identified and harmonized publishers.

We developed extensive procedures to harmonize journal titles and to assign them to the current publisher. This is notoriously difficult as there is no single reference which provides this information. Constantly changing title names and titles moving from one publisher to another cause significant challenges for accuracy and topicality of the matching process. Within the bounds of our resources, we try to consolidate information from as many sources as possible: title lists from big databases (Web of Science, Scopus, DOAJ) as well as individual title lists from a substantial number of publishers MPDL is interested in.

3.1.3 Directory of Open Access Journals

We use the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)⁷ for identification of gold open access journals. The DOAJ provides a list of over 90,000 gold open access journal titles along with metadata including publisher information. The content is primarily maintained by the publishers with some extra input via a quality assurance team. There is no guarantee with respect to completeness or correctness

⁷<https://doaj.org/about>

and we are aware of several missing cases. For reproducibility however, we use the DOAJ as the only reference without adding information from other sources. The only exception to this practice are the two SCOAP³⁸ journals published by Springer which are left out in DOAJ but have a significant impact on open access numbers.

To utilize the DOAJ, the journals titles are matched against the in-house database. For the selection of gold open access articles, we also take into account an eventual year of transformation from the subscription model to gold open access. Some prominent examples are the journals transformed in 2014 to gold open access by the SCOAP³ program.

3.2 Affiliation Matching

3.2.1 Challenges in Affiliation Matching

To be able to analyze publication patterns for individual institutions it is crucial that their affiliation strings are identified in the bibliometric raw data and assigned to the corresponding institutions. For the 349,294 Swiss articles selected for this study we have to deal with 729,766 affiliation entries. After a first step of automatic standardization (lower case, concatenating and harmonizing fields) we find 309,934 unique affiliation strings.

The Scopus database provides additional information via their proprietary Affiliation ID (AFID) which is supposed to be a unique identifier for institutions at the organization level. For Switzerland, we find 25,349 unique AFID entries aggregating 683,402 affiliation strings. For the remaining 40,198 affiliation entries no AFID is given. Cross checks against our in-house standardization (see below) show considerable deficiencies with respect to completeness, precision and reliability.

⁸<https://scoap3.org>

Therefore, we developed a routine which directly evaluates affiliations from the Scopus raw data. We created a combined affiliation string from information provided in Scopus. Within a single publication, each author has at least one affiliation which consists of all or part of the following information: country, zip code, city, institution and department. However, when the affiliation does not follow typical affiliation patterns or not all information is present, not all these fields are correctly filled by Scopus. This mostly happens when Scopus cannot clearly distinguish between an institution name at organization versus department level. Additionally, there are cases where the data do not make any sense, even after an intellectual check.

Some examples for the heterogeneity for the preprocessed affiliation strings are given here:

```
che:zürich:universität zürich physik institut
che:zurich:universität zurich physik institut
```

```
che:ch 8093 zurich:eidgenössische th zurich lab ...
che:ch 8092 zurich:eidgen tech hochschule zurich lab ...
che:ch 8093 zurich:eth hänggerberg swiss federal inst ...
che:zurich ch 8092:swiss fed institute of technology ...
che:ch 8092 zurich:eth zentrum eidgenössischen techn ...
```

```
che::univ geneva c m u 1 r michel s ctr vacc ...
che:ch 1211 Genève 4:université de Genève département ...
che:ch 1211 geneva 4:university of geneva school of ...
che:geneva:université de Genève
```

3.2.2 Affiliation Cleaning

We performed an in-depth cleaning for 10 institutions selected by the contractor. The institutions chosen for this report are:

- Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
- Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne
- Universität Zürich
- Université Genève
- Universität Bern
- Universität Basel
- Université Lausanne
- Université Fribourg
- Berner Fachhochschule
- Hochschule Luzern

In order to match affiliations, a subsample is drawn from Scopus which contains all the affiliations with the Swiss country code. Subsequently, this subset is parsed using regular expression pattern matching techniques for the individual institutions:

First, all affiliation strings are searched for the exact or nearly exact occurrences of institution names, while not taking into account the information about the city in the affiliation string. These search criteria match entries where institutions either are spread over several locations or

the city string is a non standard entry (e.g. for a suburb) or severely misspelled. Affiliation strings matched to an institution are marked. An example case for a department in a different city than the main campus is:

```
che:4058 basel:eth zürich;
department of biosystems science and engineering
```

Second, a subset of institutions is selected according to the location of the main campus. The search pattern for the institution is generalized to account for differences, inconsistencies and spelling errors in institution names. This is a crucial step especially in a multilingual country like Switzerland, where regularly the German, French, Italian, and English spelling is used. The example for affiliations we assign to the ETH are:

```
DE: che:8093 zurich:eidgenössische technische hochschule;
EN: che:zurich:swiss federal institute of technology zürich;
FR: che::école polytechnique fédérale de zurich;
IT: che:zurich:inst politecnico federal de zurich
```

Third, during the matching process, institutions which are clearly identifiable as being different are blacklisted.

After these steps, the results are evaluated based on a predefined decision tree. In the first iteration results are checked by an independent person and feedback is provided for improving the algorithms. In the following iterations, only cases which are marked as unclear by the decision tree are checked by one to two independent data scientists. For this study, we checked the affiliation entries for each unique affiliation string which was assigned to at least 4 articles (28,206 entries representing 284,109 articles, 39%). Within this data, the error rate for false matches (positive and negative) is below 0.1% in our last iteration. The significant long tail of the remaining affiliations (28,206 entries representing 284,109 articles, 61%) cannot be checked manually. However, due to the iterative improvement in our matching algorithm, we are confident that the precision of affiliation assignments is acceptable within the general framework of this study.

Hospitals are a very specific subset within the selected institutions. Therefore we decided to separate them with due diligence into their own category. No distinction between university hospitals, cantonal hospitals and private hospitals was made.

The remaining affiliations (“others”) are either other institutions within Switzerland or affiliation strings which did not contain enough information to extract any kind of information from them, for example:

```
che:8093 zurich: .
```


Abbildung 1: Number of unique affiliation strings for the 10 selected Swiss institutions, the general group “hospital” and the remaining affiliations (“others”). See also appendix tab. 12

In the light of the challenges for affiliation matching it was agreed to accept a rate of 5 percent for false assignments. Intellectually checked samples indicate that this is well achieved in general and for the institutions selected. This is corroborated by an even more extensive search for ETHZ based on its zip code only. With that we find a maximum of 1.8% of their articles to be candidates for further inclusion (appendix tab 13).

3.3 Data Analysis and Reporting

After preprocessing of raw data and standardization of journal titles, publishers, and affiliations, the Swiss dataset was ready for final analysis. All data aggregation steps were run as scripted SQL-Statements in a PostgreSQL database. Results were exported to CSV and Excel and processed with Python / IPython-Notebook for visualization.

The following definitions are used throughout the report and the accompanying Excel file:

- *article*: records from the Scopus database with the document types “article” or “review”
- *Big 4*: Elsevier, Springer, Wiley, Taylor and Francis (publishers with more than 2000 journal titles)
- *reprint affiliation*: synonym to corresponding affiliation; usually one per article
- Rankings for publishers and journals are defined by an average of the last three publication years (2013-2015)
- Example data and figures are presented for 2015 (even if we have indications that this publication year is not complete) – the ranking of that year may deviate from the overall ranking

Detailed data can be retrieved from the accompanying Excel file, either in CSV format (hidden tabs) or in the layouted version. A PDF version of that file is included in this report as an appendix.

4 Results for Switzerland

This section comprises the analysis of the international journal publishing activities in Switzerland as a whole. Switzerland is compared to four other countries, chosen by the contractors, namely: Austria (AT), Germany (DE), the Netherlands (NL) and the United Kingdom (UK), as well as to global numbers.

4.1 Open Access Articles

Abbildung 2: Development of the number of articles with at least one Swiss affiliation, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray)

For the publication year 2015, Scopus indexed a total number of 1,870,000 articles⁹ in scientific journals. Authors affiliated in Switzerland accounted for 31,000 of these articles (Figure 2). This corresponds to a Swiss article share on the world market of 2%. In comparison, Germany has a share of 6%, Austria of 1%, the Netherlands of 2%, and the United Kingdom of 7%. From 2006-2015 the global number of articles covered in Scopus increased by 59%. At the same time, the number of articles from Switzerland increased by 73%.

We see an overall decrease in numbers for 2015 as compared to 2014, both worldwide and for selected countries. This is most likely explained by the still incomplete dataset of Scopus for the year 2015 (see section 3.1.1). As outlined in the methods sections, all numbers for 2015 presumably should be increased by 5 to 10 per cent.

There has been a steady increase of absolute as well as relative numbers for gold open access articles since 2001. Over the recent decade (2006-2015) absolute numbers increased almost 6-fold worldwide and 8-fold in Switzerland. The global share of open access articles has risen from 3% to 12% in that period. The corresponding numbers for the selected countries are slightly above world average: Switzerland 16%, Germany 13%, Austria 15%, UK 13%, the Netherlands 14% (Figures 2 and 3).

⁹rounded to the nearest thousand.

Abbildung 3: Share of gold open access articles in relation to all articles for selected countries and worldwide.

References are a good measure for the use of a resource as they imply also the usefulness to the author citing the article. In this report, the term “references” corresponds to citations of an article which appeared up to two years before the citing article.

Using this definition we find that the number of references steadily rose since 2001 with an even steeper increase than for the article numbers. This is especially significant for references to gold open access articles.

Abbildung 4: Development of the number of references from articles with at least one Swiss affiliation, split into three groups (color-coding see fig. 2)

4.2 Open Access Publishers

Tabelle 2: Top publishers within the three groups shown in figure 2. Number of articles in 2015 by publisher ranked top down. Dedicated open access publishers are indicated by “oa only”

articles within gold open access journals	
PLoS (oa only)	936
BMC (oa only)	760
NPG	476
Springer	426
Elsevier	327
Frontiers (oa only)	299
Copernicus (oa only)	257
MDPI (oa only)	172
Wiley	156
Hindawi (oa only)	113
EMH	97
articles within subscription journals – “Big 4”	
Elsevier	6622
Wiley	3581
Springer	2358
Taylor	590
articles within subscription journals – other publishers	
ACS	1040
APS	784
OUP	685
RSC	613
LWW	568
NPG	547
IEEE	538
IOP	415
Sage	385
AIP	369

Table 2 and figure 5 show the publishers that Swiss authors chose most frequently in 2015.

With 22% of the articles, Elsevier is the largest publisher for Switzerland, followed by Wiley with 12%, and Springer with 9%. Taylor & Francis (the fourth big commercial publisher with more than 2000 titles in its portfolio) covers a share of less than 2% only. Together, the “Big 4” cover a market share of more than 40%. For articles in subscription based journals, the American Chemical Society (ACS), followed by the Nature Publishing Group, and the American Physical Society (APS) following after them.

The largest dedicated gold open access publishers in Switzerland are the Public Library of Science (PLoS, 3.0%) followed by BioMed Central (BMC, 2.5%). They rank amongst the top ten publishers. However, three classical publishers rank immediately after them with respect to the number of Swiss papers in open access journals: Nature Publishing Group, Springer, and Elsevier.

Abbildung 5: Top 20 publishers with which the Swiss authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

4.3 Open Access Journals

Merging the data from the Scopus database and in-house standardization data, we identified a total of 16,180 unique journal titles with 371,390 articles in the subset for Switzerland in the time period 2001 to 2015. For the publication year 2015 there were 6,702 journal titles with 31,256 articles found. The top 20 journals altogether published 3,619 articles – around 0.1% of the total number of articles. Thus, we see a very broad distribution with only little concentration towards some prominent journals.

The journal with the most articles in 2015 is PLoS One, published by the dedicated gold open access publisher PLoS, followed by *Revue Medicale Suisse* published in French by Groupe Médecine & Hygiène, and the *Journal of High Energy Physics* which is published by Springer. The latter journal is part of the SCOAP³ program and thus is published open access since 2014. Five out of the top 20 journals in Switzerland use gold open access as their revenue model.

4.4 Reprint Affiliations

Subsection 4.1 introduced the number of articles with at least one Swiss affiliation, treating each author equal. However, each article has one affiliation which is the so-called corresponding affiliation or reprint affiliation. In gold open access articles there is a consensus that the

Tabelle 3: Number of articles in the top 20 journals in Switzerland. Gold open access journals are tagged with an asterisk.

Publisher	Journal Title	#
PLoS	*PLoS ONE	707
EMH	Revue Médicale Suisse	294
Springer	*J. High Energy Physics	246
APS	Physical Review B	242
NPG	*Scientific Reports	230
NPG	*Nature Communications	230
APS	Physical Review Letters	210
APS	Physical Review D	178
EDP	Astronomy and Astrophysics	169
Hogrefe	Schweiz. Rundsch. Medizin Praxis	134
Wiley	Angewandte Chemie Int. Ed.	132
AAS	Astrophysical Journal	130
NAS	Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (PNAS)	127
Elsevier	*Physics Letters B	98
OUP	MN R. Royal Astronomical Soc.	96
ACS	Environm. Sci. Technol.	91
AIP	Applied Physics Letters	87
Hogrefe	Therapeutische Umschau	86
EMH	*Swiss Medical Weekly	70
Elsevier	Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A	62

Abbildung 6: Development of the article numbers with at least one swiss affiliation, divided into articles with swiss reprint affiliations (switzerland_rp), reprint affiliations from other countries (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

reprint affiliation is responsible for paying the article processing charge (APC). To understand the cost of an open access transformation, it is therefore crucial to know the number of articles published by reprint affiliations from a given country or institution.

Figure 6 shows the time line for the number of articles by Swiss reprint affiliations as indexed by Scopus. Absolute numbers rose throughout this time period, however relative numbers declined continuously from more than 70% in 2001 to an estimate of 54% in 2015 (after correction for presumably incomplete data – see methods section). This is found for many countries and might be explained by the growing number of authors per paper and their international cooperation.

The estimated current value of 54% articles by reprint affiliations from Switzerland compares well to another estimate derived independently from Web of Science data.¹⁰ This is typical for smaller, internationally cooperating countries as the share of reprint affiliations for countries worldwide is well correlated to the total number of articles from the respective country.

Breaking down the results by publisher for 2015, we see that the ratio of reprint affiliations is comparable for Elsevier (52%), Wiley (48%), and Springer (53%).

Abbildung 7: Overview of the distribution of reprint (rp) and non-reprint (nrp) affiliations in 2015 split by publisher.

¹⁰Palzenberger, M. (2015). Number of Scholarly Articles per Country. doi:10.17617/1.2

5 Results for Selected Institutions

This section shows the results for the 10 selected individual institutions. Together these institutions publish 49% of the Swiss articles (Figure 8, Table 4).

Tabelle 4: Articles with at least one Swiss affiliation, split by institution and publication year. Total shares sum up to more than 100% due to articles jointly published by more than one Swiss institution.

Institution	code	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	share 2015 [%]
École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	epfl	2,372	2,760	3,085	3,115	3,057	9
Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich	eth	4,288	4,972	5,094	5,407	5,086	16
Universität Basel	uba	1,545	1,708	1,930	2,027	1,872	5
Universität Bern	ube	1,910	2,079	2,195	2,597	2,473	7
Université Fribourg	ufr	485	489	532	588	649	2
Université Genève	uge	1,985	2,282	2,322	2,464	2,288	7
Université Lausanne	ula	1,114	1,238	1,334	1,365	1,408	4
Universität Zürich	uzu	2,787	3,175	3,249	3,517	3,317	10
Berner Fachhochschule	bfh	37	76	101	109	92	0
Hochschule Luzern	hslu	11	17	19	29	42	0
hospitals	xhosp	6,473	7,000	7,198	6,950	7,012	22
others	nn	14,946	15,845	16,429	17,060	15,135	48
Switzerland		27,739	30,224	31,486	32,729	31,365	

Abbildung 8: Articles with at least one Swiss affiliation, split by institution for 2015.

5.1 Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ

(a) Development of the number of articles for ETHZ, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by ETHZ, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one ETHZ affiliation, divided into articles with ETHZ reprint affiliations (eth_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the ETHZ authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 9: Data for the Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich.

5.2 Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne - EPFL

(a) Development of the number of articles for EPFL, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by EPFL, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one EPFL affiliation, divided into articles with EPFL reprint affiliations (epfl_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the EPFL authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 10: Data for the Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne.

5.3 Universität Basel

(a) Development of the number of articles for Universität Basel, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Universität Basel, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Univ. Basel affiliation, divided into articles with Univ. Basel reprint affiliations (uba_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Universität Basel authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 11: Data for the Universität Basel. As far as possible we have tried to separate the affiliations for the Universität Basel from Universitätsspital Basel (USB)

5.4 Universität Bern

(a) Development of the number of articles for Universität Bern, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Universität Bern, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Univ. Bern affiliation, divided into articles with Univ. Bern reprint affiliations (ube_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Universität Bern authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 12: Data for the Universität Bern. As far as possible we have tried to separate the affiliations for the Universität Bern from the Universitätsspital Bern (Inselspital)

5.5 Université Fribourg

(a) Development of the number of articles for Université Fribourg, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray)).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Université Fribourg, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Univ. Fribourg affiliation, divided into articles with Univ. Fribourg reprint affiliations (ufr_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Université Fribourg authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 13: Data for the Université Fribourg. As far as possible we have tried to separate the affiliations for the Université Fribourg from the Hôpital Cantonal Fribourg

5.6 Université Genève

(a) Development of the number of articles for Université Genève, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray)).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Université Genève, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Univ. Genève affiliation, divided into articles with Univ. Genève reprint affiliations (uge_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Université Genève authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 14: Data for the Université Genève. As far as possible we have tried to separate the affiliations for the Université Genève from the Hôpitaux Universitaires de Genève (HUG).

5.7 Université Lausanne

(a) Development of the number of articles for Université Lausanne, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray)).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Université Lausanne, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Univ. Lausanne affiliation, divided into articles with Univ. Lausanne reprint affiliations (ula_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Université Lausanne authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 15: Data for the Université Lausanne. As far as possible we have tried to separate the affiliations for Université Lausanne from the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV).

5.8 Universität Zürich

(a) Development of the number of articles for Universität Zürich, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Universität Zürich, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Univ. Zürich affiliation, divided into articles with Univ. Zürich reprint affiliations (uzu_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Universität Zürich authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 16: Data for the Universität Zürich. As far as possible we have tried to separate the affiliations for the Universität Zürich from the Universitätsspital Zürich (USZ)

5.9 Berner Fachhochschule

(a) Development of the number of articles for Berner Fachhochschule, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray)).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Berner Fachhochschule, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one Berner FHS affiliation, divided into articles with Berner FHS reprint affiliations (bfh_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Berner Fachhochschule authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 17: Data for the Berner Fachhochschule.

5.10 Hochschule Luzern

(a) Development of the number of articles for Hochschule Luzern, split into three groups: articles in gold open access journals (gold) and the remaining articles split up into the four large commercial publishers (green) and other publishers (gray)).

(b) Development of the number of references from articles published by Hochschule Luzern, split into three groups (color-coding see (a)).

(c) Development of the article numbers with at least one HS Luzern affiliation, divided into articles with HS Luzern reprint affiliations (hslu_rp), reprint affiliations from other institutions (other_rp) and missing affiliations (non_rp).

(d) Top 20 publishers with which the Hochschule Luzern authors published in 2015 – total numbers of articles are given irrespective of the journal type (open access versus subscription). Dedicated gold open access publishers are color-coded in gold.

Abbildung 18: Data for the Hochschule Luzern.

6 Conclusion

Key values on journal publication patterns in Switzerland and the ten selected institutions have been derived from the bibliographic database Scopus (Elsevier) and were enriched with data from the Directory of Open Access Journals and MPDL in-house authoritative files.

The presented numbers highly rely on the data delivered by its primary source, the Scopus (Elsevier) bibliographic database. It covers more than 20,000 journals from a wide variety of scientific domains. Nevertheless, any interpretation should take into account intentional and unintentional biases with respect to coverage and data quality as provided by Scopus. Deficiencies specifically relevant to this study are the lack of country information and missing tags for reprint affiliations for many articles. Our procedures aimed to correct the data adequately.

In the light of the enormous variability of affiliation entries in the database (more than 300,000 unique entries for Switzerland) it is especially difficult to assign articles to the selected institutions. A multistep semi-automatic processing of these entries was successful in identifying institutions within the contracted margin of error of 5%. We expect this level of precision to be sufficient for interpretations at the large scale intentions of the overall program.

The data compiled for Switzerland show a plausible pattern with respect to the dimensions analyzed. Key values are within expected ranges from studies on other countries and institutions irrespective of the data sources used.

Switzerland currently publishes more than 31,000 articles per year that are indexed in Scopus. This corresponds to a share of 2% of the world market. In 2015 we find a share of 16% articles published in gold open access journals, which is at the higher end of a typical range for the countries of interest for comparison. Among all Swiss articles, 54% have a Swiss reprint affiliation recorded in Scopus. This compares well to numbers for Switzerland from Web of Science and other countries of similar size.

The ten institutions selected are affiliated to 57% of the Swiss articles in 2015, with articles numbers per institution ranging from less than 50 to more than 5000 per year. Patterns and relative numbers for institutions with less than 500 articles per year (Berner Fachhochschule and Hochschule Luzern) should be interpreted with caution as random influences might be predominant.

The selected institutions show largely similar patterns with respect to their share of gold open access articles – with ETHZ and EPFL at the lower end and the universities at the higher end. The fractions for reprint affiliations are also within expected ranges.

From these data it can be estimated that approximately half of the Swiss articles would be chosen for article processing fees (APCs) to be paid by Switzerland. Using data ¹¹ from the German INTACT project ¹², an average APC of EUR 1,500 per article would be a good estimate for current costs. Based on these assumptions, we would calculate a total APC cost of EUR 26M for international Swiss research articles. Among that a fraction of estimated EUR 4M (16%) already now is spent via gold open access channels.

We hope that the data presented fit into the overall framework of the main project on the analysis of the open access landscape in Switzerland and help to shape strategies for enforcing steps towards this publishing model.

¹¹Jochen Apel et al. (2014ff): Datasets on fee-based open access publishing across German institutions. Bielefeld University. <https://github.com/OpenAPC/openapc-de>

¹²<http://intact-project.org/>

7 Appendix

This appendix includes all the tables from the accompanying MS-Excel file.

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author(s) Max Planck Digital Library
Big Data Analytics Group

Alexander Machado
Laura Hoppmann
Johannes Knaus
Margit Palzenberger

description

this MS-Excel file contains all data tables basic to the analyses described in the main report

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	2 co_art_over_rpany	number of articles per country - subset having any reprint affiliation entry
	3 co_art_over_rp	number of articles per country - with reprint author from respective country
overviews	4 art_over	number of articles per institution - total and publishing group
	5 art_over_rpany	number of articles per institution - total and publishing group
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institution details	8 art_prov_top	number of articles per institution - top 20 publishers
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swiss details	10 art_prov_long	number of articles from Switzerland - all publishers identified
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affiliation matching	12 affiliations	key numbers describing affiliation processing
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src	bibliographic data source
sco	Scopus
ctry	ISO country code
pubgroup	publishing group
oa	articles from journals and publication years identified as gold open access by DOAJ
big 4	articles from subscription journals provided by Elsevier, Wiley, Springer, Taylor
other	articles from subscription journals provided by other publishers
y2001 .. y2015	publication year
y2015*	last publication year (with high probability of incompleteness)
number of articles	number of Scopus items with document type "article" or "review"
reprint affiliation entry	Scopus affiliation entry with the attached author's person_type "correspondence"
OA mode	provider type with respect to open access
oaonly	publisher with predominately gold open access journals
scoap3	open access since 2014 by SCOAP ³ program
rankings	
top 20, top 500	aggregated numbers ranked by the average of the last 3 publications years 2013-2015
inst code	institution identifier
epfl	Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne
eth	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
uba	Universität Basel
ube	Universität Bern
ufr	Université Fribourg
uge	Université Genève
ula	Université Lausanne
uzu	Universität Zürich
bfh	Berner Fachhochschule
hslu	Hochschule Luzern
xhosp	hospitals blacklisted from selected institutions
nn	other institutions in Switzerland

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tab 1 number of articles per country

src	ctry	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015	growth 2014/2005 [%]
number of articles																		
sco	global	big 4	433,664	422,480	444,112	477,606	491,923	557,834	593,102	615,972	642,745	649,587	682,363	704,810	756,413	803,280	735,973	63
sco	global	other	593,128	614,892	641,167	676,539	738,646	771,007	794,106	803,435	849,056	869,527	922,476	951,747	983,710	983,511	907,192	33
sco	global	oa	14,488	19,409	22,431	26,016	33,294	45,211	54,624	72,411	89,633	111,199	142,815	175,383	207,693	228,683	227,230	587
sco	gb	big 4	36,439	35,139	37,543	39,925	40,624	45,847	47,715	48,236	50,072	50,634	53,026	54,487	57,893	57,570	54,195	42
sco	gb	other	34,763	35,856	39,942	42,195	46,642	50,051	52,300	51,321	54,431	55,393	58,364	60,518	61,340	60,471	57,138	30
sco	gb	oa	689	901	1,113	1,383	1,852	2,583	3,541	4,607	5,305	6,383	8,356	10,532	12,962	14,434	16,184	679
sco	de	big 4	35,586	32,347	35,065	37,407	38,893	43,664	44,277	44,928	46,058	47,010	48,767	50,379	53,154	54,996	49,564	41
sco	de	other	34,404	35,292	38,964	41,133	44,741	46,159	45,795	46,628	48,605	50,016	53,062	54,158	52,825	52,080	49,680	16
sco	de	oa	520	710	1,010	1,198	1,686	2,404	3,098	4,137	4,980	6,103	7,787	10,284	12,081	13,165	14,357	681
sco	nl	big 4	10,544	10,583	11,541	12,175	12,910	14,331	15,013	15,280	16,527	17,157	18,027	18,736	20,445	20,710	18,838	60
sco	nl	other	8,790	9,200	10,608	11,418	12,432	13,040	13,319	13,778	15,151	15,944	16,514	17,708	17,145	17,045	16,245	37
sco	nl	oa	201	217	302	300	570	816	1,050	1,297	1,683	2,225	3,046	4,166	4,822	5,339	5,793	837
sco	ch	big 4	6,449	6,347	7,268	7,809	8,033	9,403	9,769	10,078	10,729	10,930	11,787	12,318	12,969	13,644	12,631	70
sco	ch	other	7,038	7,119	8,378	9,284	10,153	10,601	10,879	11,260	11,761	12,443	13,319	14,577	14,514	14,280	13,703	41
sco	ch	oa	228	236	275	378	498	706	964	1,197	1,472	1,948	2,463	3,131	3,768	4,427	4,925	789
sco	at	big 4	4,221	3,980	4,397	4,621	4,785	5,346	5,808	6,035	6,231	6,511	6,851	7,032	7,621	8,088	7,468	69
sco	at	other	3,385	3,600	4,125	4,553	4,618	4,895	5,128	5,377	5,729	5,988	6,631	6,777	6,877	6,787	6,431	47
sco	at	oa	105	128	208	248	339	399	446	647	755	887	1,175	1,531	1,805	2,105	2,408	521
total number of articles																		
sco	global	total	1,041,280	1,056,781	1,107,710	1,180,161	1,263,863	1,374,052	1,441,832	1,491,818	1,581,434	1,630,313	1,747,654	1,831,940	1,947,816	2,015,474	1,870,395	59
sco	gb	total	71,891	71,896	78,598	83,503	89,118	98,481	103,556	104,164	109,808	112,410	119,746	125,537	132,195	132,475	127,517	49
sco	de	total	70,510	68,349	75,039	79,738	85,320	92,227	93,170	95,693	99,643	103,129	109,616	114,821	118,060	120,241	113,601	41
sco	nl	total	19,535	20,000	22,451	23,893	25,912	28,187	29,382	30,355	33,361	35,326	37,587	40,610	42,412	43,094	40,876	66
sco	ch	total	13,715	13,702	15,921	17,471	18,684	20,710	21,612	22,535	23,962	25,321	27,569	30,026	31,251	32,351	31,259	73
sco	at	total	7,711	7,708	8,730	9,422	9,742	10,640	11,382	12,059	12,715	13,386	14,657	15,340	16,303	16,980	16,307	74
global articles share																		
sco	global	tot ratio [%]	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	0
sco	gb	tot ratio [%]	6.9	6.8	7.1	7.1	7.1	7.2	7.2	7.0	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.8	6.6	6.8	-7
sco	de	tot ratio [%]	6.8	6.5	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.7	6.5	6.4	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.1	6.0	6.1	-12
sco	nl	tot ratio [%]	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.0	2.1	2.1	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.1	2.2	4
sco	ch	tot ratio [%]	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.7	9
sco	at	tot ratio [%]	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	9
Open Access share																		
sco	global	oa ratio [%]	1.4	1.8	2.0	2.2	2.6	3.3	3.8	4.9	5.7	6.8	8.2	9.6	10.7	11.3	12.1	331
sco	gb	oa ratio [%]	1.0	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.1	2.6	3.4	4.4	4.8	5.7	7.0	8.4	9.8	10.9	12.7	424
sco	de	oa ratio [%]	0.7	1.0	1.3	1.5	2.0	2.6	3.3	4.3	5.0	5.9	7.1	9.0	10.2	10.9	12.6	454
sco	nl	oa ratio [%]	1.0	1.1	1.3	1.3	2.2	2.9	3.6	4.3	5.0	6.3	8.1	10.3	11.4	12.4	14.2	463
sco	ch	oa ratio [%]	1.7	1.7	1.7	2.2	2.7	3.4	4.5	5.3	6.1	7.7	8.9	10.4	12.1	13.7	15.8	413
sco	at	oa ratio [%]	1.4	1.7	2.4	2.6	3.5	3.8	3.9	5.4	5.9	6.6	8.0	10.0	11.1	12.4	14.8	256
annual increment for total number of articles																		
sco	global	delta [%]		1.5	4.8	6.5	7.1	8.7	4.9	3.5	6.0	3.1	7.2	4.8	6.3	3.5	-7.2	
sco	gb	delta [%]		0.0	9.3	6.2	6.7	10.5	5.2	0.6	5.4	2.4	6.5	4.8	5.3	0.2	-3.7	
sco	de	delta [%]		-3.1	9.8	6.3	7.0	8.1	1.0	2.7	4.1	3.5	6.3	4.7	2.8	1.8	-5.5	
sco	nl	delta [%]		2.4	12.3	6.4	8.5	8.8	4.2	3.3	9.9	5.9	6.4	8.0	4.4	1.6	-5.1	
sco	ch	delta [%]		-0.1	16.2	9.7	6.9	10.8	4.4	4.3	6.3	5.7	8.9	8.9	4.1	3.5	-3.4	
sco	at	delta [%]		0.0	13.3	7.9	3.4	9.2	7.0	5.9	5.4	5.3	9.5	4.7	6.3	4.2	-4.0	

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tab 2 number of articles per country - subset having any reprint affiliation entry

src	ctry	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
number of articles																	
sco	global	big 4	411,341	404,280	428,196	462,791	477,335	543,251	577,375	603,356	632,491	640,072	674,575	697,735	746,557	758,211	699,948
sco	global	other	473,471	485,717	504,355	554,854	633,666	686,787	713,520	739,021	788,614	811,534	866,106	893,260	898,877	769,833	664,012
sco	global	oa	13,503	17,434	20,302	23,454	31,179	43,396	53,356	71,338	88,504	109,818	141,590	174,133	200,893	179,943	178,599
sco	gb	big 4	36,421	35,107	37,531	39,902	40,540	45,753	47,509	48,099	49,959	50,571	52,915	54,422	57,681	55,131	51,976
sco	gb	other	34,642	35,745	39,836	42,049	46,497	49,968	52,201	51,230	54,021	55,222	58,158	60,244	60,176	52,393	45,882
sco	gb	oa	689	899	1,109	1,380	1,850	2,581	3,539	4,602	5,300	6,379	8,350	10,522	12,727	11,334	12,675
sco	de	big 4	35,544	32,279	35,040	37,376	38,826	43,589	44,103	44,879	46,042	46,945	48,697	50,280	52,894	52,711	47,649
sco	de	other	34,305	35,188	38,901	40,952	44,579	46,052	45,701	46,509	48,492	49,908	52,824	53,684	51,658	43,373	36,531
sco	de	oa	519	709	1,008	1,194	1,683	2,400	3,095	4,136	4,978	6,099	7,779	10,274	11,818	10,166	11,038
sco	nl	big 4	10,541	10,574	11,521	12,151	12,894	14,274	14,979	15,263	16,516	17,141	17,996	18,720	20,395	20,112	18,287
sco	nl	other	8,757	9,166	10,572	11,370	12,399	13,018	13,275	13,764	15,099	15,889	16,450	17,586	16,759	14,745	13,055
sco	nl	oa	201	217	301	300	569	815	1,047	1,297	1,682	2,224	3,042	4,163	4,728	4,042	4,297
sco	ch	big 4	6,443	6,339	7,265	7,806	8,022	9,402	9,744	10,075	10,728	10,885	11,785	12,302	12,927	13,123	12,222
sco	ch	other	7,026	7,110	8,371	9,253	10,126	10,585	10,861	11,209	11,736	12,414	13,275	14,461	14,190	11,954	10,245
sco	ch	oa	228	236	273	378	497	706	964	1,196	1,472	1,947	2,461	3,126	3,693	3,454	3,928
sco	at	big 4	4,213	3,973	4,396	4,620	4,780	5,346	5,737	6,028	6,226	6,503	6,848	7,027	7,598	7,770	7,193
sco	at	other	3,370	3,597	4,120	4,541	4,602	4,892	5,124	5,363	5,711	5,980	6,592	6,711	6,685	5,667	4,785
sco	at	oa	105	128	208	246	337	399	446	646	754	887	1,174	1,531	1,755	1,611	1,851
total number of articles with any reprint affiliation																	
sco	global	total rp_any	898,315	907,431	952,853	1,041,099	1,142,180	1,273,434	1,344,251	1,413,715	1,509,609	1,561,424	1,682,271	1,765,128	1,846,327	1,707,987	1,542,559
sco	gb	total rp_any	71,752	71,751	78,476	83,331	88,887	98,302	103,249	103,931	109,280	112,172	119,423	125,188	130,584	118,858	110,533
sco	de	total rp_any	70,368	68,176	74,949	79,522	85,088	92,041	92,899	95,524	99,512	102,952	109,300	114,238	116,370	106,250	95,218
sco	nl	total rp_any	19,499	19,957	22,394	23,821	25,862	28,107	29,301	30,324	33,297	35,254	37,488	40,469	41,882	38,899	35,639
sco	ch	total rp_any	13,697	13,685	15,909	17,437	18,645	20,693	21,569	22,480	23,936	25,246	27,521	29,889	30,810	28,531	26,395
sco	at	total rp_any	7,688	7,698	8,724	9,407	9,719	10,637	11,307	12,037	12,691	13,370	14,614	15,269	16,038	15,048	13,829
ratio of total number of articles with any reprint affiliation to total number																	
sco	global	total rp_any share	86	86	86	88	90	93	93	95	95	96	96	96	95	85	82
sco	gb	total rp_any share	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	87
sco	de	total rp_any share	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	99	88	84
sco	nl	total rp_any share	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	90	87
sco	ch	total rp_any share	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	88	84
sco	at	total rp_any share	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	100	100	100	100	100	98	89	85
global articles share																	
sco	global	tot ratio [%]	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
sco	gb	tot ratio [%]	8.0	7.9	8.2	8.0	7.8	7.7	7.7	7.4	7.2	7.2	7.1	7.1	7.1	7.0	7.2
sco	de	tot ratio [%]	7.8	7.5	7.9	7.6	7.4	7.2	6.9	6.8	6.6	6.6	6.5	6.5	6.3	6.2	6.2
sco	nl	tot ratio [%]	2.2	2.2	2.4	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.2	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.2	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3
sco	ch	tot ratio [%]	1.5	1.5	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7
sco	at	tot ratio [%]	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Open Access share																	
sco	global	oa ratio [%]	1.5	1.9	2.1	2.3	2.7	3.4	4.0	5.0	5.9	7.0	8.4	9.9	10.9	10.5	11.6
sco	gb	oa ratio [%]	1.0	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.1	2.6	3.4	4.4	4.8	5.7	7.0	8.4	9.7	9.5	11.5
sco	de	oa ratio [%]	0.7	1.0	1.3	1.5	2.0	2.6	3.3	4.3	5.0	5.9	7.1	9.0	10.2	9.6	11.6
sco	nl	oa ratio [%]	1.0	1.1	1.3	1.3	2.2	2.9	3.6	4.3	5.1	6.3	8.1	10.3	11.3	10.4	12.1
sco	ch	oa ratio [%]	1.7	1.7	1.7	2.2	2.7	3.4	4.5	5.3	6.1	7.7	8.9	10.5	12.0	12.1	14.9
sco	at	oa ratio [%]	1.4	1.7	2.4	2.6	3.5	3.8	3.9	5.4	5.9	6.6	8.0	10.0	10.9	10.7	13.4
annual increment for total number of articles																	
sco	global	delta [%]		1.0	5.0	9.3	9.7	11.5	5.6	5.2	6.8	3.4	7.7	4.9	4.6	-7.5	-9.7
sco	gb	delta [%]		0.0	9.4	6.2	6.7	10.6	5.0	0.7	5.1	2.6	6.5	4.8	4.3	-9.0	-7.0
sco	de	delta [%]		-3.1	9.9	6.1	7.0	8.2	0.9	2.8	4.2	3.5	6.2	4.5	1.9	-8.7	-10.4
sco	nl	delta [%]		2.3	12.2	6.4	8.6	8.7	4.2	3.5	9.8	5.9	6.3	8.0	3.5	-7.1	-8.4
sco	ch	delta [%]		-0.1	16.3	9.6	6.9	11.0	4.2	4.2	6.5	5.5	9.0	8.6	3.1	-7.4	-7.5
sco	at	delta [%]		0.1	13.3	7.8	3.3	9.4	6.3	6.5	5.4	5.4	9.3	4.5	5.0	-6.2	-8.1

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tab 3 number of articles per country - with reprint author from respective country

src	ctry	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
number of articles																	
sco	global	big 4	411,341	404,280	428,196	462,791	477,335	543,251	577,375	603,356	632,491	640,072	674,575	697,735	746,557	758,211	699,948
sco	global	other	473,471	485,717	504,355	554,854	633,666	686,787	713,520	739,021	788,614	811,534	866,106	893,260	898,877	769,833	664,012
sco	global	oa	13,503	17,434	20,302	23,454	31,179	43,396	53,366	71,338	88,504	109,818	141,590	174,133	200,893	179,943	178,599
sco	gb	big 4	29,989	28,515	29,480	30,546	31,040	34,500	35,429	35,360	36,119	36,563	37,572	38,110	39,517	36,390	33,527
sco	gb	other	29,265	30,130	31,090	32,330	35,570	38,002	39,203	37,823	39,036	39,679	41,719	42,605	42,232	36,299	31,446
sco	gb	oa	477	690	791	983	1,272	1,748	2,394	3,032	3,278	4,012	4,997	6,283	7,549	6,588	7,168
sco	de	big 4	28,970	25,714	27,220	28,798	29,781	32,897	33,029	33,389	33,827	34,433	35,129	35,899	37,215	37,254	32,987
sco	de	other	28,720	29,614	30,180	31,209	33,887	34,440	33,385	34,114	34,471	35,416	37,459	37,415	35,500	29,796	25,243
sco	de	oa	369	533	737	845	1,176	1,723	2,170	2,835	3,387	4,137	5,302	6,975	7,942	6,789	7,021
sco	nl	big 4	8,234	8,343	8,642	9,024	9,689	10,404	10,927	11,186	11,748	11,934	12,335	12,551	13,398	13,137	11,775
sco	nl	other	6,933	7,293	7,524	7,982	8,696	9,020	9,022	9,370	9,980	10,402	10,680	10,979	10,438	9,234	8,000
sco	nl	oa	157	151	206	206	407	534	701	844	1,093	1,433	1,954	2,679	2,992	2,419	2,467
sco	ch	big 4	4,519	4,349	4,683	5,080	5,138	5,928	6,035	6,197	6,598	6,336	6,763	7,009	7,344	7,192	6,544
sco	ch	other	5,242	5,298	5,476	5,922	6,471	6,710	6,635	6,771	6,884	7,246	7,612	8,178	8,102	6,918	5,835
sco	ch	oa	185	177	200	274	330	465	599	712	828	1,128	1,368	1,693	2,046	1,802	1,941
sco	at	big 4	3,226	3,046	3,297	3,337	3,305	3,716	3,905	4,054	4,063	4,234	4,346	4,386	4,430	4,539	4,086
sco	at	other	2,625	2,854	2,927	3,106	3,051	3,301	3,334	3,425	3,586	3,551	4,004	3,874	3,830	3,307	2,705
sco	at	oa	87	104	166	181	229	309	290	429	459	553	692	859	986	883	966
total number of articles with reprint affiliation from respective country																	
sco	global	total rp	898,315	907,431	952,853	1,041,099	1,142,180	1,273,434	1,344,251	1,413,715	1,509,609	1,561,424	1,682,271	1,765,128	1,846,327	1,707,987	1,542,559
sco	gb	total rp	59,731	59,335	61,361	63,859	67,882	74,250	77,026	76,215	78,433	80,254	84,288	86,998	89,298	79,277	72,141
sco	de	total rp	58,059	55,861	58,137	60,852	64,844	69,060	68,584	70,338	71,685	73,986	77,890	80,289	80,657	73,839	65,251
sco	nl	total rp	15,324	15,787	16,372	17,212	18,792	19,958	20,650	21,400	22,821	23,769	24,969	26,209	26,828	24,790	22,242
sco	ch	total rp	9,946	9,824	10,359	11,276	11,939	13,103	13,269	13,680	14,310	14,710	15,743	16,880	17,492	15,912	14,320
sco	at	total rp	5,938	6,004	6,390	6,624	6,585	7,326	7,529	7,908	8,108	8,338	9,042	9,119	9,246	8,729	7,757
ratio of total number of articles with reprint affiliation from respective to total number of articles with any reprint affiliation																	
sco	global	total rp share	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
sco	gb	total rp share	83	83	78	77	76	76	75	73	72	72	71	69	68	67	65
sco	de	total rp share	83	82	78	77	76	75	74	74	72	72	71	70	69	69	69
sco	nl	total rp share	79	79	73	72	73	71	70	71	69	67	67	65	64	64	62
sco	ch	total rp share	73	72	65	65	64	63	62	61	60	58	57	56	57	56	54
sco	at	total rp share	77	78	73	70	68	69	67	66	64	62	62	60	58	58	56

comparison with data paper Palzenberger (2014) "Number of Scholarly Articles per Country" (data based on Web of Science) DOI 10.17617/1.2 including yet unpublished data for 2014

	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	
total number of WoS Articles												
wos	gb	76,996	79,407	83,494	87,402	89,914	93,082	96,739	101,345	105,907	111,968	111,280
wos	de	73,753	76,980	78,962	81,208	84,520	88,132	91,597	96,422	100,603	104,216	104,923
wos	nl	22,521	24,213	25,198	26,176	27,813	30,185	32,348	34,008	36,613	38,411	38,719
wos	ch	16,611	17,136	18,570	19,291	20,406	21,807	23,032	24,774	26,526	27,956	28,760
wos	at	8,831	9,033	9,249	9,984	10,699	11,174	11,965	12,914	13,504	14,261	14,780
total number of WoS articles with reprint author from respective country												
wos	gb	58,281	59,668	61,984	63,639	64,071	65,153	67,069	68,954	71,090	73,777	70,510
wos	de	54,978	56,994	57,950	58,832	60,673	62,619	64,133	66,875	69,235	70,678	70,673
wos	nl	15,952	17,309	17,658	18,099	19,245	20,337	21,361	22,292	23,367	24,178	23,905
wos	ch	10,680	10,969	11,739	11,747	12,220	12,905	13,234	14,023	14,880	15,413	15,490
wos	at	6,099	6,041	6,135	6,510	6,840	7,034	7,275	7,695	7,900	7,982	8,239
share of reprint authors from respective country												
wos	gb	76	75	74	73	71	70	69	68	67	66	63
wos	de	75	74	73	72	72	71	70	69	69	68	67
wos	nl	71	71	70	69	69	67	66	66	64	63	62
wos	ch	64	64	63	61	60	59	57	57	56	55	54
wos	at	69	67	66	65	64	63	61	60	59	56	56

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tab 4 number of articles per institution - total and publishing group

inst code	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015	share [%]
switzerland	oa	235	249	291	387	516	725	984	1,211	1,481	1,998	2,507	3,179	3,859	4,613	5,040	
switzerland	big 4	6,644	6,541	7,408	7,973	8,213	9,617	10,052	10,369	10,962	11,213	12,044	12,609	13,300	14,100	13,151	
switzerland	other	6,960	7,066	8,387	9,286	10,108	10,545	10,874	11,358	11,704	12,336	13,188	14,436	14,327	14,016	13,174	
switzerland	-total-	13,839	13,856	16,086	17,646	18,837	20,887	21,910	22,938	24,147	25,547	27,739	30,224	31,486	32,729	31,365	100
epfl	oa	6	7	14	15	37	47	84	78	114	138	164	223	292	352	397	
epfl	big 4	438	443	583	654	613	799	795	900	880	916	911	1,048	1,148	1,181	1,145	
epfl	other	356	431	485	658	792	934	1,000	1,111	1,102	1,113	1,297	1,489	1,645	1,582	1,515	
epfl	-total-	800	881	1,082	1,327	1,442	1,780	1,879	2,089	2,096	2,167	2,372	2,760	3,085	3,115	3,057	10
eth	oa	19	26	33	31	59	92	104	169	203	322	332	399	517	660	732	
eth	big 4	1,132	1,078	1,286	1,375	1,409	1,608	1,769	1,726	1,793	1,816	1,955	2,240	2,244	2,353	2,198	
eth	other	854	866	1,041	1,206	1,327	1,478	1,549	1,555	1,766	1,882	2,001	2,333	2,333	2,394	2,156	
eth	-total-	2,005	1,970	2,360	2,612	2,795	3,178	3,422	3,450	3,762	4,020	4,288	4,972	5,094	5,407	5,086	16
uba	oa	7	2	12	19	20	35	52	68	87	170	221	285	332	385	409	
uba	big 4	380	362	464	416	431	480	458	502	511	581	684	719	794	777	734	
uba	other	303	337	389	504	527	466	486	513	527	630	640	704	804	865	729	
uba	-total-	690	701	865	939	978	981	996	1,083	1,125	1,381	1,545	1,708	1,930	2,027	1,872	6
ube	oa	23	18	26	24	40	51	86	80	107	144	172	237	328	491	524	
ube	big 4	452	488	561	607	613	711	692	737	786	857	940	953	1,024	1,181	1,077	
ube	other	371	360	477	470	580	605	591	675	688	698	798	889	843	925	872	
ube	-total-	846	866	1,064	1,101	1,233	1,367	1,369	1,492	1,581	1,699	1,910	2,079	2,195	2,597	2,473	8
ufr	oa	1	3	5	5	7	8	8	14	21	31	40	43	73	81	136	
ufr	big 4	98	102	118	115	123	120	147	137	163	188	201	197	204	243	235	
ufr	other	91	95	108	122	120	158	165	163	202	215	244	249	255	264	278	
ufr	-total-	190	200	231	242	250	286	320	314	386	434	485	489	532	588	649	2
uge	oa	12	8	17	24	26	43	66	69	97	117	150	195	259	374	386	
uge	big 4	405	417	481	537	531	616	616	590	708	716	777	904	904	941	850	
uge	other	516	515	650	702	785	822	791	815	942	967	1,124	1,310	1,159	1,149	1,052	
uge	-total-	933	940	1,148	1,263	1,342	1,481	1,473	1,474	1,747	1,800	1,985	2,282	2,322	2,464	2,288	7
ula	oa	7	13	13	25	31	36	47	54	78	93	151	150	203	204	247	
ula	big 4	332	300	335	360	297	391	434	406	436	452	484	581	622	663	658	
ula	other	319	307	411	432	422	400	364	451	462	446	479	507	509	498	503	
ula	-total-	658	620	759	817	750	827	845	911	976	991	1,114	1,238	1,334	1,365	1,408	4
uzu	oa	20	17	26	37	36	53	93	141	141	234	308	397	490	659	655	
uzu	big 4	547	568	632	668	775	868	941	946	1,065	1,102	1,233	1,348	1,323	1,477	1,411	
uzu	other	479	480	578	715	815	809	931	1,019	1,055	1,159	1,246	1,430	1,436	1,381	1,251	
uzu	-total-	1,046	1,065	1,236	1,420	1,626	1,730	1,965	2,106	2,261	2,495	2,787	3,175	3,249	3,517	3,317	11
bfh	oa	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	4	5	18	12	28	
bfh	big 4	1	0	0	2	2	4	2	11	13	15	19	44	47	54	36	
bfh	other	4	1	1	2	4	2	11	21	25	20	14	27	36	43	28	
bfh	-total-	5	1	2	4	6	6	15	33	40	35	37	76	101	109	92	0
hslu	oa	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	9	
hslu	big 4	1	1	0	0	5	3	2	6	6	3	8	9	8	16	20	
hslu	other	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	7	3	4	3	8	9	10	13	
hslu	-total-	1	1	0	1	5	4	6	14	10	8	11	17	19	29	42	0
xhosp	oa	94	66	96	117	180	232	261	293	375	502	716	910	1,048	1,012	1,133	
xhosp	big 4	1,383	1,423	1,451	1,607	1,895	2,082	2,160	2,329	2,420	2,581	2,833	3,033	3,144	3,032	2,991	
xhosp	other	1,858	1,752	2,045	2,234	2,414	2,557	2,556	2,595	2,657	2,857	2,924	3,057	3,006	2,906	2,888	
xhosp	-total-	3,335	3,241	3,592	3,958	4,489	4,871	4,977	5,217	5,452	5,940	6,473	7,000	7,198	6,950	7,012	22
nn	oa	82	135	131	203	243	397	552	657	834	1,018	1,326	1,654	1,946	2,647	2,845	
nn	big 4	3,122	2,944	3,412	3,780	4,002	4,852	5,070	5,360	5,800	5,933	6,462	6,431	7,025	7,481	6,224	
nn	other	3,188	3,283	4,312	4,858	5,113	5,406	5,616	5,928	6,106	6,762	7,158	7,760	7,458	6,932	6,066	
nn	-total-	6,392	6,362	7,855	8,841	9,358	10,655	11,238	11,945	12,740	13,713	14,946	15,845	16,429	17,060	15,135	48

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tab 5 number of articles per institution - total and publishing group

inst code	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015	share [%]
switzerland	oa	235	247	286	386	515	724	984	1,211	1,480	1,997	2,505	3,173	3,780	3,539	4,029	
switzerland	big 4	6,631	6,521	7,395	7,962	8,194	9,615	10,019	10,351	10,955	11,160	12,039	12,561	13,237	13,455	12,644	
switzerland	other	6,899	7,026	8,331	9,197	10,027	10,516	10,864	11,321	11,686	12,310	13,146	14,352	14,001	11,549	9,720	
switzerland	-total-	13765	13,794	16,012	17,545	18,736	20,855	21,867	22,883	24,121	25,467	27,690	30,086	31,018	28,543	26,393	100
epfl	oa	6	7	13	15	37	47	84	78	114	138	164	223	271	232	312	
epfl	big 4	437	442	582	652	613	799	795	899	880	884	910	1,046	1,145	1,113	1,103	
epfl	other	356	431	484	655	788	932	997	1,110	1,099	1,109	1,292	1,471	1,609	1,212	899	
epfl	-total-	799	880	1,079	1,322	1,438	1,778	1,876	2,087	2,093	2,131	2,366	2,740	3,025	2,557	2,314	9
eth	oa	19	26	31	31	59	92	104	169	203	321	332	398	499	500	574	
eth	big 4	1,128	1,076	1,286	1,374	1,406	1,607	1,767	1,725	1,792	1,807	1,953	2,232	2,232	2,201	2,091	
eth	other	848	864	1,040	1,201	1,316	1,475	1,549	1,549	1,764	1,876	1,994	2,325	2,263	1,864	1,449	
eth	-total-	1995	1,966	2,357	2,606	2,781	3,174	3,420	3,443	3,759	4,004	4,279	4,955	4,994	4,565	4,114	16
uba	oa	7	2	12	19	20	35	52	68	87	170	221	285	331	309	341	
uba	big 4	377	359	462	413	431	480	458	502	511	580	684	719	789	743	711	
uba	other	292	328	381	479	515	463	486	513	527	629	638	701	789	742	576	
uba	-total-	676	689	855	911	966	978	996	1,083	1,125	1,379	1,543	1,705	1,909	1,794	1,628	6
ube	oa	23	18	25	24	40	50	86	80	107	144	172	237	327	358	393	
ube	big 4	451	484	555	602	611	711	692	737	786	856	940	952	1,015	1,122	1,021	
ube	other	358	349	463	455	561	599	591	674	687	695	793	870	805	751	649	
ube	-total-	832	851	1,043	1,081	1,212	1,360	1,369	1,491	1,580	1,695	1,905	2,059	2,147	2,231	2,063	8
ufr	oa	1	3	5	5	7	8	8	14	21	31	40	43	71	63	108	
ufr	big 4	98	102	118	115	122	120	147	137	163	188	201	197	202	227	223	
ufr	other	90	93	108	122	120	158	164	163	202	214	242	248	251	219	204	
ufr	-total-	189	198	231	242	249	286	319	314	386	433	483	488	524	509	535	2
uge	oa	12	8	17	23	26	43	66	69	97	117	150	195	254	283	296	
uge	big 4	404	416	481	537	531	615	615	590	706	714	711	774	899	898	825	
uge	other	512	510	645	696	785	821	790	812	942	965	1,117	1,291	1,119	924	671	
uge	-total-	928	934	1,143	1,256	1,342	1,479	1,471	1,471	1,745	1,796	1,978	2,260	2,272	2,105	1,792	7
ula	oa	7	12	13	25	31	36	47	54	78	93	151	149	200	137	206	
ula	big 4	332	298	335	360	296	391	434	406	436	452	484	581	618	629	629	
ula	other	315	305	406	423	417	397	363	451	461	445	478	504	499	410	408	
ula	-total-	654	615	754	808	744	824	844	911	975	990	1,113	1,234	1,317	1,176	1,243	5
uzu	oa	20	16	25	37	36	53	93	141	141	233	306	396	480	491	515	
uzu	big 4	545	568	629	667	773	868	941	946	1,065	1,101	1,232	1,321	1,318	1,387	1,341	
uzu	other	466	473	561	705	798	807	931	1,016	1,054	1,158	1,241	1,418	1,394	1,159	1,006	
uzu	-total-	1031	1,057	1,215	1,409	1,607	1,728	1,965	2,103	2,260	2,492	2,779	3,135	3,192	3,037	2,862	11
bfh	oa	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	4	5	18	9	19	
bfh	big 4	1	0	0	2	2	4	2	11	13	15	19	44	47	52	36	
bfh	other	4	1	1	2	4	2	11	21	25	20	14	26	34	37	26	
bfh	-total-	5	1	2	4	6	6	15	33	40	35	37	75	99	98	81	0
hslu	oa	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	2	2	9	
hslu	big 4	1	1	0	0	1	3	2	6	6	3	8	9	8	12	17	
hslu	other	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	7	3	4	3	8	9	9	13	
hslu	-total-	1	1	0	1	1	4	6	14	10	8	11	17	19	23	39	0
xhosp	oa	94	66	96	117	180	232	261	293	374	502	716	909	1,044	813	862	
xhosp	big 4	1,382	1,422	1,451	1,607	1,894	2,082	2,160	2,329	2,420	2,580	2,833	3,033	3,139	2,996	2,960	
xhosp	other	1,858	1,752	2,045	2,233	2,411	2,557	2,555	2,594	2,651	2,855	2,924	3,055	2,984	2,688	2,602	
xhosp	-total-	3334	3,240	3,592	3,957	4,485	4,871	4,976	5,216	5,445	5,937	6,473	6,997	7,167	6,497	6,424	24
nn	oa	82	135	131	203	242	397	552	657	834	1,018	1,325	1,652	1,915	2,070	2,310	
nn	big 4	3,121	2,937	3,410	3,780	3,994	4,852	5,040	5,343	5,796	5,925	6,456	6,419	6,996	7,221	5,977	
nn	other	3,179	3,281	4,307	4,839	5,100	5,395	5,610	5,900	6,098	6,740	7,115	7,697	7,248	5,726	4,292	
nn	-total-	6382	6,353	7,848	8,822	9,336	10,644	11,202	11,900	12,728	13,683	14,896	15,768	16,159	15,017	12,579	48

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tab 6 number of articles with reprint affiliation for respective institution - total and publishing group

inst_code	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015	share [%]
switzerland	oa	199	195	214	292	362	503	659	759	896	1,244	1,473	1,837	2,240	1,988	2,079	
switzerland	big 4	4,916	4,750	5,083	5,524	5,647	6,520	6,702	6,888	7,348	7,133	7,618	7,861	8,256	8,089	7,121	
switzerland	other	5,301	5,436	5,766	6,264	6,824	7,129	7,188	7,257	7,426	7,788	8,196	8,790	8,559	7,081	5,671	
switzerland	-total-	10416	10,381	11,063	12,080	12,833	14,152	14,549	14,904	15,670	16,165	17,287	18,488	19,055	17,158	14,871	100
epfl	oa	5	5	9	7	22	20	40	34	40	65	77	96	124	95	133	
epfl	big 4	275	273	376	403	357	450	447	456	517	467	456	525	535	529	545	
epfl	other	232	265	270	352	423	489	479	434	482	518	654	677	734	538	417	
epfl	-total-	512	543	655	762	802	959	966	924	1,039	1,050	1,187	1,298	1,393	1,162	1,095	7
eth	oa	14	10	19	18	37	44	57	87	84	161	137	192	225	184	212	
eth	big 4	695	684	760	834	793	917	940	978	996	937	1,021	1,098	1,083	1,017	896	
eth	other	551	530	569	683	729	821	809	830	927	972	936	1,082	1,054	899	692	
eth	-total-	1260	1,224	1,348	1,535	1,559	1,782	1,806	1,895	2,007	2,070	2,094	2,372	2,362	2,100	1,800	12
uba	oa	5	1	6	8	12	17	23	31	37	51	56	69	88	69	84	
uba	big 4	232	187	244	218	206	223	217	264	250	225	278	282	308	299	271	
uba	other	165	209	176	226	223	216	230	219	242	281	286	289	362	298	235	
uba	-total-	402	397	426	452	441	456	470	514	529	557	620	640	758	666	590	4
ube	oa	14	12	20	14	27	23	45	34	48	72	75	108	134	154	125	
ube	big 4	268	270	303	295	320	356	372	371	379	390	428	408	429	495	409	
ube	other	242	233	261	229	263	320	273	300	321	294	329	339	370	311	274	
ube	-total-	524	515	584	538	610	699	690	705	748	756	832	855	933	960	808	5
ufr	oa	0	3	5	1	3	4	1	6	13	13	16	25	34	25	33	
ufr	big 4	60	68	67	63	66	65	79	77	91	84	98	97	97	93	107	
ufr	other	53	64	52	65	65	95	87	87	87	110	114	122	141	118	104	
ufr	-total-	113	135	124	129	134	164	167	170	191	207	228	244	272	236	244	2
uge	oa	7	6	7	12	12	22	43	31	46	54	62	81	106	110	102	
uge	big 4	255	254	251	297	267	308	306	311	345	326	317	337	383	395	379	
uge	other	297	331	320	324	392	381	363	348	416	396	461	534	473	405	296	
uge	-total-	559	591	578	633	671	711	712	690	807	776	840	952	962	910	777	5
ula	oa	6	7	3	15	16	22	14	26	32	43	47	59	87	53	86	
ula	big 4	210	162	164	163	128	199	216	204	205	204	228	260	269	301	264	
ula	other	191	168	168	172	186	178	166	190	208	214	210	236	233	194	188	
ula	-total-	407	337	335	350	330	399	396	420	445	461	485	555	589	548	538	4
uzu	oa	17	10	11	24	14	27	51	71	66	103	161	151	220	181	174	
uzu	big 4	333	366	349	370	393	461	465	441	514	499	556	584	576	596	538	
uzu	other	271	289	290	342	370	372	437	426	473	526	540	583	551	535	413	
uzu	-total-	621	665	650	736	777	860	953	938	1,053	1,128	1,257	1,318	1,347	1,312	1,125	8
bfh	oa	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	3	10	
bfh	big 4	1	0	0	1	0	4	0	4	4	10	6	14	15	16	11	
bfh	other	1	1	0	0	1	2	3	15	16	11	3	14	17	13	13	
bfh	-total-	2	1	0	1	1	6	3	19	20	21	9	28	38	32	34	0
hslu	oa	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	
hslu	big 4	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	2	1	2	5	3	8	7	
hslu	other	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	7	3	1	2	4	3	4	7	
hslu	-total-	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	12	5	2	4	9	6	13	17	0
xhosp	oa	85	57	65	86	101	147	164	184	198	287	374	444	509	387	380	
xhosp	big 4	917	923	910	999	1,142	1,210	1,276	1,346	1,330	1,374	1,440	1,505	1,572	1,413	1,376	
xhosp	other	1,408	1,368	1,414	1,448	1,527	1,566	1,524	1,587	1,494	1,570	1,577	1,643	1,590	1,345	1,264	
xhosp	-total-	2410	2,348	2,389	2,533	2,770	2,923	2,964	3,117	3,022	3,231	3,391	3,592	3,671	3,145	3,020	20
nn	oa	46	84	69	106	118	177	221	254	332	395	468	612	707	726	737	
nn	big 4	1,670	1,563	1,659	1,881	1,975	2,326	2,383	2,432	2,715	2,616	2,788	2,746	2,986	2,927	2,318	
nn	other	1,890	1,978	2,246	2,423	2,645	2,688	2,816	2,814	2,757	2,895	3,084	3,267	3,031	2,421	1,768	
nn	-total-	3606	3,625	3,974	4,410	4,738	5,191	5,420	5,500	5,804	5,906	6,340	6,625	6,724	6,074	4,823	32

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tab 7 share [%] of articles with reprint affiliation for respective institution - total and publishing group

inst code	pubgroup	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
switzerland	oa	85	79	75	76	70	69	67	63	61	62	59	58	59	56	52
switzerland	big 4	74	73	69	69	69	68	67	67	67	64	63	63	62	60	56
switzerland	other	77	77	69	68	68	68	66	64	64	63	62	61	61	61	58
switzerland	-total-	76	75	69	69	68	68	67	65	65	63	62	61	61	60	56
epfl	oa	83	71	69	47	59	43	48	44	35	47	47	43	46	41	43
epfl	big 4	63	62	65	62	58	56	56	51	59	53	50	50	47	48	49
epfl	other	65	61	56	54	54	52	48	39	44	47	51	46	46	44	46
epfl	-total-	64	62	61	58	56	54	51	44	50	49	50	47	46	45	47
eth	oa	74	38	61	58	63	48	55	51	41	50	41	48	45	37	37
eth	big 4	62	64	59	61	56	57	53	57	56	52	52	49	49	46	43
eth	other	65	61	55	57	55	56	52	54	53	52	47	47	47	48	48
eth	-total-	63	62	57	59	56	56	53	55	53	52	49	48	47	46	44
uba	oa	71	50	50	42	60	49	44	46	43	30	25	24	27	22	25
uba	big 4	62	52	53	53	48	46	47	53	49	39	41	39	39	40	38
uba	other	57	64	46	47	43	47	47	43	46	45	45	41	46	40	41
uba	-total-	59	58	50	50	46	47	47	47	47	40	40	38	40	37	36
ube	oa	61	67	80	58	68	46	52	43	45	50	44	46	41	43	32
ube	big 4	59	56	55	49	52	50	54	50	48	46	46	43	42	44	40
ube	other	68	67	56	50	47	53	46	45	47	42	41	39	46	41	42
ube	-total-	63	61	56	50	50	51	50	47	47	45	44	42	43	43	39
ufr	oa	0	100	100	20	43	50	13	43	62	42	40	58	48	40	31
ufr	big 4	61	67	57	55	54	54	54	56	56	45	49	49	48	41	48
ufr	other	59	69	48	53	54	60	53	53	43	51	47	49	56	54	51
ufr	-total-	60	68	54	53	54	57	52	54	49	48	47	50	52	46	46
uge	oa	58	75	41	52	46	51	65	45	47	46	41	42	42	39	34
uge	big 4	63	61	52	55	50	50	50	53	49	46	45	44	43	44	46
uge	other	58	65	50	47	50	46	46	43	44	41	41	41	42	44	44
uge	-total-	60	63	51	50	50	48	48	47	46	43	42	42	42	43	43
ula	oa	86	58	23	60	52	61	30	48	41	46	31	40	44	39	42
ula	big 4	63	54	49	45	43	51	50	50	47	45	47	45	44	48	42
ula	other	61	55	41	41	45	45	46	42	45	48	44	47	47	47	46
ula	-total-	62	55	44	43	44	48	47	46	46	47	44	45	45	47	43
uzu	oa	85	63	44	65	39	51	55	50	47	44	53	38	46	37	34
uzu	big 4	61	64	55	55	51	53	49	47	48	45	45	44	44	43	40
uzu	other	58	61	52	49	46	46	47	42	45	45	44	41	40	46	41
uzu	-total-	60	63	53	52	48	50	48	45	47	45	45	42	42	43	39
bfh	oa			0				0	0	0		0		33	33	53
bfh	big 4	100			50	0	100	0	36	31	67	32	32	32	31	31
bfh	other	25	100	0	0	25	100	27	71	64	55	21	54	50	35	50
bfh	-total-	40	100	0	25	17	100	20	58	50	60	24	37	38	33	42
hslu	oa				100				100	0	0			0	50	33
hslu	big 4	0	0			0	33	50	67	33	33	25	56	38	67	41
hslu	other						100	25	100	100	25	67	50	33	44	54
hslu	-total-	0	0		100	0	50	33	86	50	25	36	53	32	57	44
xhosp	oa	90	86	68	74	56	63	63	63	53	57	52	49	49	48	44
xhosp	big 4	66	65	63	62	60	58	59	58	55	53	51	50	50	47	46
xhosp	other	76	78	69	65	63	61	60	61	56	55	54	54	53	50	49
xhosp	-total-	72	72	67	64	62	60	60	60	56	54	52	51	51	48	47
nn	oa	56	62	53	52	49	45	40	39	40	39	35	37	37	35	32
nn	big 4	54	53	49	50	49	48	47	46	47	44	43	43	43	41	39
nn	other	59	60	52	50	52	50	50	48	45	43	43	42	42	42	41
nn	-total-	57	57	51	50	51	49	48	46	46	43	43	42	42	40	38

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tab 8 number of articles per institution - top 20 publishers

inst code	provider	OA mode	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
switzerland	1 Elsevier		3,433	3,249	3,504	3,886	4,013	4,865	5,066	5,086	5,352	5,189	5,755	5,900	6,669	6,825	6,958
switzerland	2 Wiley		1,948	1,975	2,167	2,299	2,398	2,726	2,775	2,915	3,176	3,242	3,360	3,463	3,511	3,624	3,744
switzerland	3 Springer		1,488	1,475	1,900	1,969	1,871	2,143	2,309	2,451	2,429	2,756	2,951	3,438	3,334	3,924	2,789
switzerland	4 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	1	8	30	47	141	197	283	383	623	908	1,090	1,042	937
switzerland	5 ACS		402	489	508	582	649	660	650	729	779	823	821	937	999	989	1,040
switzerland	6 APS		399	418	482	567	647	658	732	815	803	837	930	992	925	923	829
switzerland	7 NPG		221	154	243	286	278	330	331	378	400	424	444	610	695	756	1,023
switzerland	8 OUP		342	312	380	407	489	463	536	559	662	581	718	803	771	949	748
switzerland	9 BMC	oaonly	30	54	59	90	130	225	304	367	406	535	647	648	708	736	782
switzerland	10 IEEE		197	213	234	246	293	341	319	329	340	357	436	534	588	628	542
switzerland	11 Taylor		153	176	200	200	238	249	280	264	362	458	479	551	568	581	592
switzerland	12 LWW		400	355	424	487	463	495	524	531	543	553	588	589	604	534	568
switzerland	13 RSC		82	91	137	139	153	130	173	195	255	307	415	473	486	572	615
switzerland	14 IOP		147	137	184	199	227	281	361	410	420	409	451	504	522	472	474
switzerland	15 EMH		273	334	323	372	437	441	403	380	353	430	386	426	456	357	391
switzerland	16 AIP		191	216	211	230	312	338	329	335	333	309	319	342	363	426	377
switzerland	17 Sage		71	82	77	119	118	151	178	231	224	221	266	336	337	348	389
switzerland	18 Hogrefe		310	257	319	313	361	353	319	262	245	275	277	276	329	296	287
switzerland	19 Karger		200	172	173	169	236	231	260	237	207	265	248	362	290	299	256
switzerland	20 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	23	43	76	145	219	301	299
switzerland	21 others		3,552	3,697	4,560	5,078	5,494	5,760	5,918	6,259	6,552	7,150	7,549	7,987	8,022	8,147	7,725
eth	1 Elsevier		566	496	557	649	641	793	862	840	819	839	934	944	1,067	1,140	1,160
eth	2 Wiley		355	374	399	400	455	463	496	512	558	566	575	657	655	663	691
eth	3 Springer		226	228	332	360	314	349	422	365	402	401	447	681	557	582	408
eth	4 ACS		123	146	137	165	206	204	201	216	237	244	257	319	332	340	343
eth	5 APS		63	73	91	122	114	125	160	159	168	182	223	271	232	253	214
eth	6 NPG		25	11	25	33	42	36	57	54	71	81	82	137	160	171	239
eth	7 RSC		27	23	41	39	38	35	54	56	72	83	127	149	130	178	193
eth	8 IEEE		55	52	74	73	72	89	85	97	111	105	110	114	158	182	142
eth	9 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	0	6	9	12	34	41	53	73	113	142	141	112
eth	10 AIP		55	71	63	67	87	111	85	99	104	99	91	94	117	139	137
eth	11 OUP		36	27	29	57	63	58	62	50	78	64	96	122	122	156	106
eth	12 IOP		26	19	21	34	39	54	71	70	95	104	103	91	98	89	89
eth	13 Taylor		26	27	35	22	42	50	46	43	59	70	91	98	97	95	82
eth	14 Copernicus	oaonly	1	3	10	6	14	30	19	30	45	59	77	58	73	86	95
eth	15 AAS		1	6	15	11	28	24	54	30	43	64	55	52	55	78	69
eth	16 BMC	oaonly	2	6	4	5	14	14	25	36	34	53	54	49	64	60	51
eth	17 GSW		13	26	20	37	28	32	47	23	34	35	43	47	57	49	40
eth	18 NAS		18	12	14	21	23	14	20	19	44	23	29	39	53	46	25
eth	19 Sage		2	3	8	9	7	7	19	18	27	18	17	28	34	31	41
eth	20 OSA		25	10	19	18	34	26	32	38	38	34	28	29	32	42	31
eth	21 others		360	357	466	484	528	655	593	661	682	843	776	880	859	886	818
uba	1 Elsevier		182	197	222	190	206	212	186	216	209	313	312	341	408	392	409
uba	2 Wiley		144	121	147	140	122	172	147	177	197	170	225	215	221	225	215
uba	3 Springer		65	61	88	92	91	95	120	101	102	99	145	159	155	181	137
uba	4 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	0	4	8	8	13	21	41	84	107	115	115	96
uba	5 BMC	oaonly	0	1	1	7	6	8	13	22	28	62	59	66	88	81	86
uba	6 NPG		15	5	22	19	16	14	23	13	33	32	35	40	69	76	100
uba	7 ACS		23	34	38	45	42	36	40	41	37	56	63	60	83	77	79
uba	8 APS		37	27	47	42	60	45	48	58	58	55	62	82	74	88	66
uba	9 RSC		11	13	17	24	23	16	23	30	28	29	42	30	52	55	41
uba	10 OUP		17	19	19	18	17	30	24	29	26	26	45	48	39	65	35
uba	11 Taylor		6	3	18	8	24	13	13	16	13	12	18	24	38	27	22
uba	12 LWW		10	13	13	16	20	20	15	31	21	27	25	18	24	28	23
uba	13 ASM		4	10	8	14	19	8	12	10	8	14	22	22	15	22	26

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inst code	provider	OA mode	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
uba	14 AIP		13	9	15	14	16	14	16	9	9	13	18	16	13	28	20
uba	15 IOP		5	9	8	17	11	11	20	19	18	17	13	16	16	19	23
uba	16 Karger		10	7	4	7	34	10	11	20	7	12	10	13	16	21	20
uba	17 NAS		8	6	9	10	22	9	15	11	15	8	13	18	19	25	11
uba	18 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	3	10	9	27	18	
uba	19 Sage		1	4	2	6	0	6	10	7	13	22	12	19	17	20	15
uba	20 Thieme		6	4	8	12	10	14	10	11	10	12	9	19	14	22	15
uba	21 others		133	158	179	258	235	240	242	249	270	361	330	385	445	433	415
ube	1 Elsevier		206	211	230	249	272	328	312	326	315	363	471	463	529	563	525
ube	2 Wiley		182	177	204	238	239	213	238	236	289	278	281	298	278	356	353
ube	3 Springer		72	94	124	139	107	171	127	175	188	221	210	260	262	335	275
ube	4 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	1	2	1	18	16	30	31	50	70	96	112	112
ube	5 NPG		10	5	12	14	18	19	12	25	28	16	21	40	44	49	82
ube	6 BMC	oaonly	4	5	3	3	6	16	27	22	29	33	33	37	44	74	54
ube	7 APS		11	7	9	14	23	10	11	23	35	32	56	82	41	59	71
ube	8 OUP		16	13	28	21	31	28	36	47	37	41	36	58	47	70	51
ube	9 Copernicus	oaonly	3	3	1	3	1	9	17	8	20	21	29	32	55	50	61
ube	10 ACS		23	38	25	31	35	32	26	41	32	42	46	45	47	46	60
ube	11 Taylor		6	15	16	6	13	16	33	20	19	34	36	44	43	37	53
ube	12 LWW		16	18	30	28	26	26	30	30	35	31	38	42	34	44	41
ube	13 Sage		5	6	9	11	13	17	24	14	17	19	26	27	34	23	38
ube	14 IOP		14	7	8	6	8	7	15	17	17	9	16	17	23	39	22
ube	15 RSC		2	5	11	11	11	10	11	11	13	19	24	14	27	31	25
ube	16 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	15	10	25	30
ube	17 CUP		6	5	7	8	7	8	11	7	13	16	12	14	15	28	19
ube	18 Karger		18	11	11	10	8	31	17	16	13	13	21	18	14	26	17
ube	19 ASM		10	7	21	13	19	19	21	19	11	17	19	14	16	14	23
ube	20 EDP		2	1	1	6	5	8	8	5	10	23	11	10	8	8	35
ube	21 others		240	238	314	289	389	398	375	433	429	438	473	479	528	608	526
ufr	1 Elsevier		52	43	53	49	53	54	50	60	72	60	71	76	92	97	120
ufr	2 Wiley		27	33	40	33	34	35	48	33	44	67	67	62	59	78	70
ufr	3 Springer		19	23	25	33	32	28	36	33	39	45	47	47	48	60	63
ufr	4 APS		17	14	17	26	14	20	28	26	29	23	28	32	38	30	48
ufr	5 ACS		19	12	8	12	12	16	19	18	29	26	23	21	22	23	25
ufr	6 RSC		1	3	5	1	4	5	4	10	13	14	14	30	22	23	21
ufr	7 Taylor		1	4	1	3	4	4	14	11	8	17	17	15	17	26	
ufr	8 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	3	7	10	13	17	18	18
ufr	9 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	6	9	14	16
ufr	10 IOP		3	7	7	7	4	6	10	16	18	21	19	13	13	17	9
ufr	11 NPG		8	0	4	3	2	8	4	2	3	6	10	13	6	11	22
ufr	12 OUP		0	3	4	4	3	3	9	10	9	4	6	6	12	9	13
ufr	13 BMC	oaonly	1	0	0	0	5	2	1	2	4	5	7	4	10	10	11
ufr	14 Sage		2	2	1	4	1	3	3	2	0	6	4	7	8	11	12
ufr	15 ASM		0	2	0	3	1	2	1	0	1	2	0	4	2	15	9
ufr	16 AIP		5	1	0	2	5	6	5	4	2	7	5	4	6	8	4
ufr	17 Psycart		0	1	0	1	0	3	1	1	5	1	5	5	6	5	5
ufr	18 Copernicus	oaonly	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	2	3	2	4	4	7
ufr	19 CUP		1	2	3	1	2	1	1	0	2	3	3	7	7	4	4
ufr	20 Degruyter		0	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	6	3
ufr	21 others		34	49	62	57	73	87	80	78	102	114	139	120	133	128	143
uge	1 Elsevier		222	247	243	298	287	300	309	279	317	341	364	407	479	486	486
uge	2 Springer		89	83	101	89	99	121	129	124	159	143	178	200	245	289	217
uge	3 Wiley		117	108	152	155	141	191	173	173	220	221	205	206	209	213	197
uge	4 APS		75	75	66	80	123	129	114	132	134	132	178	207	167	163	143
uge	5 EDP		19	13	65	57	66	75	85	64	79	105	100	76	92	120	88

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inst code	provider	OA mode	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
uge	6 OUP		21	33	34	41	41	39	46	51	77	64	63	80	80	99	76
uge	7 ACS		37	42	43	54	48	62	45	51	64	58	52	79	83	68	79
uge	8 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	2	4	1	17	14	29	35	52	70	76	82	70
uge	9 NPG		16	11	20	22	26	34	24	31	30	37	44	64	46	64	74
uge	10 IOP		10	15	8	24	17	34	24	49	47	30	39	60	53	58	54
uge	11 Taylor		16	14	17	19	24	18	20	21	26	37	32	63	47	49	56
uge	12 RSC		8	8	19	10	11	24	18	24	20	24	34	46	33	55	43
uge	13 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	12	21	33	43	39
uge	14 EMH		22	21	13	4	12	18	16	13	21	20	16	18	39	27	35
uge	15 BMC	oaonly	2	0	1	5	5	13	14	13	15	24	29	26	30	35	33
uge	16 LWW		15	11	16	23	24	20	22	19	29	19	20	28	38	29	22
uge	17 AAS		11	9	14	16	15	12	21	16	24	47	35	25	21	17	41
uge	18 Sage		5	6	4	10	8	10	9	13	19	17	20	27	26	22	23
uge	19 CUP		4	1	6	6	25	8	7	5	9	13	18	20	14	17	13
uge	20 AIP		8	6	6	10	17	11	8	9	13	14	14	5	14	14	15
uge	21 others		236	237	320	338	349	361	372	373	415	412	480	554	497	514	484
ula	1 Elsevier		168	148	163	205	153	166	211	199	206	171	227	235	284	260	349
ula	2 Wiley		131	122	125	112	89	155	146	129	149	168	157	194	210	226	192
ula	3 Springer		62	51	79	75	58	73	74	75	76	93	86	130	111	147	83
ula	4 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	1	5	7	10	15	25	29	53	67	79	80	54
ula	5 OUP		12	13	23	32	36	23	33	32	39	26	38	45	45	60	53
ula	6 NPG		25	14	14	24	16	23	29	33	43	34	42	46	40	58	58
ula	7 Taylor		7	6	8	9	10	9	12	10	16	27	20	33	31	45	53
ula	8 BMC	oaonly	0	1	0	9	10	13	20	20	20	16	32	28	29	31	35
ula	9 Sage		4	1	3	8	6	12	5	8	19	10	16	20	26	33	32
ula	10 EMH		7	12	29	28	28	21	14	15	14	32	16	14	22	22	27
ula	11 LWW		16	10	25	29	23	29	25	26	29	19	21	28	20	18	32
ula	12 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	8	24	14	28	28
ula	13 RSOCLondon		2	2	0	0	6	9	3	7	4	4	8	11	13	26	10
ula	14 NAS		6	6	5	6	7	11	14	6	16	12	13	7	20	12	12
ula	15 GSW		2	1	6	10	4	4	9	10	6	9	7	18	18	10	14
ula	16 Hogrefe		3	2	3	3	10	7	11	5	2	5	6	3	9	7	15
ula	17 ASM		5	5	10	26	17	22	11	16	18	15	17	12	9	9	11
ula	18 CUP		2	2	3	3	5	3	4	4	8	6	4	7	5	11	9
ula	19 BMJ		1	3	6	5	6	5	1	2	5	2	6	6	9	4	11
ula	20 AACR		2	0	4	2	6	5	3	8	6	4	5	5	8	8	7
ula	21 others		203	221	253	230	255	230	210	291	275	306	346	325	316	302	323
uzu	1 Elsevier		246	210	253	302	327	410	421	400	453	429	516	568	663	659	674
uzu	2 Wiley		201	240	257	248	273	296	315	335	385	383	421	422	419	454	524
uzu	3 Springer		124	127	138	131	173	194	225	227	229	277	338	431	344	457	319
uzu	4 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	1	1	0	6	20	14	37	55	76	142	167	141	131
uzu	5 OUP		25	27	26	43	50	53	62	79	79	82	85	116	108	152	103
uzu	6 BMC	oaonly	8	5	7	12	10	22	42	56	44	73	106	88	94	118	103
uzu	7 NPG		26	15	31	35	31	36	48	44	44	57	57	76	84	97	131
uzu	8 APS		19	21	18	25	50	49	49	74	61	62	86	90	100	83	67
uzu	9 Taylor		8	13	17	20	46	23	35	30	49	61	57	83	64	84	64
uzu	10 ACS		34	21	36	39	43	44	36	51	42	57	45	63	76	66	64
uzu	11 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	5	15	17	29	43	73	60
uzu	12 Sage		4	9	8	13	15	13	27	18	32	36	32	47	55	50	61
uzu	13 LWW		24	23	31	47	38	47	41	43	35	27	36	39	53	31	65
uzu	14 RSC		2	2	4	8	18	5	10	11	21	23	25	32	28	35	41
uzu	15 Hogrefe		12	6	10	11	21	14	16	26	13	38	29	28	31	31	30
uzu	16 Karger		10	7	12	21	14	16	28	12	12	11	24	33	22	47	22
uzu	17 IOP		7	4	7	7	9	6	10	19	16	41	32	38	35	32	21
uzu	18 CUP		5	7	9	7	13	7	16	18	10	15	21	29	30	21	21

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inst code	provider	OA mode	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
uzu	19 ASM		14	14	22	30	35	24	18	21	25	38	26	25	22	28	27
uzu	20 NAS		12	13	20	9	21	9	24	20	22	29	19	29	28	28	20
uzu	21 others		265	301	329	411	439	456	522	604	647	686	745	775	784	821	769
bfh	1 Elsevier		0	0	0	1	0	0	1	4	5	5	7	20	27	28	18
bfh	2 Wiley		0	0	0	1	1	4	1	3	3	5	5	12	5	12	12
bfh	3 Springer		1	0	0	0	1	0	0	4	5	5	7	9	12	12	4
bfh	4 BMC	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	4	4	10
bfh	5 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	9
bfh	6 Taylor		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	3	3	3	3
bfh	7 IEEE		0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	3	2	3
bfh	8 Thieme		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	3	3	4	1
bfh	9 CUP		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	2	3	0
bfh	10 Hogrefe		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	3	2
bfh	11 AIP		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	3	0
bfh	12 Degruyter		0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	3	0	1	1	3	0	1
bfh	13 Sage		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	2
bfh	14 ACS		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
bfh	15 Hindawi	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
bfh	16 Huber		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0
bfh	17 IHC		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
bfh	18 IOS		0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	1	2	0
bfh	19 LWW		0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	0	0	0	2	1	2	0
bfh	20 NPG		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	1	1
bfh	21 others		1	1	2	2	1	0	11	15	14	13	11	15	31	21	20
hslu	1 Elsevier		1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	4	1	2	8	9
hslu	2 Wiley		0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	3	5	3
hslu	3 Springer		0	0	0	0	4	1	2	6	3	2	1	4	3	1	4
hslu	4 Taylor		0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	2	4
hslu	5 Copernicus	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	5
hslu	6 Emerald		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	1
hslu	7 NPG		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
hslu	8 Sage		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
hslu	9 IOS		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
hslu	10 ams		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
hslu	11 AMSCIPUB		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	12 ASM		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
hslu	13 BMC	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	14 EMH		0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	15 chforst		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	16 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	17 Hindawi	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	18 Hogrefe		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
hslu	19 Karger		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
hslu	20 Maney		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	21 others		0	0	0	0	0	1	4	8	3	4	3	6	2	8	9
xhosp	1 Elsevier		605	655	622	724	843	954	986	1,071	1,106	1,217	1,371	1,448	1,565	1,477	1,556
xhosp	2 Springer		380	397	434	441	557	533	587	610	583	687	712	785	849	914	733
xhosp	3 Wiley		402	373	396	446	497	608	597	675	753	707	771	838	767	712	774
xhosp	4 LWW		301	255	277	330	332	344	358	383	391	394	425	404	412	336	417
xhosp	5 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	0	7	8	26	27	59	93	168	243	305	267	286
xhosp	6 BMC	oaonly	12	6	10	21	55	103	101	128	145	180	226	255	259	262	316
xhosp	7 EMH		190	218	260	281	307	278	271	262	229	279	266	295	298	245	233
xhosp	8 OUP		119	108	108	121	158	151	163	179	236	208	262	247	225	263	239
xhosp	9 Hogrefe		218	208	229	253	268	274	228	160	170	192	184	206	232	208	179
xhosp	10 NPG		63	49	86	89	98	113	100	115	113	125	134	143	159	175	198

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inst code	provider	OA mode	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
xhosp	11 Karger		127	106	103	110	155	137	179	155	136	165	147	220	178	161	160
xhosp	12 Thieme		123	96	99	95	98	107	129	152	125	123	121	127	129	129	148
xhosp	13 BMJ		50	45	45	70	63	56	64	74	85	104	107	118	118	118	115
xhosp	14 IHC		48	36	50	52	62	72	68	91	83	82	91	86	95	106	86
xhosp	15 Sage		16	20	24	30	34	42	44	49	49	46	75	81	78	82	86
xhosp	16 Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	10	16	42	61	80	67	
xhosp	17 Hindawi	oaonly	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	9	14	21	47	58	51	43	
xhosp	18 ASM		22	21	52	43	48	52	47	43	52	70	64	49	48	45	53
xhosp	19 CUP		19	13	14	12	15	13	23	19	23	36	27	31	41	38	41
xhosp	20 MAL		9	7	13	18	19	18	21	26	20	37	25	43	50	32	38
xhosp	21 others		630	626	769	821	871	1,006	983	994	1,084	1,171	1,260	1,292	1,271	1,249	1,244
nn	1 Elsevier		1,797	1,670	1,879	1,933	2,052	2,542	2,624	2,678	2,978	2,811	3,205	3,276	3,824	3,881	3,496
nn	2 Springer		790	726	929	1,034	965	1,180	1,224	1,389	1,308	1,658	1,837	1,944	1,882	2,266	1,512
nn	3 Wiley		874	810	924	1,131	1,136	1,367	1,409	1,479	1,607	1,714	1,724	1,664	1,745	1,819	1,733
nn	4 APS		175	206	241	296	306	304	345	431	415	504	638	637	559	549	518
nn	5 ACS		169	257	262	280	330	324	333	381	423	434	442	496	499	490	490
nn	6 BMC	oaonly	9	43	41	50	73	136	206	231	247	324	404	410	464	407	463
nn	7 PLoS	oaonly	0	0	0	5	10	12	57	89	112	138	263	394	448	438	434
nn	8 NPG		98	54	108	132	146	167	158	181	191	224	187	318	347	379	431
nn	9 OUP		172	138	185	171	240	233	276	276	314	263	360	431	345	427	319
nn	10 IOP		74	52	106	95	118	153	229	296	253	322	301	311	353	346	237
nn	11 Taylor		71	75	78	124	116	121	133	135	189	214	250	251	272	287	275
nn	12 IEEE		119	128	111	113	158	202	159	150	164	170	195	270	272	282	248
nn	13 EMH		74	83	102	139	191	240	187	179	193	218	198	216	246	203	224
nn	14 LWW		125	93	153	191	170	170	206	205	198	228	221	227	234	228	169
nn	15 RSC		18	23	57	55	47	49	65	84	102	115	166	185	181	226	223
nn	16 Copernicus	oaonly	5	11	14	19	23	43	48	58	109	122	129	146	148	198	178
nn	17 AIP		73	90	88	88	133	155	159	162	162	140	160	173	160	182	149
nn	18 Sage		31	37	34	57	57	78	91	101	101	102	123	170	135	154	173
nn	19 EDP		19	21	86	65	65	43	114	64	90	260	155	132	127	158	132
nn	20 Karger		74	75	66	78	87	101	96	117	85	130	124	183	154	142	112
nn	21 others		1,625	1,770	2,391	2,785	2,935	3,035	3,119	3,259	3,499	3,622	3,864	4,011	4,034	3,998	3,619

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tab 9 number of articles per institution - top 20 journals

inst code	rc provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
switzerland	1 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	4	58	105	169	238	446	699	884	809	707
switzerland	2 EMH		Revue Médicale Suisse		0	0	0	0	328	318	287	264	234	261	216	251	300	235	294
switzerland	3 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		108	124	176	184	241	230	254	250	272	302	314	313	276	288	242
switzerland	4 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	70	57	72	76	71	91	116	117	103	124	143	246	260	249	246
switzerland	5 APS		Physical Review Letters		100	115	137	202	221	219	240	282	236	244	250	315	279	247	210
switzerland	6 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		99	114	81	89	93	105	106	152	151	146	186	194	203	192	178
switzerland	7 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		78	68	80	91	115	90	127	103	144	130	139	156	195	179	127
switzerland	8 EDP		Astronomy and Astrophysics		54	45	122	109	125	119	143	95	129	208	154	150	156	171	169
switzerland	9 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	26	52	92	160	230
switzerland	10 Hogrefe		Schweizerische Rundschau für Medizin Praxis		188	163	191	192	195	209	202	111	101	103	115	104	144	135	134
switzerland	11 NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	37	77	86	230
switzerland	12 Wiley		Angewandte Chemie International Edition		53	37	55	59	68	55	78	89	80	94	105	107	95	114	132
switzerland	13 AAS		The Astrophysical Journal		22	29	50	57	62	63	70	84	95	97	100	103	86	117	130
switzerland	14 AIP		Applied Physics Letters		47	64	58	73	85	108	114	100	103	111	94	100	110	134	87
switzerland	15 Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	136	140	99	102	97	75	55	62	58	59	103	151	115	98	98
switzerland	16 OUP		Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society		10	16	18	52	51	43	44	44	50	51	85	108	94	115	96
switzerland	17 ACS		Environmental Science and Technology		32	45	41	44	82	67	71	80	92	73	81	110	114	96	91
switzerland	18 EMH		Swiss Medical Weekly	2001	74	60	52	66	71	83	90	76	86	130	131	148	124	94	70
switzerland	19 Elsevier		Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section .		115	95	52	53	74	187	167	94	128	59	86	64	127	88	62
switzerland	20 Hogrefe		Therapeutische Umschau		92	70	89	83	108	89	59	83	75	80	81	97	101	84	86
switzerland	21		others		12,561	12,614	14,713	16,114	16,750	18,732	19,629	20,747	21,841	23,024	24,877	26,719	27,654	29,038	27,746
epfl	1 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		21	27	31	40	48	77	66	58	82	70	78	73	89	66	67
epfl	2 APS		Physical Review Letters		11	16	24	41	57	57	59	59	45	50	49	62	76	66	44
epfl	3 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	10	16	19	24	46	65	51	44
epfl	4 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		0	0	0	9	18	16	24	23	27	25	24	27	44	33	41
epfl	5 AIP		Applied Physics Letters		17	29	24	27	25	38	38	40	40	43	35	36	44	39	34
epfl	6 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	0	0	1	2	3	1	6	10	9	8	15	23	43	34	20
epfl	7 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	10	25	28	41
epfl	8 OSA		Optics Express	1997	1	2	1	4	15	14	16	13	17	29	27	23	30	36	26
epfl	9 EDP		Astronomy and Astrophysics		0	0	0	4	8	15	13	14	13	8	11	26	20	52	17
epfl	10 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		1	3	4	4	5	12	15	8	14	17	12	19	37	23	23
epfl	11 Wiley		Angewandte Chemie International Edition		1	3	5	8	14	7	11	16	17	18	21	22	19	29	30
epfl	12 ACS		The Journal of Physical Chemistry C :: Nanomaterials and Interf.		0	0	0	0	0	0	12	15	13	15	11	19	23	25	30
epfl	13 NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	6	16	17	44
epfl	14 ACS		Nano Letters		0	3	1	3	5	8	7	13	7	19	22	21	14	33	27
epfl	15 ACS		Journal of the American Chemical Society		3	7	14	18	21	27	12	15	22	20	22	25	17	24	30
epfl	16 IOP		Nuclear Fusion		10	12	15	6	11	7	22	4	14	10	16	14	21	14	28
epfl	17 ACS		ACS Nano		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	6	8	13	16	15	21	21
epfl	18 AIP		The Journal of Chemical Physics		5	6	3	6	9	11	18	10	9	9	11	13	14	24	18
epfl	19 RSC		Physical Chemistry, Chemical Physics		3	2	4	5	6	3	2	3	6	11	13	17	17	18	20
epfl	20 AIP		Journal of Applied Physics		20	14	5	16	18	30	20	19	25	15	15	18	22	19	11
epfl	21		others		707	757	950	1,134	1,179	1,457	1,530	1,756	1,714	1,773	1,946	2,244	2,434	2,463	2,441
uba	1 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	8	13	23	48	59	77	72	55
uba	2 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		12	11	21	18	36	20	21	25	31	25	24	36	26	36	29
uba	3 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	25	25	21	20	24
uba	4 APS		Physical Review Letters		11	10	16	17	11	11	15	17	9	12	19	20	23	18	15
uba	5 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		8	6	9	10	22	9	15	11	15	8	13	18	19	25	11
uba	6 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	8	20	24
uba	7 BMC	oaonly	Malaria Journal	2002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	10	13	10	15	16	16
uba	8 Elsevier		Acta Tropica		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	3	2	16	2	21
uba	9 BMC	oaonly	Parasites and Vectors	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	7	10	9	11	15
uba	10 NPG		Nature		4	2	4	2	1	4	2	0	3	4	11	3	5	11	17
uba	11 APS		Physical Review C :: Nuclear Physics		10	2	5	6	5	11	7	8	12	12	12	11	7	16	10
uba	12 ACS		Journal of Medicinal Chemistry		0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	7	4	13	9	11	10
uba	13 Wiley		Angewandte Chemie International Edition		7	1	6	8	6	3	5	12	7	7	10	11	4	13	11

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tab 9 number of articles per institution - top 20 journals

inst code	rc provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
uba	14 Wiley		Chemistry - A European Journal		5	2	4	6	2	5	4	7	10	8	10	6	15	8	5
uba	15 NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	4	6	18
uba	16 APS		Physical Review A :: Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics		2	1	3	1	5	2	4	5	4	5	5	8	11	10	6
uba	17 OUP		Nucleic Acids Research	1996	1	0	4	6	1	5	3	6	7	3	8	6	8	12	5
uba	18 ASBMB		Journal of Biological Chemistry		11	20	11	27	12	11	8	11	8	11	10	6	11	7	7
uba	19 AIP		The Journal of Chemical Physics		7	5	11	7	8	5	7	5	5	5	6	4	4	9	11
uba	20 RSC		Chemical Communications		3	3	3	6	2	3	3	5	5	5	15	6	9	12	3
uba	21		others		608	638	768	825	865	892	898	961	994	1,223	1,301	1,448	1,629	1,692	1,559
ube	1 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	16	18	40	59	78	97	95
ube	2 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	1	1	4	2	1	5	1	5	6	12	9	32	35	42	47
ube	3 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		6	4	2	3	4	1	1	8	11	10	28	42	26	30	35
ube	4 Springer	scoop3	The European Physical Journal - C :: Particles and Fields	2014	1	2	4	7	2	0	2	3	3	10	11	17	12	20	36
ube	5 Copernicus	oaonly	Climate of the Past	2005	0	0	0	0	0	2	11	1	0	5	9	14	25	14	12
ube	6 EDP		Astronomy and Astrophysics		2	1	1	5	5	8	8	5	10	22	11	9	7	8	34
ube	7 APS		Physical Review Letters		0	0	2	4	7	2	2	8	17	16	23	29	12	16	21
ube	8 Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	1	2	1	4	5	2	5	2	4	4	22	46	22	12	13
ube	9 Huber		Schweizer Archiv für Tierheilkunde		4	9	6	7	12	12	7	13	13	14	10	14	13	16	17
ube	10 Elsevier		Journal of Dairy Science		0	4	3	4	7	4	2	2	6	6	10	6	15	15	13
ube	11 Wiley		Clinical Oral Implants Research		11	3	10	15	11	14	18	16	14	7	12	18	6	13	21
ube	12 Springer		Clinical Oral Investigations		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	6	3	13	16	14	8
ube	13 Elsevier		Quaternary Science Reviews		1	0	4	2	2	8	5	5	6	18	13	13	9	14	14
ube	14 IOP		Journal of Instrumentation		0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	4	4	4	8	8	21	7
ube	15 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		4	3	5	6	3	6	4	10	10	7	7	8	7	18	8
ube	16 EMH		Swiss Medical Weekly	2001	3	2	1	3	4	6	4	5	13	13	9	6	13	12	6
ube	17 Copernicus	oaonly	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	2001	0	3	1	2	1	6	4	4	4	7	5	7	10	6	15
ube	18 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	8	6	15
ube	19 OUP		The European Journal of Orthodontics		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	1	0	1	3	10	15	3
ube	20 AAAS		Science		1	4	5	4	7	4	5	3	10	6	6	10	4	7	17
ube	21		others		811	828	1,015	1,033	1,162	1,287	1,282	1,380	1,431	1,514	1,676	1,724	1,859	2,201	2,036
ufr	1 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		1	4	7	12	5	8	6	5	6	8	5	15	13	13	19
ufr	2 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	6	8	13	14	13	14
ufr	3 APS		Physical Review Letters		5	4	2	10	5	4	8	10	8	9	7	6	12	10	9
ufr	4 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21
ufr	5 APS		Physical Review A :: Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics		4	3	5	3	3	6	7	8	5	5	8	5	9	4	5
ufr	6 NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	10
ufr	7 ASM		Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	11	5
ufr	8 RSC		Physical Chemistry, Chemical Physics		0	1	3	0	1	1	1	2	3	0	1	4	4	3	8
ufr	9 IOP		Europhysics Letters		1	3	1	2	0	2	3	4	5	6	10	6	5	5	2
ufr	10 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	10
ufr	11 Elsevier		Physica A :: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications		4	2	2	4	2	2	3	6	5	4	7	4	3	6	2
ufr	12 Copernicus	oaonly	The Cryosphere	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	3	2	6
ufr	13 AIP		The Journal of Chemical Physics		2	0	0	2	3	4	0	2	0	2	3	3	4	4	2
ufr	14 chimia		CHIMIA International Journal for Chemistry		1	1	1	0	1	0	2	5	4	6	1	3	7	3	0
ufr	15 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		1	4	0	0	1	1	3	0	2	3	3	4	4	2	4
ufr	16 ACS		Langmuir		1	3	2	0	2	1	2	3	5	8	2	3	4	1	5
ufr	17 RSC		Soft Matter		0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	2	7	6	9	5	4	1
ufr	18 Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	7
ufr	19 Wiley		Molecular Ecology		1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	3	2	1	5	2
ufr	20 Frontiers	oaonly	Frontiers in Human Neuroscience	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	4	1
ufr	21		others		168	173	207	207	226	257	284	264	337	366	418	409	438	490	516
uge	1 EDP		Astronomy and Astrophysics		19	13	65	56	66	75	83	62	79	105	100	75	90	119	86
uge	2 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		22	27	8	17	26	31	25	34	47	36	53	67	69	57	47
uge	3 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	9	14	22	39	56	61	54	51
uge	4 APS		Physical Review Letters		21	19	22	34	49	50	47	50	50	48	74	70	50	59	46
uge	5 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	1	3	6	19	20	23	31	37

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inst code	rc provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
uge	6 OUP		Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society		2	7	5	7	11	12	11	12	14	10	26	30	26	33	30
uge	7 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		19	11	21	19	32	32	28	29	23	32	31	40	27	27	22
uge	8 EMH		Revue Médicale Suisse		0	0	0	0	11	16	14	10	17	12	10	8	25	20	31
uge	9 Springer	scoop3	The European Physical Journal - C :: Particles and Fields	2014	11	3	8	3	3	6	6	2	1	8	16	19	14	18	31
uge	10 AAS		The Astrophysical Journal		8	8	13	15	12	12	16	16	22	31	22	19	15	11	27
uge	11 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	7	5	23	24
uge	12 IOP	scoop3	Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics		0	0	2	0	1	0	0	4	5	5	9	9	19	16	12
uge	13 Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	21	27	16	21	14	4	2	1	1	4	25	48	22	10	13
uge	14 Elsevier		NeuroImage		0	1	3	2	6	4	3	7	4	5	9	17	13	14	13
uge	15 APS		Physical Review A :: Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics		6	5	4	3	9	13	8	13	8	11	14	21	15	8	16
uge	16 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		8	9	5	14	13	10	15	9	11	15	11	7	21	6	11
uge	17 OUP		Nucleic Acids Research	1996	3	2	7	5	4	11	8	5	7	1	7	8	12	11	12
uge	18 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Genetics	2005	0	0	0	0	1	0	6	3	7	8	8	8	9	17	9
uge	19 IOP		New Journal of Physics	1998	0	1	0	1	2	4	3	6	11	4	6	4	14	11	8
uge	20 Wiley		Chemistry - A European Journal		4	0	4	6	7	5	14	9	12	14	5	9	13	8	11
uge	21		others		789	806	965	1,060	1,073	1,196	1,176	1,192	1,411	1,421	1,493	1,740	1,779	1,911	1,751
ula	1 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	7	19	19	41	50	66	63	37
ula	2 EMH		Revue Médicale Suisse		0	0	0	0	22	15	10	8	10	20	7	9	16	16	21
ula	3 Elsevier		Forensic Science International		4	2	5	7	7	8	20	10	12	5	15	14	22	11	13
ula	4 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		6	6	5	6	7	11	14	6	16	12	13	7	20	12	12
ula	5 RSOCLondon		Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series B : Biologic		2	2	0	0	4	8	2	5	2	1	1	8	9	15	5
ula	6 Wiley		Journal of Evolutionary Biology		4	0	2	1	4	6	5	4	6	5	8	10	8	11	7
ula	7 Wiley		Molecular Ecology		1	5	3	4	9	3	12	4	6	9	9	11	8	10	8
ula	8 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	5	15
ula	9 OUP		Nucleic Acids Research	1996	2	3	1	3	5	3	3	2	8	2	8	5	2	10	8
ula	10 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Genetics	2005	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	4	3	4	3	9	6	5	7
ula	11 NPG		Nature		2	1	1	2	5	6	3	5	4	5	10	9	4	7	7
ula	12 AAAS		Science		1	0	0	6	5	2	3	4	6	5	4	5	7	6	4
ula	13 NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	13
ula	14 Wiley		Evolution		2	2	6	4	1	9	1	2	5	4	3	8	8	7	1
ula	15 Elsevier		Earth and Planetary Science Letters		1	4	0	1	2	2	0	3	2	2	4	2	3	8	5
ula	16 Elsevier		Current Biology		1	1	1	2	1	2	2	4	1	5	5	4	5	5	6
ula	17 ASBMB		Journal of Biological Chemistry		13	11	16	16	19	14	14	11	12	15	11	10	3	7	6
ula	18 Springer		International Journal of Legal Medicine		2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	3	2	6	4	4
ula	19 Elsevier		Tectonophysics		0	1	1	1	2	0	1	5	1	3	4	3	6	4	4
ula	20 amerai		Journal of Immunology		2	4	9	8	6	18	5	8	12	11	9	3	5	4	5
ula	21		others		615	578	709	756	649	714	742	818	850	864	954	1,066	1,126	1,152	1,220
uzu	1 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	2	9	11	23	37	60	121	140	116	98
uzu	2 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	2	1	6	2	5	5	10	9	12	12	30	67	59	69	49
uzu	3 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		5	5	5	3	10	21	15	15	12	23	27	29	37	32	34
uzu	4 Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	14	6	6	12	16	23	13	12	13	5	27	41	37	31	33
uzu	5 APS		Physical Review Letters		5	9	6	13	24	17	25	42	25	17	32	43	42	30	23
uzu	6 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		12	13	20	9	21	9	24	20	22	29	19	29	28	28	20
uzu	7 Springer	scoop3	The European Physical Journal - C :: Particles and Fields	2014	10	11	6	9	6	16	9	4	9	11	14	25	21	21	33
uzu	8 Huber		Schweizer Archiv für Tierheilkunde		10	20	22	15	19	25	21	15	29	19	28	32	23	22	29
uzu	9 OUP		Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society		0	1	1	13	11	16	18	18	16	22	22	27	20	26	18
uzu	10 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	8	6	21	28
uzu	11 Elsevier		Journal of Forensic Radiology and Imaging		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	18	15
uzu	12 jneurosci		Journal of Neuroscience		4	4	4	9	7	12	11	20	10	12	16	13	19	13	16
uzu	13 Elsevier		NeuroImage		0	2	2	7	4	12	6	14	10	14	12	14	18	14	14
uzu	14 Wiley		Clinical Oral Implants Research		2	0	4	1	1	2	5	2	6	3	4	4	3	5	34
uzu	15 AAS		The Astrophysical Journal		0	0	2	10	4	10	7	17	14	16	19	17	14	16	12
uzu	16 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		8	7	6	9	15	9	8	14	23	21	24	18	18	17	7
uzu	17 RSOCLondon		Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series B : Biologic		1	3	4	2	5	4	8	7	6	3	11	11	14	20	7
uzu	18 ASBMB		Journal of Biological Chemistry		34	26	24	19	15	13	11	6	13	14	16	6	16	13	9

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tab 9 number of articles per institution - top 20 journals

inst code	rc	provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
uzu	19	OUP		Nucleic Acids Research	1996	6	4	6	6	11	5	9	9	6	3	7	13	12	16	8
uzu	20	NPG		Nature		7	3	4	5	7	5	8	10	10	17	10	5	14	10	12
uzu	21			others		926	950	1,108	1,276	1,445	1,524	1,748	1,861	2,002	2,216	2,407	2,652	2,690	2,979	2,818
bfn	1	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	9
bfn	2	Elsevier		Gait and Posture		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	3	0	2
bfn	3	Elsevier		Soil and Tillage Research		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	2
bfn	4	Elsevier		Atmospheric Environment		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	2
bfn	5	BMC	oaonly	Trials	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
bfn	6	Degruyter		Holzforschung		0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	1	3	0	1
bfn	7	Elsevier		Journal of Dairy Science		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	0
bfn	8	Hogrefe		Pflege		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	0	2	2
bfn	9	Springer		Applied Physics A :: Materials Science and Processing		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	3	0
bfn	10	Wiley		Animal Genetics		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
bfn	11	Elsevier		Industrial Crops and Products		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
bfn	12	Elsevier		Medical Engineering and Physics		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	1	0
bfn	13	IHC		Disability and Rehabilitation - Assistive Technology		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
bfn	14	BMC	oaonly	Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation (JNER)	2004	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1
bfn	15	IOS		Technology and Health Care		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	1	2	0
bfn	16	IEEE		IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2
bfn	17	CUP		Animal		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0
bfn	18	Huber		Schweizer Archiv für Tierheilkunde		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0
bfn	19	Elsevier		Safety and Health at Work		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
bfn	20	Springer		RILEM Bookseries		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
bfn	21			others		5	1	2	4	6	5	14	32	35	33	30	65	75	83	64
hslu	1	Wiley		Beton- und Stahlbetonbau		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0
hslu	2	Copernicus	oaonly	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
hslu	3	Springer		Prävention und Gesundheitsförderung		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
hslu	4	Wiley		Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
hslu	5	Taylor		Numerical Heat Transfer - Part B :: Fundamentals		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
hslu	6	NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
hslu	7	Springer		Informatik-Spektrum		0	0	0	0	4	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	8	Springer		Service Business		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	9	Springer		Journal of International Migration and Integration		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	10	Springer		Review of Managerial Science		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	11	Wiley		Creativity and Innovation Management		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
hslu	12	Wiley		Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	13	Wiley		Nonprofit Management and Leadership		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
hslu	14	Wiley		Scottish Journal of Political Economy		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	15	Wiley		Cytometry Part A		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
hslu	16	Elsevier		Biomass and Bioenergy		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	17	Elsevier		Construction and Building Materials		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	18	Elsevier		Cortex		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	19	Elsevier		Economic Modelling		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
hslu	20	Elsevier		Energy and Buildings		1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
hslu	21			others		0	0	0	1	1	3	5	13	10	7	11	16	12	20	27
xhosp	1	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	20	37	68	144	211	261	236	258
xhosp	2	EMH		Revue Médicale Suisse		0	0	0	0	220	177	171	169	133	158	122	150	170	153	158
xhosp	3	Hogrefe		Schweizerische Rundschau für Medizin Praxis		160	147	154	168	162	185	171	92	82	89	93	92	127	114	100
xhosp	4	EMH		Swiss Medical Weekly	2001	58	39	53	58	65	73	80	72	77	98	116	127	104	77	62
xhosp	5	Hogrefe		Therapeutische Umschau		53	55	68	73	86	72	46	52	64	72	68	84	77	66	51
xhosp	6	OUP		European Heart Journal		9	9	10	12	13	18	14	16	24	34	40	34	29	47	42
xhosp	7	Thieme		Klinische Monatsblätter für Augenheilkunde		26	6	0	2	3	2	37	54	29	22	25	27	27	30	44
xhosp	8	OUP		Annals of Oncology		8	5	14	12	33	13	29	28	31	17	28	29	31	25	35
xhosp	9	Elsevier		International Journal of Cardiology		1	2	2	4	6	12	18	14	16	8	8	14	43	17	28
xhosp	10	Elsevier		NeuroImage		4	7	7	14	13	24	16	27	18	25	19	37	31	25	22

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tab 9 number of articles per institution - top 20 journals

inst code	rc provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	y2001	y2002	y2003	y2004	y2005	y2006	y2007	y2008	y2009	y2010	y2011	y2012	y2013	y2014	y2015
xhosp	11 Springer		European Radiology		19	36	28	19	18	16	30	28	29	22	28	10	21	28	23
xhosp	12 LWW		Neurology		23	16	19	25	24	25	15	17	17	15	26	21	21	24	25
xhosp	13 OUP		European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery		26	20	9	11	11	19	17	24	26	14	23	26	22	37	9
xhosp	14 Hindawi	oaonly	biomed research international	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	25	28
xhosp	15 LWW		Stroke		4	3	5	13	13	17	8	8	13	10	14	18	32	25	7
xhosp	16 NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United		13	13	12	11	12	15	20	18	20	21	29	17	23	22	15
xhosp	17 BMJ		BMJ Case Reports		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	12	8	9	12	23	19	18
xhosp	18 ASM		Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy		3	9	14	10	6	13	8	2	15	14	15	18	20	14	21
xhosp	19 Wiley		Allergy		9	15	7	10	9	9	8	8	15	8	12	21	15	22	17
xhosp	20 BMJ		Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases		5	7	3	12	12	7	5	9	17	22	22	29	20	13	20
xhosp	21		others		2,914	2,852	3,187	3,504	3,783	4,174	4,267	4,558	4,777	5,215	5,632	6,023	6,089	5,931	6,029
nn	1 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	1	23	38	73	71	163	280	344	322	308
nn	2 Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	74	60	77	83	58	85	103	119	96	144	150	253	258	260	269
nn	3 EMH		Revue Médicale Suisse		0	0	0	0	146	193	156	139	144	166	141	162	193	158	181
nn	4 APS		Physical Review Letters		34	48	57	84	106	96	115	164	132	166	172	213	186	144	152
nn	5 APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, and Cosmolo		62	86	63	72	40	49	58	87	72	87	187	173	161	149	148
nn	6 Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	154	140	115	121	85	76	47	60	50	70	148	181	159	133	128
nn	7 EDP		Astronomy and Astrophysics		18	20	85	59	59	35	106	61	87	252	151	127	119	150	126
nn	8 APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materials Physics		27	47	78	90	110	111	95	116	144	179	183	166	134	140	116
nn	9 Springer	scoop3	The European Physical Journal - C :: Particles and Fields	2014	105	58	128	158	58	101	84	65	46	139	145	100	84	112	124
nn	10 Elsevier		Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section .		106	84	52	53	71	163	161	94	132	66	91	67	128	100	60
nn	11 IOP		Journal of Instrumentation		0	0	0	0	0	4	16	70	36	102	62	94	104	112	61
nn	12 NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	10	37	50	87	103
nn	13 ACS		Environmental Science and Technology		28	30	38	41	61	57	46	59	63	59	56	84	78	69	61
nn	14 Copernicus	oaonly	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	2001	0	6	7	10	13	28	32	37	48	58	60	47	64	76	64
nn	15 AAS		The Astrophysical Journal		4	19	28	26	34	30	11	32	68	67	63	69	51	56	68
nn	16 NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	15	36	33	100
nn	17 NPG		Nature		19	8	12	21	40	28	26	30	29	61	52	61	49	56	62
nn	18 PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	19	16	26	42	48	42	55	69
nn	19 chagro		Agrarforschung Schweiz		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	68	50	49	59
nn	20 AIP		Applied Physics Letters		23	30	32	34	42	65	74	46	47	53	54	44	48	62	41
nn	21		others		5,738	5,726	7,083	7,989	8,435	9,533	10,079	10,709	11,457	11,938	13,015	13,556	14,091	14,737	12,835

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tab 10 number of articles from Switzerland - all publishers identified

	provider	OA mode	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]
	total		13,839	13,856	16,086	17,646	18,837	20,887	21,910	22,938	24,147	25,547	27,739	30,224	31,486	32,729	31,365		
1	Elsevier		3,433	3,249	3,504	3,886	4,013	4,865	5,066	5,086	5,352	5,189	5,755	5,900	6,669	6,825	6,958	22	22
2	Wiley		1,948	1,975	2,167	2,299	2,398	2,726	2,775	2,915	3,176	3,242	3,360	3,463	3,511	3,624	3,744	12	34
3	Springer		1,488	1,475	1,900	1,969	1,871	2,143	2,309	2,451	2,429	2,756	2,951	3,438	3,334	3,924	2,789	9	43
4	PLoS	oaonly	0	0	1	8	30	47	141	197	283	383	623	908	1,090	1,042	937	3	46
5	ACS		402	489	508	582	649	660	650	729	779	823	821	937	999	989	1,040	3	49
6	APS		399	418	482	567	647	658	732	815	803	837	930	992	925	923	829	3	52
7	NPG		221	154	243	286	278	330	331	378	400	424	444	610	695	756	1,023	3	55
8	OUP		342	312	380	407	489	463	536	559	662	581	718	803	771	949	748	2	58
9	BMC	oaonly	30	54	59	90	130	225	304	367	406	535	647	648	708	736	782	2	60
10	IEEE		197	213	234	246	293	341	319	329	340	357	436	534	588	628	542	2	62
11	Taylor		153	176	200	200	238	249	280	264	362	458	479	551	568	581	592	2	64
12	LWW		400	355	424	487	463	495	524	531	543	553	588	589	604	534	568	2	66
13	RSC		82	91	137	139	153	130	173	195	255	307	415	473	486	572	615	2	67
14	IOP		147	137	184	199	227	281	361	410	420	409	451	504	522	472	474	2	69
15	EMH		273	334	323	372	437	441	403	380	353	430	386	426	456	357	391	1	70
16	AIP		191	216	211	230	312	338	329	335	333	309	319	342	363	426	377	1	71
17	Sage		71	82	77	119	118	151	178	231	224	221	266	336	337	348	389	1	73
18	Hogrefe		310	257	319	313	361	353	319	262	245	275	277	276	329	296	287	1	74
19	Karger		200	172	173	169	236	231	260	237	207	265	248	362	290	299	256	1	74
20	Frontiers	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	23	43	76	145	219	301	299	1	75
21	Copernicus	oaonly	7	13	22	25	38	70	70	79	131	160	189	198	219	259	257	1	76
22	Thieme		193	151	156	170	169	192	203	231	207	201	204	219	224	209	240	1	77
23	CUP		69	72	85	90	138	86	105	108	172	157	169	180	213	255	185	1	78
24	BMJ		74	77	85	117	104	128	120	130	129	169	175	195	212	193	225	1	78
25	IHC		98	86	125	110	152	157	171	177	186	200	213	177	202	204	206	1	79
26	EDP		61	50	131	127	135	137	156	105	142	223	166	170	176	181	188	1	80
27	ASM		103	114	196	197	205	198	186	162	191	205	206	185	151	175	201	1	80
28	NAS		78	68	80	91	115	90	127	104	145	130	139	156	195	179	127	0	81
29	AAS		29	34	57	74	74	76	101	98	107	145	137	139	131	158	188	1	81
30	MDPI	oaonly	2	1	1	1	0	3	6	22	28	63	51	81	106	156	174	1	82
31	Degruyter	oaonly	38	50	77	74	84	77	81	85	110	78	118	108	129	143	117	0	82
32	OSA		51	26	46	47	95	91	84	89	100	124	117	112	106	146	107	0	82
33	Hindawi	oaonly	1	5	4	2	4	6	11	8	33	53	71	128	126	113	113	0	83
34	RSOCLondon		10	13	21	34	41	58	39	66	45	45	74	87	105	145	88	0	83
35	AAAS		20	29	45	62	54	57	49	51	70	73	74	89	90	105	113	0	83
36	MAL		31	21	32	33	48	48	53	55	64	69	65	79	110	100	88	0	84
37	GSW		41	47	59	80	55	70	92	64	74	79	92	103	108	87	83	0	84
38	univchicago		25	25	60	59	61	54	64	70	72	88	77	94	69	89	117	0	84
39	ASBMB		169	155	164	188	131	134	114	114	118	113	131	140	89	106	72	0	85
40	Emerald		12	9	15	25	41	45	49	48	48	80	64	60	71	68	71	0	85
41	chimia		128	63	63	59	58	59	45	75	86	80	74	57	73	89	46	0	85
42	AACR		25	15	37	50	57	37	55	75	70	47	67	60	65	67	64	0	85
43	Bentham	oaonly	12	12	40	44	42	59	76	52	45	69	82	106	58	66	69	0	85
44	wscipub		24	23	36	37	50	30	45	32	36	56	47	64	54	69	67	0	86
45	Psycart		8	6	16	9	30	26	27	58	54	34	46	67	61	70	47	0	86
46	JAPS		71	66	58	61	57	71	78	66	68	68	56	53	58	56	59	0	86
47	landes		0	0	1	10	5	11	14	16	25	49	50	66	61	39	65	0	86
48	chagro		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70	50	50	63	0	86
49	DOVE	oaonly	0	0	0	0	1	3	9	17	15	8	25	33	36	53	67	0	87
50	ACM		3	4	11	6	5	18	33	44	28	56	66	61	59	52	44	0	87
51	IOS		25	6	13	26	19	28	27	46	42	38	50	60	52	47	56	0	87
52	jneurosci		19	29	27	41	32	46	49	48	37	64	58	58	63	42	41	0	87

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tab 10 number of articles from Switzerland - all publishers identified

	provider	OA mode	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]
53	schatt		24	28	38	48	49	49	41	47	47	40	54	41	51	46	47	0	87
54	cbiol		34	36	42	48	56	55	50	37	46	52	37	47	44	57	40	0	87
55	Huber		62	77	87	37	37	47	39	46	51	53	54	51	53	43	41	0	87
56	chforst		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	47	40	36	41	43	0	88
57	brill		18	10	12	19	23	19	21	32	32	25	46	35	32	46	41	0	88
58	amerai		30	26	44	60	61	73	49	64	61	49	54	46	26	50	35	0	88
59	coldspring		18	16	19	31	35	19	23	31	39	45	34	42	44	37	25	0	88
60	adis		18	15	32	22	16	30	22	15	18	13	17	22	37	29	34	0	88
61	soceurs	oaonly	10	11	9	12	13	16	15	27	21	21	22	32	31	43	25	0	88
62	ash		32	44	29	19	23	15	52	53	46	59	74	50	33	41	23	0	88
63	elife		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	14	30	52	0	88
64	aspb		21	12	25	34	26	22	26	26	26	27	33	37	36	27	32	0	88
65	exprev		2	4	8	9	9	13	21	31	33	27	37	34	26	40	29	0	88
66	futuremed		2	1	1	3	2	11	9	12	19	23	32	19	30	32	31	0	89
67	endocsoc		41	36	30	34	40	28	43	31	38	40	30	41	31	30	27	0	89
68	annrev		4	9	12	14	13	12	16	20	21	26	18	30	34	22	30	0	89
69	who		20	24	24	40	37	37	31	37	28	40	23	28	45	18	23	0	89
70	Maney		12	13	13	19	13	22	16	18	14	19	24	37	25	32	26	0	89
71	rockefeller		46	35	34	32	29	27	26	44	33	38	21	32	38	25	19	0	89
72	Impact	oaonly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	4	2	4	15	60	0	89
73	dustri		14	17	19	11	31	24	22	17	26	26	17	27	25	22	24	0	89
74	jove		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	19	15	32	23	0	89
75	palgrave		16	6	8	18	15	19	9	13	25	25	31	23	31	22	17	0	89
76	portland		10	16	25	28	24	21	17	16	20	16	15	25	26	16	23	0	89
77	indersci		14	13	16	28	36	39	44	49	42	36	34	37	22	23	19	0	90
78	minervamed		5	10	15	2	7	19	17	14	16	26	28	35	25	17	22	0	90
79	mit		7	12	10	14	18	8	13	16	18	17	21	25	28	16	18	0	90
80	schwbart		10	13	23	26	21	30	15	33	34	14	26	15	26	16	20	0	90
81	aspet		24	34	28	19	22	34	23	27	14	14	21	18	22	21	16	0	90
82	nrc		12	15	13	18	16	26	14	16	21	13	21	15	16	23	20	0	90
83	chadwyck		3	6	10	20	10	12	11	14	19	16	25	16	13	28	17	0	90
84	asco		3	5	10	10	10	13	11	17	7	9	20	35	19	18	19	0	90
85	ams		10	3	6	10	8	16	17	11	12	7	16	21	20	15	20	0	90
86	iwapub		2	3	5	21	23	16	12	24	14	18	21	22	19	15	19	0	90
87	wichtig		4	6	11	9	10	19	14	17	17	16	21	18	18	16	19	0	90
88	coaction	oaonly	4	5	5	2	4	1	1	6	3	6	9	9	14	23	14	0	90
89	ada		20	12	12	15	20	14	19	20	18	14	24	19	22	13	15	0	90
90	Medknow	oaonly	0	1	1	3	3	2	0	2	3	10	20	8	13	19	17	0	90
91	ingenta		5	1	6	10	9	5	12	9	22	25	18	18	9	20	17	0	90
92	krause	oaonly	10	8	10	11	7	17	12	16	11	15	22	17	27	9	9	0	90
93	humkin		2	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	9	8	7	7	9	20	15	0	90
94	ecs		17	10	10	21	10	17	13	17	12	11	17	13	9	8	25	0	90
95	spie		6	8	10	7	13	11	13	10	13	10	19	16	11	17	14	0	91
96	baishideng	oaonly	2	0	1	0	5	8	5	7	5	10	8	6	15	15	10	0	91
97	digizs		3	5	9	13	14	8	8	13	17	17	21	20	19	14	6	0	91
98	usncid	oaonly	5	5	6	14	7	13	23	15	18	8	14	8	17	5	16	0	91
99	versita	oaonly	2	2	1	4	2	3	3	13	8	13	10	10	7	19	12	0	91
100	rsmedicine		6	5	5	6	5	7	4	8	8	9	11	7	10	9	12	0	91
101	wiso		5	9	13	21	27	19	25	16	25	23	11	15	13	12	5	0	91
102	aans		6	5	7	4	4	6	13	8	6	16	8	4	12	12	5	0	91
103	ems		2	2	3	4	10	7	3	6	7	7	7	5	8	8	13	0	91
104	interres		5	3	4	7	4	5	8	10	9	15	9	12	12	5	11	0	91
105	csiro		4	3	4	6	5	8	6	12	11	18	12	11	3	14	10	0	91
106	spandido		1	1	1	3	9	11	9	8	9	6	8	9	7	11	8	0	91
107	euclid		6	2	4	3	2	7	3	5	4	8	4	6	12	3	9	0	91

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tab 10 number of articles from Switzerland - all publishers identified

provider	OA mode	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]	
108	slack	0	2	8	4	4	6	6	0	4	6	11	5	9	5	14	5	0	91
109	peeters	0	1	2	4	4	2	3	1	3	9	9	1	8	9	8	5	0	91
110	tsw	0	2	1	0	0	0	3	0	1	1	4	4	10	14	7	1	0	91
111	caj	0	4	2	6	8	9	10	13	15	13	15	16	13	11	6	4	0	91
112	translic	0	0	2	5	33	13	1	12	2	9	8	22	12	6	5	10	0	91
113	pagepress	0	1	1	3	4	1	3	2	5	2	7	9	6	9	8	3	0	91
114	eio	0	0	2	2	4	3	7	1	0	6	3	10	3	9	5	5	0	91
115	univ	0	3	7	5	7	3	2	6	9	3	8	4	2	6	10	3	0	91
116	AMSCIPUB	0	0	1	1	2	2	6	9	8	7	2	7	8	6	5	7	0	91
117	akiado	0	5	2	3	8	3	3	6	13	8	1	6	10	7	7	3	0	91
118	medwell	0	1	0	2	2	1	3	3	3	5	7	7	6	4	6	7	0	91
119	profengineerpt	0	6	4	8	5	5	6	8	7	11	3	5	9	5	7	5	0	91
120	scielo	0	1	1	3	3	4	3	5	4	7	7	3	6	5	6	6	0	91
121	daedalus	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	3	1	3	7	6	0	91
122	decker	0	5	4	4	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	3	3	9	4	0	91
123	libertas	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	1	3	3	7	2	7	0	91
124	sharpe	0	0	1	5	5	2	0	1	4	6	2	2	1	4	8	4	0	91
125	advanstar	0	1	3	2	5	12	14	6	10	9	9	3	7	4	4	6	0	91
126	begell	0	4	0	6	3	4	6	5	3	3	4	7	5	6	5	3	0	91
127	ceol	0	0	3	2	7	0	7	7	11	8	1	7	5	7	3	4	0	91
128	kluwerhealth	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0	4	5	4	5	4	0	91
129	kluwerlaw	0	2	5	6	4	9	7	6	4	7	5	7	4	6	3	4	0	91
130	beck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	9	0	0	0	91
131	kluwer	0	3	6	2	3	5	7	3	4	2	9	4	5	6	5	1	0	91
132	csic	0	1	0	0	0	1	4	1	2	1	3	5	4	2	4	3	0	91
133	duncker	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	1	3	2	2	1	2	6	0	91
134	commground	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	4	2	2	0	0	91
135	scipub	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5	2	1	0	91
136	telford	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	4	0	0	91
137	aosis	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	2	0	0	91
138	poiesis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	1	4	1	4	2	0	91
139	igi	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	4	4	1	4	2	2	2	2	0	91
140	igitur	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	3	4	1	1	0	91
141	intellect	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	2	0	91
142	nomos	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	1	1	4	0	91
143	soecd	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	91
144	clsje	0	0	0	2	2	3	3	1	2	2	0	2	2	3	2	0	0	91
145	csa	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	0	2	2	1	0	91
146	ecentury	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	2	1	1	3	0	0	91
147	fangeli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	2	1	0	91
148	termedia	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	3	2	0	0	91
149	brepols	0	0	1	2	1	1	2	2	3	0	3	0	4	0	4	0	0	91
150	hmpg	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	2	5	4	1	1	2	0	91
151	pennwell	0	3	2	3	1	2	6	2	2	3	1	2	1	3	1	0	0	91
152	samedan	0	0	0	1	6	2	1	7	1	2	3	1	0	3	1	0	0	91
153	strct	0	1	0	7	2	2	1	3	4	0	0	1	4	0	3	1	0	91
154	acadmana	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	1	1	1	0	91
155	rsocnz	0	12	0	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	91
156	abacad	0	1	0	0	1	3	4	1	3	1	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	91
157	chinmed	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	91
158	ciao	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0	2	4	1	1	1	0	0	91
159	rapra	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	91
160	acadj	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	5	3	6	0	0	0	1	0	0	91
161	chroma	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	91
162	claypool	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	91

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tab 10 number of articles from Switzerland - all publishers identified

provider	OA mode	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]	
163	frontbiosci	0	0	3	4	2	2	3	3	4	2	1	1	4	0	1	0	91	
164	guilford	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	91	
165	hanser	0	2	0	22	14	11	15	6	0	0	0	3	1	0	1	0	91	
166	heldref	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	91	
167	livrev	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	91	
168	niscair	0	1	2	3	1	2	1	0	6	1	1	2	0	0	1	0	91	
169	serisc	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	91	
170	slavica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	91	
171	transtech	0	25	3	2	2	3	0	0	3	3	2	0	1	1	0	0	91	
172	aashpc	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	91	
173	advanst	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
174	ansi	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
175	apa	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	91	
176	baywood	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
177	beech	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
178	berkeley	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
179	gauthier	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
180	humankinetics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	91	
181	iasc	0	3	2	1	1	3	4	1	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	91	
182	ibm	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
183	iscip	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	91	
184	jane	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
185	nowpub	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	91	
186	pabst	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	1	0	6	0	0	0	91	
187	penton	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
188	primedia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	91	
189	reed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	91	
190	rsshj	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	91	
191	sabinet	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	91	
192	socdem	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	91	
193	swets	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	91	
194	xx	9	1,392	1,708	1,887	2,107	2,366	2,479	2,508	2,634	2,620	2,860	2,951	3,090	3,057	2,906	2,697	9	100

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]	
total		total		13,732	13,732	15,938	17,523	18,727	20,778	21,698	22,586	23,978	25,394	27,632	30,116	31,362	32,548	31,333			
1	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS ONE	2006	0	0	0	0	0	4	58	105	169	238	446	699	884	809	707	2	2
2	EMH		Revue Médicale Suisse	0	0	0	0	328	318	287	264	234	261	216	251	300	235	294		3	3
3	APS		Physical Review B :: Condensed Matter and Materie	0	108	124	176	184	241	230	254	250	272	302	314	313	276	288	242	4	4
4	Springer	scoop3	Journal of High Energy Physics	2014	70	57	72	76	71	91	116	117	103	124	143	246	260	249	246	5	5
5	APS		Physical Review Letters	0	100	115	137	202	221	219	240	282	236	244	250	315	279	247	210	5	6
6	APS		Physical Review D :: Particles, Fields, Gravitation, a	0	99	114	81	89	93	105	106	152	151	146	186	194	203	192	178	6	6
7	NAS		Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences c	0	78	68	80	91	115	90	127	103	144	130	139	156	195	179	127	7	7
8	EDP		Astronomy and Astrophysics	0	54	45	122	109	125	119	143	95	129	208	154	150	156	171	169	7	7
9	NPG		Nature Communications	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	26	52	92	160	230	8	8
10	Hogrefe		Schweizerische Rundschau für Medizin Praxis	0	188	163	191	192	195	209	202	111	101	103	115	104	144	135	134	8	8
11	NPG		Scientific Reports	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	37	77	86	230		8	9
12	Wiley		Angewandte Chemie International Edition	0	53	37	55	59	68	55	78	89	80	94	105	107	95	114	132	9	10
13	AAS		The Astrophysical Journal	0	22	29	50	57	62	63	70	84	95	97	100	103	86	117	130	9	10
14	AIP		Applied Physics Letters	0	47	64	58	73	85	108	114	100	103	111	94	100	110	134	87	9	10
15	Elsevier		Physics Letters B	2014	136	140	99	102	97	75	55	62	58	59	103	151	115	98	98	10	11
16	OUP		Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society	0	10	16	18	52	51	43	44	44	50	51	85	108	94	115	96	10	11
17	ACS		Environmental Science and Technology	0	32	45	41	44	82	67	71	80	92	73	81	110	114	96	91	10	11
18	EMH		Swiss Medical Weekly	2001	74	60	52	66	71	83	90	76	86	130	131	148	124	94	70	11	12
19	Elsevier		Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Resea	0	115	95	52	53	74	187	167	94	128	59	86	64	127	88	62	11	12
20	Hogrefe		Therapeutische Umschau	0	92	70	89	83	108	89	59	83	75	80	81	97	101	84	86	11	12
21	ACS		Journal of the American Chemical Society	0	39	58	68	85	80	99	62	91	73	81	84	96	87	85	85	11	12
22	IOP		Journal of Instrumentation	0	0	0	0	0	5	16	42	37	63	43	80	84	97	69		12	13
23	NPG		Nature	0	52	22	35	42	58	52	45	60	58	67	76	75	68	76	106	12	13
24	Springer	scoop3	The European Physical Journal - C :: Particles and I	2014	64	44	70	90	43	61	65	43	40	60	75	83	67	78	99	12	13
25	Copernicus	oaonly	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	2001	0	8	11	15	22	46	37	46	57	78	79	62	68	82	78	12	13
26	AAAS		Science	0	19	29	42	60	50	54	49	47	64	60	63	71	68	73	81	13	14
27	RSC		Physical Chemistry, Chemical Physics	0	14	13	20	18	22	15	18	27	46	64	55	58	62	82	78	13	14
28	Wiley		Chemistry - A European Journal	0	39	36	35	43	49	56	52	60	83	90	67	74	77	81	63	13	14
29	OSA		Optics Express	1997	5	3	8	12	35	36	35	53	54	76	67	56	65	82	74	13	14
30	ACS		The Journal of Physical Chemistry C :: Nanomateria	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	47	51	59	60	61	57	80	82	14	15
31	AIP		The Journal of Chemical Physics	0	52	46	54	44	64	62	48	56	68	44	61	55	52	79	87	14	15
32	chimia		CHIMIA International Journal for Chemistry	0	128	63	63	59	58	59	45	75	86	80	74	57	73	89	46	14	15
33	ASBMB		Journal of Biological Chemistry	0	166	153	160	182	116	118	97	96	105	99	106	106	65	81	59	14	15
34	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	19	21	32	47	53	50	69	76	15	16
35	OUP		European Heart Journal	0	10	10	14	15	17	22	19	20	31	34	44	37	44	62	72	15	16
36	OUP		Nucleic Acids Research	1996	25	18	30	36	39	35	42	31	44	24	46	54	57	71	49	15	16
37	ACS		Nano Letters	0	1	5	5	8	12	25	24	24	32	38	40	47	46	57	67	15	16
38	chagro		Agrarforschung Schweiz	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70	50	50	63	15	16
39	RSC		Chemical Communications	0	16	19	41	34	38	35	35	50	36	47	71	70	46	61	54	16	17
40	Wiley		Geophysical Research Letteres	0	24	22	26	30	33	37	41	45	42	30	44	42	48	51	62	16	17
41	Elsevier		NeuroImage	0	6	10	16	18	20	39	23	45	32	41	40	56	57	54	49	16	17
42	Elsevier		Vaccine	0	25	18	27	24	27	37	51	30	43	31	47	47	63	37	59	16	17
43	AIP		Journal of Applied Physics	0	40	32	22	33	53	70	51	58	55	41	43	44	59	55	45	16	17
44	Springer		Methods in Molecular Biology	0	1	5	3	17	3	6	10	43	21	25	30	193	65	89	4	16	17
45	OUP		Annals of Oncology	0	31	13	41	25	56	20	65	76	55	33	36	60	56	47	53	17	18
46	APS		Physical Review A :: Atomic, Molecular, and Optical	0	24	11	20	22	27	32	38	38	36	56	53	62	54	45	57	17	18
47	RSOCLondon		Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series	0	6	9	17	20	24	41	20	22	25	11	26	39	48	70	37	17	18
48	ASM		Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy	0	15	13	26	28	26	31	36	22	38	38	43	51	38	59	58	17	18
49	IOP	scoop3	Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics	0	0	0	9	6	8	17	11	20	31	28	51	47	61	55	36	17	18
50	RSC		RSC Advances	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	14	36	55	61	17	18	
51	ACS		Langmuir	0	21	34	33	34	51	32	41	46	52	62	46	45	54	47	49	18	19
52	ACS		Analytical Chemistry	0	27	25	25	24	23	28	27	39	30	30	31	33	47	46	56	18	19

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

	provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]	
53	Springer		Lecture Notes in Computer Science	0	0	233	274	2	3	0	2	0	0	74	25	5	120	22	18	19		
54	jneurosci		Journal of Neuroscience	0	19	29	27	41	32	46	49	48	37	64	58	63	42	41	18	19		
55	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Genetics	2005	0	0	0	0	5	10	13	13	21	36	25	39	48	53	42	18	19	
56	APS		Physical Review E :: Statistical, Nonlinear, and Soft	0	30	32	36	35	25	35	50	45	54	35	52	40	54	42	46	18	19	
57	IOP		New Journal of Physics	1998	4	12	6	13	9	10	16	31	41	50	43	50	59	43	39	19	19	
58	Wiley		Water Resources Research	0	6	8	5	8	11	21	21	32	28	38	39	45	51	43	47	19	19	
59	IEEE		IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity	0	0	3	1	1	1	0	2	3	0	0	29	75	57	25	57	19	20	
60	ACS		ACS Nano	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	11	19	29	39	42	52	43	19	20	
61	Huber		Schweizer Archiv für Tierheilkunde	0	38	50	46	37	37	47	39	46	51	53	54	51	53	43	41	19	20	
62	Elsevier		Science of The Total Environment	0	10	6	1	7	5	10	8	18	13	15	14	20	30	57	49	19	20	
63	Frontiers	oaonly	Frontiers in Psychology	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	15	27	30	52	52	19	20
64	Elsevier		Earth and Planetary Science Letters	0	25	28	15	32	29	34	34	32	36	34	31	35	42	52	39	20	20	
65	Thieme		Klinische Monatsblätter für Augenheilkunde	0	30	7	0	3	5	3	43	53	37	33	30	44	38	39	53	20	21	
66	Hindawi	oaonly	biomed research international	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	46	58	20	21	
67	ACS		Journal of Medicinal Chemistry	0	15	17	25	27	46	28	23	30	31	50	26	50	41	42	40	20	21	
68	Elsevier		The Lancet	0	33	38	35	40	38	62	73	76	60	58	53	44	36	34	52	20	21	
69	APS		Physical Review C :: Nuclear Physics	0	29	9	20	26	32	26	25	32	34	40	46	39	30	47	44	20	21	
70	BMC	oaonly	Malaria Journal	2002	0	3	3	5	12	13	17	33	34	35	50	44	39	42	39	20	21	
71	chforst		Schweizerische Zeitschrift für Forstwesen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	47	40	36	41	43	21	22	
72	RSC		Dalton Transactions	0	10	13	22	17	22	23	19	19	27	35	42	32	34	41	41	21	22	
73	Elsevier		Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta	0	13	19	24	15	36	19	28	23	36	32	37	32	35	46	34	21	22	
74	RSC		Nanoscale	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	9	12	21	32	31	52	21	22	
75	Elsevier		Current Biology	0	10	14	16	14	16	15	8	16	13	22	35	40	31	44	38	21	22	
76	amerai		Journal of Immunology	0	30	26	44	60	61	73	49	64	61	49	54	46	26	50	35	21	22	
77	ACS		The Journal of Physical Chemistry B :: Condensed I	0	27	50	36	64	57	68	30	37	47	43	36	30	33	41	36	21	22	
78	Wiley		Clinical Oral Implants Research	0	12	6	12	21	12	22	31	22	32	16	28	42	18	33	58	21	22	
79	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Pathogens	2005	0	0	0	0	3	6	8	10	21	29	29	36	36	38	35	22	23	
80	Elsevier		International Journal of Cardiology	0	2	5	2	4	9	14	22	12	17	11	8	16	48	27	33	22	23	
81	univchicago		Clinical Infectious Diseases	0	10	5	16	19	20	14	10	31	22	26	19	38	30	16	59	22	23	
82	AIP		Review of Scientific Instruments	0	13	10	18	15	24	22	25	27	26	19	26	36	27	44	33	22	23	
83	Elsevier		Cell Reports	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	30	29	45	22	23	
84	OUP		Geophysical Journal International	0	8	3	13	11	7	14	19	15	28	19	18	31	40	40	23	22	23	
85	Copernicus	oaonly	Biogeosciences	2004	0	0	0	0	2	3	5	10	25	17	19	29	30	36	36	22	23	
86	RSC		Chemical Science	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	16	21	29	34	39	22	23	
87	Wiley		Acta Crystallographica Section E :: Structure Report	2008	0	0	22	19	17	33	29	19	13	20	22	10	3	14	83	22	24	
88	IEEE		IEEE Transactions on Information Theory	0	4	9	10	6	21	26	15	23	17	25	24	27	31	43	26	22	24	
89	BMC	oaonly	BMC Public Health	2001	1	2	4	3	5	13	16	19	12	26	34	41	34	36	29	22	24	
90	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Computational Biology	2005	0	0	0	0	3	3	12	9	17	19	19	31	28	34	37	23	24	
91	ACS		The Journal of Physical Chemistry A :: Molecules, S	0	23	31	29	35	20	41	33	33	32	41	29	21	41	21	37	23	24	
92	Frontiers	oaonly	Frontiers in Human Neuroscience	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	9	8	12	33	48	16	23	24	
93	IOP		Journal of Physics - Condensed Matter	0	21	19	28	43	39	39	35	48	40	26	35	40	34	25	38	23	24	
94	Karger		Schweizerische Zeitschrift für Ganzheitsmedizin	0	0	17	14	10	9	18	17	15	8	6	28	31	28	32	36	23	25	
95	elife		eLife	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	14	30	52	23	25	
96	ash		Blood	0	32	44	29	19	23	15	52	53	46	59	73	50	33	39	23	23	25	
97	Elsevier		Water Research	0	10	9	14	7	20	19	23	21	18	24	21	18	35	25	33	23	25	
98	ACS		Organic Letters	0	11	25	24	32	27	23	22	25	15	26	33	35	35	32	25	23	25	
99	Elsevier		Journal of Chromatography A	0	19	12	10	27	21	26	26	29	19	31	21	30	36	25	30	23	25	
100	AAS		The Astrophysical Journal Letters	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	25	22	32	23	36	24	25	
101	Wiley		Journal of Geophysical Research - D - Atmosphere	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	25	30	36	24	25	
102	Wiley		Molecular Ecology	0	13	17	13	17	22	13	30	21	23	34	28	46	32	34	24	24	25	
103	soceurs	oaonly	European Respiratory Journal	0	9	11	9	12	10	15	15	27	19	20	22	26	29	38	23	24	25	
104	ACS		ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	9	9	19	23	25	41	24	26	
105	ASM		Journal of Virology	0	14	30	31	39	35	22	35	32	24	31	35	30	24	32	33	24	26	
106	Elsevier		Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Resea	0	6	12	5	7	7	18	35	41	12	34	5	5	32	22	34	24	26	
107	APS		Physical Review Accelerators and Beams	1998	9	10	8	8	3	9	18	14	18	13	25	17	22	34	32	24	26	

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108	EMH		Swiss Archives of Neurology, Psychiatry and Psych	1997	24	23	23	31	38	40	26	40	33	39	39	27	32	28	27	24	26
109	BMC	oaonly	Parasites and Vectors	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	7	14	19	21	26	39	24	26
110	Wiley		--nn--	0	5	1	1	2	4	8	16	4	9	12	16	19	15	15	55	24	26
111	LWW		Neurology	0	29	15	20	32	29	29	17	23	20	17	31	26	26	26	33	24	26
112	ACS		Chemistry of Materials	0	5	12	3	15	12	9	14	14	15	12	15	7	27	22	36	25	27
113	Wiley		Journal of Evolutionary Biology	0	12	4	9	14	12	14	25	15	24	23	31	22	30	30	24	25	27
114	Wiley		New Phytologist	0	7	9	5	11	8	18	14	16	14	18	14	18	27	24	33	25	27
115	ACS		Inorganic Chemistry	0	39	19	36	44	36	41	33	46	32	32	41	36	29	29	26	25	27
116	Elsevier		Journal of Dairy Science	0	3	6	6	6	14	10	10	10	13	9	19	11	31	28	25	25	27
117	Copernicus	oaonly	Atmospheric Measurement Techniques	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	15	24	27	20	30	34	25	27
118	Springer		Clinical Oral Investigations	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	6	5	5	11	16	21	39	28	16	25	27
119	Wiley		Magnetic Resonance in Medicine	0	13	11	15	19	14	17	13	21	25	17	19	25	22	27	33	25	27
120	Elsevier		Acta Materialia	0	11	7	12	14	10	16	17	24	28	17	41	21	23	30	29	25	27
121	BMJ		British Journal of Sports Medicine	0	1	1	1	6	1	10	13	8	11	14	16	19	35	18	28	25	27
122	Elsevier		Nuclear Physics B	2014	77	65	50	49	50	41	27	20	22	28	26	31	38	22	20	25	27
123	Wiley		Allergy	0	9	17	10	12	12	20	13	16	23	12	26	25	23	34	22	25	27
124	Elsevier		Forensic Science International	0	9	6	13	10	15	13	28	22	14	16	33	29	33	28	18	26	28
125	Elsevier		Neuron	0	6	11	8	5	11	7	14	6	8	6	14	20	23	22	34	26	28
126	LWW		AIDS	0	25	21	26	22	15	14	21	19	18	30	14	20	22	46	11	26	28
127	IEEE		IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science	0	1	26	7	15	19	41	13	1	10	9	12	19	31	30	18	26	28
128	ACS		Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	0	0	0	0	0	3	8	11	10	16	18	18	31	32	19	28	26	28
129	BMJ		Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases	0	8	9	5	15	16	9	11	12	23	32	30	33	25	21	33	26	28
130	ASM		Journal of Clinical Microbiology	0	13	9	25	21	21	27	25	19	26	34	32	21	19	32	27	26	28
131	Elsevier		Cell	0	5	8	11	19	10	16	13	12	10	17	25	19	24	23	30	26	28
132	BMJ		BMJ Case Reports	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14	10	11	13	33	23	21	26	28
133	Springer		European Radiology	0	20	36	28	19	19	15	33	30	31	27	32	17	23	28	25	26	28
134	Elsevier		Journal of Hydrology	0	12	10	11	8	11	12	10	6	17	11	17	21	16	26	34	26	28
135	RSC		Soft Matter	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	3	9	17	21	44	40	30	26	20	26	28
136	RSC		Journal of Materials Chemistry A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	35	26	27	29
137	BMC	oaonly	BMC Genomics	2000	0	1	0	1	2	7	13	13	16	24	12	18	20	31	24	27	29
138	LWW		New England Journal of Medicine	0	14	15	15	22	22	21	17	18	11	22	21	30	21	22	31	27	29
139	OUP		Bioinformatics	0	3	4	3	4	12	15	12	12	14	16	15	20	19	32	23	27	29
140	univchicago		Journal of Infectious Diseases	0	4	10	24	18	19	18	12	16	22	27	37	34	18	40	16	27	29
141	Elsevier		Journal of Nuclear Materials	0	6	22	3	1	2	28	36	22	51	10	19	16	32	28	13	27	29
142	who		Bulletin of the World Health Organization	1947	19	21	21	32	31	30	26	32	23	34	20	25	36	17	20	27	29
143	Wiley		Advanced Functional Materials	0	5	5	8	2	7	25	12	11	20	15	20	16	21	25	26	27	29
144	Wiley		Evolution	0	11	13	24	10	7	16	10	18	17	19	26	30	25	28	19	27	29
145	Copernicus	oaonly	Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	1997	0	0	5	1	2	6	10	4	13	10	21	18	24	29	19	27	29
146	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Medicine	2004	0	0	0	1	7	12	21	16	15	13	41	29	29	19	24	27	29
147	OUP		Human Molecular Genetics	0	11	10	11	8	13	11	9	10	22	11	14	21	23	29	20	27	29
148	RSC		Lab on a Chip - Miniaturisation for Chemistry and Bi	0	7	5	3	8	10	3	12	9	23	17	17	29	21	27	24	28	29
149	AACR		Clinical Cancer Research	0	4	2	16	19	23	13	19	33	27	15	20	20	26	26	28	30	30
150	Wiley		Advanced Materials	0	15	8	12	6	9	9	18	25	15	26	18	20	29	21	21	28	30
151	Elsevier		Atmospheric Environment	0	14	11	10	15	23	19	18	19	18	18	17	26	18	22	31	28	30
152	Elsevier		Biomaterials	0	12	14	20	16	32	23	18	15	18	33	31	17	27	20	24	28	30
153	BMC	oaonly	BMC Infectious Diseases	2001	1	0	1	2	4	8	7	11	8	23	16	18	19	27	25	28	30
154	LWW		Stroke	0	5	5	7	17	17	21	12	10	18	13	15	23	28	30	13	28	30
155	Impact	oaonly	OncoTarget	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	12	58	28	30
156	jove		Journal of visualized experiments : JoVE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	19	15	32	23	28	30
157	Elsevier		Quaternary Science Reviews	0	5	2	6	3	5	12	13	11	17	30	25	17	18	33	18	28	30
158	IOP		Physics in Medicine and Biology	0	4	3	9	13	11	10	15	17	17	24	23	18	25	24	20	28	30
159	Wiley		Ecology and Evolution	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	12	28	25	16	28	30
160	Springer		Oecologia	0	14	7	14	9	21	12	10	10	12	17	13	13	28	23	16	28	30
161	Wiley		International Journal of Cancer	0	19	17	13	10	19	31	14	23	19	18	19	25	22	17	27	29	30
162	OUP		European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery	0	22	18	9	10	11	19	21	23	27	13	26	26	20	37	9	29	31

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163	IOP	Nuclear Fusion	0	11	12	16	7	12	7	23	4	15	10	20	14	22	15	29	29	31
164	OUP	Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy	0	4	7	5	11	5	9	12	19	11	12	22	14	18	29	19	29	31
165	BMJ	BMJ Open	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	13	17	21	28	29	31
166	Elsevier	Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters	0	22	20	20	19	17	27	22	30	34	48	28	20	20	26	19	29	31
167	Elsevier	Electrochimica Acta	0	7	14	3	11	7	11	10	9	11	9	22	10	25	17	23	29	31
168	RSOCLondon	Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of L	0	3	2	2	0	2	3	1	11	6	13	22	11	25	22	18	29	31
169	Elsevier	Journal of Biomechanics	0	30	4	11	11	4	13	17	15	20	19	15	18	20	18	26	29	31
170	AAAS	Science Translational Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	5	9	16	22	26	29	31
171	ACS	The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	11	14	17	24	23	29	31
172	Elsevier	Journal of Computational Physics	0	5	6	8	7	8	9	16	11	13	15	18	14	17	18	28	29	31
173	Copernicus	oaonly	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	3	12	11	12	17	17	29	29	31
174	ASM	Applied and Environmental Microbiology	0	16	17	33	21	31	34	28	22	26	39	32	33	29	14	20	29	31
175	Frontiers	oaonly	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	13	12	15	36	29	32
176	Springer	Journal of Neurology	0	5	11	6	2	10	8	12	15	15	12	17	23	22	27	13	30	32
177	Elsevier	Cement and Concrete Research	0	3	6	5	5	3	10	9	17	10	17	20	24	18	13	31	30	32
178	Elsevier	Cortex	0	0	2	0	3	3	5	1	1	7	5	6	6	29	16	17	30	32
179	Elsevier	European Journal of Cancer	2012	15	17	28	21	10	16	29	23	28	22	16	34	21	24	17	30	32
180	Elsevier	Nuclear Physics A	0	48	41	47	29	44	16	17	9	26	7	21	1	30	29	3	30	32
181	Elsevier	Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology	0	3	3	3	9	4	3	3	4	2	8	6	20	11	29	22	30	32
182	cbiol	Development	0	13	15	19	18	19	21	21	15	15	21	19	18	19	25	18	30	32
183	Elsevier	Clinical Microbiology and Infection	0	5	8	5	7	2	11	5	5	7	18	27	22	9	29	23	30	32
184	Elsevier	Journal of Hepatology	0	12	13	6	14	12	20	13	12	13	11	20	17	19	24	18	30	32
185	Elsevier	The Lancet Oncology	0	2	6	2	4	3	4	4	7	7	6	10	20	17	22	22	30	32
186	Frontiers	oaonly	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	13	23	16	22	30	32
187	Springer	European Spine Journal	0	10	11	13	13	20	27	19	16	23	21	24	41	16	33	11	30	32
188	Wiley	Global Change Biology	0	2	5	8	8	9	15	9	9	8	19	18	15	15	25	20	30	32
189	Elsevier	Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecolog	0	5	8	7	7	10	12	11	17	17	8	11	22	28	10	22	30	32
190	Frontiers	oaonly	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	5	10	7	16	14	30	30	33
191	Copernicus	oaonly	2005	0	0	0	0	0	3	12	1	3	7	11	20	26	19	15	31	33
192	OSA	Optics Letters	0	17	7	16	15	29	25	20	12	25	20	22	25	18	31	11	31	33
193	Wiley	Journal of Geophysical Research - B - Solid Earth	0	9	5	1	1	5	10	13	15	20	17	18	20	21	22	17	31	33
194	Wiley	Ecology Letters	0	5	4	2	4	7	6	3	11	3	9	15	18	17	23	19	31	33
195	Elsevier	Journal of the American College of Cardiology	0	7	11	18	8	17	8	12	11	13	16	25	14	15	24	20	31	33
196	Elsevier	Tectonophysics	0	11	11	10	8	13	17	7	14	13	17	16	14	30	15	14	31	33
197	MDPI	oaonly	2004	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	6	2	1	11	27	21	31	33
198	CUP	Journal of Fluid Mechanics	0	5	2	10	7	5	2	8	6	8	10	7	7	22	21	16	31	33
199	OUP	Brain	0	9	10	8	8	6	12	12	13	15	24	15	18	18	18	23	31	33
200	Elsevier	Molecular Cell	0	11	8	15	13	8	11	10	9	9	7	11	18	18	20	20	31	33
201	ACS	Organometallics	0	15	10	11	20	26	24	23	22	29	20	17	28	18	21	19	31	33
202	AACR	Cancer Research	0	21	8	17	28	29	19	26	28	28	20	24	18	27	20	11	31	33
203	Wiley	ChemBioChem	0	9	19	11	19	21	18	11	18	26	15	12	12	23	12	22	31	33
204	Wiley	European Journal of Immunology	0	44	34	25	23	41	35	35	32	15	30	16	23	19	19	19	31	33
205	Wiley	Human Brain Mapping	0	2	2	1	4	4	7	3	8	17	7	8	16	11	29	17	31	33
206	Elsevier	Chemical Geology	0	6	17	4	10	8	9	12	18	12	12	19	23	25	17	15	31	33
207	ACS	Journal of Proteome Research	0	0	1	0	4	8	11	20	13	25	14	15	22	20	12	25	32	34
208	cbiol	Journal of Cell Science	0	14	10	18	26	25	27	17	18	21	23	15	22	20	19	18	32	34
209	Springer	International Orthopaedics	0	2	4	2	2	1	1	3	4	7	6	13	19	20	25	11	32	34
210	Springer	Swiss Journal of Geosciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	32	23	21	26	10	28	16	12	32	34
211	Wiley	Hepatology	0	8	8	6	3	6	13	12	16	19	16	18	16	24	18	14	32	34
212	MDPI	oaonly	2001	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	18	1	15	5	16	15	28	13	32	34
213	aspb	Plant Physiology	0	14	8	17	22	16	12	11	16	12	13	20	13	17	14	25	32	34
214	asco	Journal of Clinical Oncology	0	3	5	10	10	10	13	11	17	6	9	20	35	19	18	19	32	34
215	Springer	Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry	0	9	6	12	12	7	11	16	22	16	25	26	24	24	17	14	32	34
216	Elsevier	Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology	0	7	7	10	14	9	13	17	14	21	15	30	29	18	18	19	32	34
217	BMC	oaonly	2000	1	0	1	1	4	4	5	12	3	17	17	15	18	18	19	32	34

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

	provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]
218	RSC		Energy and Environmental Science	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6	6	20	17	14	17	24	32	34
219	Elsevier		Journal of Forensic Radiology and Imaging	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	18	16	32	34
220	Elsevier		Acta Biomaterialia	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	3	6	12	22	10	16	17	21	16	32	34
221	Elsevier		Chemosphere	0	3	7	10	9	11	11	17	15	10	15	18	11	15	19	20	32	34
222	Elsevier		Geomorphology	0	1	2	2	3	7	6	6	9	14	18	10	16	14	22	18	32	34
223	Elsevier		Bone :: Official Journal of the International Bone and Joint Society	0	7	9	11	12	14	14	14	17	15	15	22	15	20	17	16	32	34
224	Elsevier		Journal of Affective Disorders	0	3	4	5	6	5	6	9	6	8	14	13	16	12	27	14	33	35
225	NPG		British Journal of Cancer	0	12	10	14	13	10	18	12	19	19	17	8	21	13	23	17	33	35
226	IEEE		IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics	0	1	1	2	3	4	4	7	8	12	5	8	18	19	20	14	33	35
227	schatt		Thrombosis and Haemostasis	0	7	8	14	18	19	20	11	12	16	8	18	9	19	14	20	33	35
228	Wiley		The EMBO Journal	0	39	30	35	28	27	46	31	19	41	23	34	27	21	12	19	33	35
229	Karger		Dermatology	0	19	15	8	12	30	15	7	15	14	19	17	16	21	13	18	33	35
230	Springer		Springer Plus	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	26	16	33	35
231	Springer		Osteoporosis International	0	5	10	3	8	14	7	9	11	11	14	14	23	23	14	14	33	35
232	Wiley		Helvetica Chimica Acta	0	106	115	102	75	66	58	32	26	32	30	22	31	22	10	19	33	35
233	Elsevier		Injury	0	18	8	8	16	4	14	6	10	8	15	15	14	19	16	16	33	35
234	Elsevier		Neuropsychologia	0	4	6	2	3	6	7	18	13	17	18	16	11	13	13	25	33	35
235	BMC	oaonly	Radiation Oncology	2006	0	0	0	0	0	5	5	8	5	11	15	15	14	20	17	33	35
236	NPG		Nature Genetics	0	5	2	8	10	12	13	10	17	22	23	18	28	22	14	15	33	35
237	IOP		Nanotechnology	0	0	4	5	9	14	17	34	30	35	36	29	26	19	16	16	33	35
238	NPG		Nature Geoscience	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	10	9	12	14	16	16	19	33	35
239	GSW		Geology	0	7	8	2	18	7	12	18	8	11	9	23	20	19	16	16	33	35
240	endocsoc		Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism	0	22	19	12	21	24	14	24	16	20	21	21	28	23	17	11	33	35
241	Frontiers	oaonly	Frontiers in Plant Science	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	10	17	13	21	33	35
242	Springer		Acta Neurochirurgica	0	6	10	10	10	34	7	8	6	8	34	11	16	14	18	18	33	36
243	Springer		Archives of Orthopaedic and Trauma Surgery	0	11	4	3	6	7	5	13	14	11	21	24	21	19	13	18	33	36
244	Wiley		Plant Journal	0	12	11	12	13	14	11	23	17	17	18	18	19	22	18	10	34	36
245	Elsevier		Engineering Structures	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	3	4	7	10	5	8	11	21	18	34	36
246	Elsevier		European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharma	0	7	4	11	12	7	3	6	16	11	8	13	9	22	11	17	34	36
247	Elsevier		Psychiatry Research	0	0	3	2	8	4	3	5	8	5	8	15	19	20	18	12	34	36
248	BMC	oaonly	BMC Evolutionary Biology	2001	0	0	0	2	1	3	18	12	16	18	24	14	18	12	20	34	36
249	Sage		Multiple Sclerosis	0	0	1	3	4	5	3	7	9	6	6	12	25	16	22	12	34	36
250	Elsevier		Animal Behaviour	0	6	5	9	10	5	8	12	21	14	10	23	15	16	12	21	34	36
251	Elsevier		European Journal of Radiology	0	0	1	2	2	6	2	2	14	7	14	16	40	21	12	16	34	36
252	Elsevier		Forest Ecology and Management	0	10	6	9	7	10	15	3	12	17	6	17	6	17	20	12	34	36
253	Elsevier		Journal of Power Sources	0	4	2	1	8	4	13	15	12	15	18	17	13	12	13	24	34	36
254	Elsevier		Neuroscience	0	15	13	13	20	17	20	10	17	24	14	13	11	17	14	18	34	36
255	Taylor		Molecular Physics	0	4	6	11	2	8	6	11	6	5	9	8	6	28	5	16	34	36
256	Wiley		ChemCatChem	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	7	7	12	17	19	13	34	36
257	BMC	oaonly	Trials	2006	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	8	2	9	8	14	21	14	34	36
258	IOP		Journal of Physics D :: Applied Physics	0	5	6	5	3	2	11	13	14	9	8	15	12	14	16	19	34	36
259	LWW		Circulation	0	30	19	26	31	18	21	21	21	25	21	24	26	25	12	12	34	36
260	Wiley		Environmental Microbiology	0	2	6	8	3	4	7	10	8	13	10	6	12	19	14	15	34	37
261	Elsevier		Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry	0	9	2	12	8	9	17	8	9	17	27	19	7	25	14	9	34	37
262	Elsevier		Environmental Science and Policy	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	1	4	3	4	6	4	12	14	22	34	37
263	BMC	oaonly	BMC Cancer	2001	0	2	0	1	5	7	5	10	12	10	12	17	13	17	18	34	37
264	PLoS	oaonly	PLoS Biology	2003	0	0	1	7	12	12	22	25	19	15	13	19	13	20	15	34	37
265	Frontiers	oaonly	Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	5	5	11	21	16	35	37
266	IOP		Europhysics Letters	0	19	18	21	22	18	18	19	22	23	32	29	34	22	17	9	35	37
267	AIP		Physics of Plasmas	0	4	4	5	7	4	7	13	11	15	7	10	15	10	20	18	35	37
268	ACS		The Journal of Organic Chemistry	0	17	24	27	17	19	22	21	15	24	12	20	15	27	11	10	35	37
269	RSC		Organic and Biomolecular Chemistry	0	0	0	12	15	15	11	13	15	22	16	18	25	17	9	22	35	37
270	RSOCLondon		Journal of the Royal Society Interface	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	2	9	2	10	6	15	14	18	16	35	37
271	ACS		ACS Catalysis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	26	15	13	20	35	37
272	Springer		European Journal of Applied Physiology	0	5	2	9	6	6	14	8	9	10	15	18	15	17	21	9	35	37

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

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273	Springer	European Journal of Pediatrics			21	11	17	10	18	10	9	11	13	12	13	9	11	17	19	35	37
274	Wiley	Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine	2015		2	1	4	4	3	14	10	12	10	18	9	7	11	22	14	35	37
275	Elsevier	Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells			6	3	4	2	2	6	10	2	5	5	14	13	19	14	14	35	37
276	BMC	BMC Health Services Research	2001		0	0	0	2	4	15	4	12	6	14	11	15	15	17	35	37	
277	IEEE	IEEE Transactions on Image Processing			4	7	10	7	10	8	8	14	6	4	12	15	21	17	9	35	37
278	Wiley	Swiss Political Science Review			0	0	0	0	0	15	9	11	17	24	9	18	13	21	13	35	37
279	ACS	Industrial and Engineering Chemistry - Research			9	9	8	14	10	17	13	15	12	11	15	13	12	24	11	35	37
280	Springer	Plant and Soil			10	4	5	8	12	10	8	3	10	13	19	10	16	17	13	35	37
281	Wiley	European Journal of Organic Chemistry			17	13	16	22	18	28	22	17	19	18	28	16	15	15	16	35	38
282	Elsevier	Acta Tropica			9	3	8	2	13	6	8	4	4	5	6	5	18	5	23	35	38
283	Elsevier	Advances in Water Resources			3	2	0	3	3	8	8	16	11	8	2	8	26	11	9	35	38
284	Elsevier	Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis			3	9	4	7	4	4	8	4	7	10	9	14	13	16	17	35	38
285	Elsevier	Schizophrenia Research			3	3	2	1	4	4	11	4	11	10	9	11	14	21	11	36	38
286	LWW	Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal			7	4	8	10	8	6	8	10	5	9	8	11	26	13	7	36	38
287	ACS	Macromolecules			15	17	15	7	26	13	20	17	28	26	25	29	16	18	12	36	38
288	Wiley	Medical Physics			4	4	6	8	4	6	7	4	9	13	24	18	17	21	8	36	38
289	Hogrefe	Pflege			1	1	1	1	2	2	4	4	15	10	8	13	16	16	14	36	38
290	BMC	Critical Care			1	1	1	0	1	11	10	13	16	23	20	15	15	15	16	36	38
291	Wiley	ChemMedChem			0	0	0	0	0	12	20	13	15	20	14	9	12	17	16	36	38
292	Wiley	Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging			19	8	4	11	5	8	15	13	11	15	17	22	14	13	18	36	38
293	Wiley	Journal of Synchrotron Radiation			5	1	1	5	1	2	6	7	11	15	9	13	12	21	12	36	38
294	Elsevier	European Urology			7	9	9	10	11	9	19	23	26	20	18	15	11	21	13	36	38
295	Elsevier	Lithos			3	2	4	3	3	6	7	12	9	8	8	6	14	16	15	36	38
296	Elsevier	Microelectronic Engineering			0	0	0	0	0	25	24	25	20	15	3	6	8	7	30	36	38
297	Elsevier	The Veterinary Journal			3	3	5	6	10	11	18	7	16	14	16	20	21	17	7	36	38
298	Copernicus	Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences	2001		0	4	3	5	8	4	2	9	13	12	13	15	13	14	18	36	38
299	BMC	BMC Veterinary Research	2005		0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	7	2	11	15	16	13	16	36	38
300	BMJ	British Medical Journal			15	10	16	21	19	12	10	15	11	14	17	13	11	12	22	36	38
301	Wiley	Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems			3	0	7	2	4	13	7	10	13	4	12	15	19	14	12	36	39
302	Springer	Intensive Care Medicine			18	18	19	18	9	16	20	18	19	14	21	15	18	15	11	36	39
303	Wiley	European Journal of Neurology			4	0	3	3	9	8	5	4	15	17	12	16	14	15	15	36	39
304	Elsevier	Atherosclerosis			5	4	2	7	4	7	8	7	13	13	14	17	15	8	21	36	39
305	Elsevier	Sensors and Actuators B :: Chemical			9	2	2	3	7	15	10	10	6	8	15	19	15	19	10	36	39
306	Elsevier	Soil Biology and Biochemistry			3	2	7	4	5	10	8	10	5	10	9	6	15	13	16	37	39
307	Elsevier	Veterinary Parasitology			3	5	7	9	5	16	12	10	13	12	17	15	17	10	17	37	39
308	LWW	JAIDS Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Sync			6	4	6	8	8	6	10	9	16	13	17	14	17	15	12	37	39
309	Springer	Communications in Mathematical Physics			14	6	9	12	7	8	10	11	13	8	11	13	13	15	15	37	39
310	Springer	European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecu			0	0	22	13	10	15	17	11	17	22	17	15	11	22	10	37	39
311	Springer	Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy			5	1	0	4	9	11	9	7	4	11	14	12	12	26	5	37	39
312	Wiley	European Journal of Neuroscience			26	26	37	45	30	23	20	21	33	17	24	17	13	17	13	37	39
313	Wiley	Hydrological Processes			2	4	4	4	6	7	7	4	9	12	15	8	12	15	16	37	39
314	Elsevier	Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences			4	4	10	3	6	4	8	13	12	12	26	15	9	15	19	37	39
315	Elsevier	Applied Energy			0	0	2	0	0	2	1	3	1	0	3	6	7	17	19	37	39
316	Elsevier	Remote Sensing of Environment			1	0	2	3	9	4	8	7	6	7	14	14	8	16	19	37	39
317	NPG	Nature Materials			0	2	4	8	5	13	4	12	12	7	8	10	18	12	13	37	39
318	NPG	Nature Methods			0	0	0	0	8	7	9	6	9	10	8	11	14	13	16	37	39
319	NPG	Nature Neuroscience			8	4	6	10	6	9	10	12	18	11	8	16	15	15	13	37	39
320	ACS	Biomacromolecules			2	4	3	5	10	6	10	9	4	13	15	13	15	16	12	37	39
321	coldspring	Genome Research			1	3	2	6	6	1	8	9	8	11	9	13	18	14	11	37	39
322	Wiley	American Journal of Transplantation			1	5	8	12	15	16	9	14	17	12	9	10	18	11	13	37	40
323	Wiley	Tropical Medicine and International Health			26	6	10	23	18	17	17	17	18	25	19	23	14	16	12	37	40
324	Elsevier	Computer Physics Communications			11	3	12	9	7	11	6	13	19	12	13	11	10	20	12	37	40
325	Elsevier	The Biophysical Journal			12	10	29	28	23	35	17	23	14	18	9	11	13	14	15	37	40
326	IOS	Journal of Alzheimer's Disease			1	0	0	1	0	2	0	3	3	7	8	8	9	14	19	37	40
327	OUP	Molecular Biology and Evolution			1	1	8	4	2	5	7	6	11	9	11	14	19	15	8	38	40

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328	ACS		Crystal Growth and Design	0	0	0	1	3	6	6	6	11	17	12	13	13	15	9	18	38	40
329	RSC		Chemical Society Reviews	0	3	0	6	5	7	1	7	3	6	8	4	10	17	11	14	38	40
330	Springer		Lecture Notes in Computational Science and Engin	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	10	0	0	0	0	14	14	14	38	40	
331	Springer		Climatic Change	0	12	1	3	3	3	13	14	9	7	15	10	15	15	9	17	38	40
332	Springer		Skeletal Radiology	0	6	8	3	5	7	3	7	9	3	12	14	15	19	13	9	38	40
333	Springer		World Journal of Surgery	0	3	5	2	4	6	6	5	11	15	13	11	13	13	15	13	38	40
334	Wiley		Computer Graphics Forum	0	4	0	1	0	6	0	8	3	8	10	5	8	21	18	2	38	40
335	Elsevier		Construction and Building Materials	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	2	7	6	8	21	10	12	19	38	40
336	Elsevier		Economics Letters	0	2	3	6	4	3	7	4	9	6	12	9	26	14	16	11	38	40
337	Elsevier		Energy Policy	0	2	2	7	10	6	4	19	8	13	11	23	18	19	13	9	38	40
338	Elsevier		International Journal of Pharmaceutics	0	11	11	3	8	4	8	8	6	10	13	10	10	14	10	17	38	40
339	Elsevier		Journal of Shoulder and Elbow Surgery	0	1	3	3	6	4	11	9	11	12	7	11	15	16	13	12	38	40
340	Elsevier		Nuclear Engineering and Design	0	12	2	1	2	4	5	11	18	14	14	16	12	14	17	10	38	40
341	BMC	oaonly	BMC Research Notes	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	6	16	9	18	12	11	38	40
342	NPG		Nature Physics	0	0	0	0	0	2	10	11	7	10	10	16	16	16	10	15	38	40
343	LWW		Investigative Radiology	0	7	2	4	3	5	3	9	9	8	11	9	10	11	14	16	38	40
344	ecs		Journal of The Electrochemical Society	0	15	6	8	16	7	13	8	12	10	9	14	11	8	8	25	38	40
345	IEEE		IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices	0	4	4	8	3	4	11	11	7	2	9	14	12	15	16	10	38	41
346	OUP		Cerebral Cortex	0	1	6	4	7	13	7	11	13	7	10	7	17	11	21	9	38	41
347	rockefeller		The Journal of Cell Biology	0	22	19	15	11	15	12	12	13	21	19	9	15	15	12	14	38	41
348	CUP		British Journal of Nutrition	0	8	5	4	8	5	8	7	8	13	14	13	11	14	12	15	38	41
349	ASM		mBio	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	3	8	9	24	38	41
350	Springer		Environmental Science and Pollution Research	0	2	1	1	2	5	2	2	3	14	9	6	12	7	12	21	38	41
351	Springer		International Journal of Legal Medicine	0	2	1	1	1	4	6	2	8	5	4	12	14	14	14	12	38	41
352	Springer		Supportive Care in Cancer	0	4	9	2	5	4	4	6	13	2	9	11	6	16	15	9	39	41
353	Wiley		Earth Surface Processes and Landforms	0	1	0	1	0	5	1	5	5	7	7	10	14	10	17	13	39	41
354	Wiley		Journal of Clinical Periodontology	0	13	10	11	10	13	4	11	10	17	16	13	17	10	17	13	39	41
355	Wiley		Journal of Ecology	0	4	5	2	4	7	8	10	8	7	8	11	8	14	15	11	39	41
356	Elsevier		Chemical Physics Letters	0	31	28	34	16	23	22	6	12	16	9	10	8	13	14	13	39	41
357	Elsevier		Energy	0	0	1	5	9	1	6	4	5	4	11	3	23	9	12	19	39	41
358	Elsevier		Environmental Pollution	0	4	1	3	4	4	6	22	11	24	24	20	9	10	18	12	39	41
359	Frontiers	oaonly	Frontiers in Cellular Neuroscience	2007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	12	13	15	39	41
360	IOP		Superconductor Science and Technology	0	2	6	3	10	4	8	7	6	10	10	6	18	10	12	18	39	41
361	OUP		The European Journal of Orthodontics	0	1	0	1	1	2	0	5	4	9	3	1	6	15	20	5	39	41
362	Wiley		Ecology	0	6	11	10	11	11	11	8	16	16	17	11	13	16	11	13	39	41
363	ACS		ACS Chemical Biology	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	0	4	4	2	9	16	11	13	39	41
364	RSC		Journal of Materials Chemistry C	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	9	11	39	41
365	Springer		Psychopharmacology	0	7	6	9	10	15	9	14	7	13	4	12	11	11	22	6	39	41
366	Springer		The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment	0	2	3	6	7	14	6	7	5	10	8	8	7	13	10	16	39	41
367	Wiley		ChemPhysChem :: a European journal of physical c	0	6	5	6	17	18	20	17	16	19	25	20	19	17	10	12	39	42
368	Elsevier		Environment International	0	2	0	2	3	1	2	3	3	2	1	4	8	6	16	17	39	42
369	Elsevier		Journal of Controlled Release	0	11	4	4	8	11	9	6	6	7	16	15	12	9	15	15	39	42
370	Elsevier		The Lancet Infectious Diseases	0	2	8	12	1	10	12	8	7	8	8	13	13	12	11	16	39	42
371	Elsevier		The American Journal of Human Genetics	0	1	4	10	10	6	8	10	18	11	12	18	10	19	11	9	39	42
372	Elsevier		The Annals of Thoracic Surgery	0	12	10	10	15	17	21	19	12	6	17	18	13	13	19	7	39	42
373	Wiley		EMBO Molecular Medicine	2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	8	6	10	12	16	11	39	42
374	Karger		Respiration	0	7	6	5	6	3	6	2	5	4	10	4	13	12	17	10	40	42
375	rockefeller		Journal of Experimental Medicine	0	22	12	18	19	14	13	12	29	12	18	10	13	22	12	5	40	42
376	aspb		Plant Cell	0	7	4	8	12	10	10	15	10	14	14	13	24	19	13	7	40	42
377	ASBMB		Molecular and Cellular Proteomics	0	0	0	0	3	9	12	13	15	10	10	19	28	12	17	10	40	42
378	Wiley		British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology	0	3	7	7	9	4	9	9	4	9	5	8	5	17	8	13	40	42
379	Wiley		European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry	0	10	8	13	17	22	15	24	19	16	20	12	22	17	12	9	40	42
380	Wiley		Functional Ecology	0	4	4	8	3	10	11	12	11	4	7	9	10	11	15	12	40	42
381	Wiley		Journal of Applied Crystallography	0	1	3	5	1	5	4	4	8	11	7	8	4	13	12	13	40	42
382	Wiley		Journal of Biogeography	0	0	2	3	3	2	10	5	9	9	8	21	21	8	17	13	40	42

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]
383	Wiley	Molecular Microbiology	0	15	20	18	15	14	14	14	7	17	10	15	12	14	14	10	40	42
384	Elsevier	The Journal of Investigative Dermatology	0	14	9	12	10	11	10	22	11	9	11	6	10	13	14	11	40	42
385	Wiley	Advanced Energy Materials	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	8	8	15	15	40	42
386	Elsevier	Icarus :: International Journal of Solar System Studi	0	0	3	4	4	1	18	4	3	12	10	13	5	18	12	8	40	42
387	Elsevier	Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution	0	6	1	3	6	5	5	9	18	12	13	7	12	13	17	8	40	42
388	usncid	oaonly	1995	5	5	6	14	7	13	23	15	18	8	14	8	17	5	16	40	42
389	BMC	oaonly	2003	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	3	5	7	10	6	10	7	21	40	42
390	IOP	Journal of Physics A :: Mathematical and Theoretica	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	9	16	9	13	16	13	14	11	40	42
391	NPG	Leukemia	0	4	1	6	7	7	8	8	7	9	4	7	15	10	10	18	40	42
392	AIP	Physics of Fluids	0	7	2	6	1	9	10	6	5	5	9	9	11	12	14	12	40	42
393	OUP	Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	0	0	7	13	21	4	40	43
394	GSW	Geophysics	0	3	6	5	4	5	5	12	5	7	8	9	12	13	9	16	40	43
395	Frontiers	oaonly	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	13	9	13	16	40	43
396	Springer	Molecules Online	1997	2	3	2	0	2	0	1	3	1	5	3	4	12	12	14	40	43
397	Wiley	Journal of Geophysical Research - F - Earth Surfac	0	0	0	0	0	6	9	15	13	4	16	11	13	14	9	15	40	43
398	Springer	Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research	0	3	11	8	10	12	7	5	8	10	12	7	6	11	4	22	40	43
399	Wiley	Human Mutation	0	6	6	2	9	4	9	5	11	20	12	12	17	13	12	12	40	43
400	Wiley	Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis	0	0	0	11	11	9	13	8	10	12	16	10	10	11	15	11	40	43
401	Elsevier	Journal of Banking and Finance	0	2	3	2	9	6	5	7	7	4	15	6	13	16	12	9	41	43
402	Elsevier	Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical M	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	7	10	15	9	13	41	43
403	Elsevier	Journal of Proteomics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	10	12	11	25	13	13	11	41	43
404	Elsevier	Cell Host and Microbe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	8	5	6	10	11	11	15	41	43
405	Elsevier	Cell Metabolism	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	3	7	6	5	11	8	14	15	8	41	43
406	Elsevier	Structure	0	1	7	5	4	7	10	6	3	4	5	2	14	16	13	8	41	43
407	NPG	European Journal of Human Genetics	0	2	1	1	7	3	3	3	5	7	11	9	12	19	9	9	41	43
408	OUP	Journal of Experimental Botany	0	9	3	5	0	3	3	4	5	7	3	11	11	10	11	16	41	43
409	ACS	Biochemistry	0	37	33	31	28	33	24	25	19	24	15	13	16	16	10	11	41	43
410	ACS	Organic Process Research and Development	0	5	4	18	16	5	12	10	7	8	6	10	18	11	12	14	41	43
411	NPG	Nature Climate Change	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	14	12	10	15	41	43
412	Springer	Hyperfine Interactions	0	13	1	2	1	4	3	2	2	10	13	2	19	9	13	14	41	43
413	Wiley	Scandinavian Journal of Medicine and Science in S	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	3	3	11	7	5	10	12	14	41	43
414	Elsevier	Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular Ce	0	0	1	3	3	1	6	2	10	9	3	5	5	19	8	9	41	43
415	Elsevier	Energy and Buildings	0	10	6	3	4	9	3	5	4	0	4	3	11	7	21	8	41	43
416	Elsevier	International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics	0	5	3	3	2	0	8	7	2	9	3	4	10	10	11	15	41	43
417	Elsevier	Journal of Alloys and Compounds	0	10	4	10	4	19	11	14	9	14	17	5	1	12	13	11	41	44
418	Elsevier	Neuropharmacology	0	11	8	10	10	11	3	6	5	4	3	6	12	10	13	13	41	44
419	Elsevier	Psychoneuroendocrinology	0	0	1	1	4	2	5	10	7	8	11	2	11	18	10	8	41	44
420	Elsevier	Radiotherapy and Oncology	0	6	5	7	7	12	11	5	7	12	9	7	10	15	14	7	41	44
421	Elsevier	Immunity	0	5	8	4	2	7	1	5	10	4	11	7	11	10	9	17	41	44
422	Wiley	European Journal of Heart Failure	0	0	3	2	6	7	1	8	7	6	12	19	7	10	8	18	41	44
423	NPG	Neuropsychopharmacology	0	7	5	5	10	7	5	5	9	9	5	9	9	8	15	13	41	44
424	BMC	oaonly	2001	0	0	0	2	2	7	3	3	4	3	14	15	19	9	8	41	44
425	LWW	Journal of Hypertension	0	8	7	3	10	6	13	7	7	13	7	9	9	14	9	13	41	44
426	univchicago	American Naturalist	0	3	4	3	6	3	5	13	6	12	11	10	10	9	10	17	41	44
427	wscipub	International Journal of Modern Physics A :: Particle	0	2	4	3	9	13	6	5	5	0	12	4	7	8	13	15	41	44
428	LWW	Journal of the American Society of Nephrology : JA	0	5	11	10	12	20	10	11	7	8	7	6	8	4	19	13	42	44
429	BMJ	British Heart Journal	0	8	8	8	14	6	10	10	5	13	13	15	15	13	15	8	42	44
430	MDPI	oaonly	2009	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	3	4	9	11	16	42	44
431	Springer	Experimental Brain Research	0	9	9	10	12	11	12	9	17	11	10	16	8	18	12	5	42	44
432	Wiley	BJU International	0	0	4	7	3	4	7	7	9	6	5	7	11	14	11	10	42	44
433	Wiley	British Journal of Dermatology	0	11	11	9	10	12	9	6	14	15	9	11	16	12	12	11	42	44
434	Wiley	Global Ecology	0	2	0	0	1	0	1	4	1	6	3	4	10	15	10	10	42	44
435	Wiley	Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology a	0	1	0	0	3	2	9	3	4	2	7	3	11	6	7	22	42	44
436	Wiley	Proteomics	0	12	15	4	18	11	25	20	10	18	30	15	15	10	14	11	42	44
437	Wiley	American Journal of Medical Genetics Part A	0	0	0	13	11	12	9	6	10	6	11	10	8	10	15	10	42	44

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]
438	Springer	Environmental Earth Sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	5	3	11	11	13	42	44
439	Elsevier	The American Journal of Cardiology	0	4	3	3	7	7	9	7	12	14	10	11	16	12	4	19	42	44
440	Elsevier	Solar Energy	0	1	5	4	7	1	11	11	5	2	8	11	3	9	10	16	42	44
441	Elsevier	Toxicology in Vitro	0	0	3	0	1	0	4	3	3	6	7	8	2	15	10	10	42	45
442	IOP	Environmental Research Letters	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6	4	5	8	7	14	11	10	42	45
443	NPG	Nature Medicine	0	9	5	8	9	15	5	7	9	11	5	7	9	11	8	16	42	45
444	NPG	Nature Structural and Molecular Biology	0	0	0	0	4	3	7	10	4	5	10	8	16	18	8	9	42	45
445	IOP	Smart Materials and Structures	0	0	0	1	4	4	5	9	1	6	5	8	4	13	7	15	42	45
446	Bentham	Current Pharmaceutical Design	0	1	1	6	5	5	5	12	6	3	8	4	18	7	11	17	42	45
447	IEEE	IEEE Sensors Journal	0	1	1	0	4	7	9	2	1	3	2	3	8	12	10	13	42	45
448	OUP	Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation	0	12	12	12	22	24	14	16	14	23	13	19	20	9	12	14	42	45
449	OUP	Schizophrenia Bulletin	0	1	1	0	5	1	2	3	0	4	4	10	10	4	18	13	42	45
450	NPG	Bone Marrow Transplantation	0	2	8	6	9	8	9	5	10	11	13	15	13	11	9	15	42	45
451	Copernicus	Geoscientific Model Development	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	8	15	12	42	45
452	Springer	Gynäkologische Endokrinologie	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	4	3	6	7	13	11	10	42	45
453	Springer	Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology	0	1	0	1	4	2	4	4	0	3	8	5	6	6	25	3	42	45
454	Wiley	Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences	0	0	0	0	4	3	0	1	0	5	4	15	11	10	17	7	42	45
455	Elsevier	Carbon	0	4	8	5	4	7	4	4	2	10	7	4	8	12	14	8	42	45
456	Elsevier	Clinical Neurology and Neurosurgery	0	1	0	0	2	0	1	0	2	5	2	8	10	14	13	7	43	45
457	Elsevier	Drug Discovery Today	0	4	2	3	4	5	2	3	11	2	1	10	13	12	12	10	43	45
458	Elsevier	European Neuropsychopharmacology	0	1	2	0	1	5	0	2	3	6	3	6	3	9	15	10	43	45
459	Elsevier	International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer	0	7	2	7	6	6	7	5	11	11	5	6	17	17	7	10	43	45
460	Elsevier	Journal of Cranio-Maxillofacial Surgery	0	3	1	0	4	7	1	3	3	2	1	5	7	6	9	19	43	45
461	Elsevier	Journal of Structural Biology	0	3	1	4	4	10	6	23	3	6	9	16	23	11	11	12	43	45
462	MDPI	International Journal of Molecular Sciences	2000	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	5	4	7	6	13	7	14	43	45
463	BMC	Reproductive Health	2004	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	1	4	3	2	2	9	5	20	43	45
464	NPG	Nature Immunology	0	15	6	7	8	6	4	11	12	3	6	7	7	10	13	11	43	45
465	LWW	Annals of Surgery	0	2	6	1	2	7	7	8	12	11	6	10	9	15	6	13	43	45
466	LWW	Transplantation	0	20	22	21	20	21	12	14	14	18	11	15	15	8	12	14	43	46
467	ACS	Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling	0	6	7	4	7	4	6	11	6	6	8	13	6	10	12	12	43	46
468	ada	Current Medical Literature: Diabetes	0	17	7	10	10	13	14	12	12	8	9	18	12	14	9	11	43	46
469	IEEE	IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	8	13	13	43	46
470	APS	Physical Review X	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	2	19	13	43	46
471	Springer	Cancer Chemotherapy and Pharmacology	0	2	3	2	3	5	3	2	4	1	1	7	6	12	9	12	43	46
472	Springer	Diabetologia	0	4	4	7	7	9	9	14	11	10	12	13	13	9	18	6	43	46
473	Springer	The European Physical Journal - A :: Hadrons and N	0	8	10	12	11	14	5	11	8	14	6	6	10	11	10	12	43	46
474	Springer	Virchows Archiv	0	6	6	6	7	3	4	16	12	9	5	8	16	8	15	10	43	46
475	Springer	The European Physical Journal - Special Topics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	4	5	6	10	29	18	8	7	43	46
476	Wiley	International Journal of Climatology	0	1	4	2	3	9	6	2	7	6	3	6	6	8	11	14	43	46
477	Elsevier	Applied Geochemistry	0	2	0	8	4	8	3	10	14	9	5	23	13	11	13	9	43	46
478	Elsevier	Clinical Neurophysiology	0	13	7	15	16	8	8	11	10	11	6	20	7	12	8	13	43	46
479	Elsevier	Environmental Modelling and Software	0	0	2	0	2	1	4	3	2	11	7	6	9	9	9	15	43	46
480	Elsevier	European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences	0	2	4	3	6	10	7	2	6	12	9	8	2	11	13	9	43	46
481	Elsevier	Ophthalmology	2012	3	2	7	3	3	3	2	0	13	2	6	7	11	12	10	43	46
482	Elsevier	Surface and Coatings Technology	0	15	6	16	11	22	24	9	18	8	12	13	10	10	13	10	43	46
483	Elsevier	Developmental Cell	0	1	3	10	10	7	6	7	8	7	10	11	12	12	10	11	43	46
484	IEEE	IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing	0	1	4	3	8	2	6	5	6	10	14	8	10	9	12	12	43	46
485	IEEE	IEEE Transactions on Magnetics	0	0	0	3	6	2	2	2	11	5	2	1	5	13	7	7	44	46
486	Wiley	British Journal of Pharmacology	0	13	9	9	6	4	3	11	11	10	12	9	19	9	9	15	44	46
487	JAPS	Journal of Applied Physiology	0	9	13	6	8	7	9	4	10	13	7	8	7	13	10	10	44	46
488	Thieme	Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift - DMW	0	5	8	16	7	6	10	7	9	5	8	9	4	5	16	12	44	46
489	Springer	Journal of Materials Science	0	6	7	2	4	3	1	8	4	7	9	6	9	10	11	11	44	46
490	Wiley	Ecography	0	1	1	0	5	3	5	2	1	8	13	7	7	9	15	8	44	46
491	Elsevier	Biochemical Pharmacology	0	7	8	10	8	7	4	5	9	1	8	12	8	9	14	9	44	46
492	Elsevier	Journal of Cleaner Production	0	0	0	0	3	6	2	10	6	8	3	6	5	3	16	13	44	46

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tab 11 number of articles from Switzerland - top 500 journals

provider	OA mode	journal title	OA from	Y2001	Y2002	Y2003	Y2004	Y2005	Y2006	Y2007	Y2008	Y2009	Y2010	Y2011	Y2012	Y2013	Y2014	Y2015	share [%]	cum [%]
493	Elsevier	Journal of Clinical Epidemiology	0	3	5	4	4	6	5	11	7	11	3	18	5	15	8	9	44	47
494	Elsevier	Journal of Psychiatric Research	0	1	1	1	2	4	1	7	7	4	10	11	10	9	15	8	44	47
495	Elsevier	Medical Engineering and Physics	0	1	2	4	0	2	1	2	4	3	2	8	4	13	15	4	44	47
496	Elsevier	Veterinary Microbiology	0	9	8	6	10	7	10	8	13	22	17	17	11	15	9	8	44	47
497	Hogrefe	Swiss Journal of Psychology	0	6	5	7	8	9	12	12	15	10	12	12	11	9	14	9	44	47
498	NPG	The ISME Journal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	8	4	3	9	12	8	12	44	47
499	BMC	Genome Biology	2000	1	4	1	3	2	4	6	13	7	5	3	5	12	7	13	44	47
500	Wiley	EMBO Reports	0	15	8	13	13	13	11	12	13	7	10	8	7	10	11	11	44	47
others				8,541	8,822	10,057	10,913	11,522	12,912	13,429	13,914	14,614	15,368	16,377	17,241	17,493	18,128	17,264	100	104

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tab 12 key numbers describing affiliation processing

inst code	items	items ch	affils	affils uni1	affils uni2	affils ch	affils != ch	AFIDs	AFID [%]	AFID uni
switzerland	349,294	346,091	729,766	309,934	296,336	723,600	6,166	683,402	94	25,349
epfl	29,938	29,389	47,097	22,599	22,359	46,338	759	45,447	96	535
eth	54,430	54,038	87,230	35,149	30,207	86,450	780	84,815	97	193
uba	18,822	18,484	28,590	8,646	8,519	27,964	626	27,986	98	143
ube	23,872	23,050	38,232	12,141	11,966	36,708	1,524	37,353	98	201
ufr	5,597	5,551	8,693	2,858	2,829	8,591	102	8,456	97	50
uge	24,959	24,682	39,754	15,076	14,886	39,150	604	38,687	97	165
ula	14,615	14,349	23,115	9,400	9,317	22,549	566	22,354	97	161
uzu	33,002	32,412	52,715	17,242	14,661	51,638	1,077	51,335	97	168
bfh	562	529	806	503	502	745	61	760	94	33
hslu	168	167	249	160	159	248	1	239	96	12
xhosp	76,739	76,715	167,680	84,889	82,427	167,614	66	155,903	93	4,212
nn	143,418	143,418	235,605	101,351	98,616	235,605	0	210,067	89	20,771

40,198

item per affil	#	affils	cum affils	affils [%]	cum affils [%]
100+	199	43,321	43,321	6	6
<100	372	25,162	68,483	3	9
<50	5,633	100,840	169,323	14	23
<10	22,002	114,786	284,109	16	39
<4	310,366	445,657	729,766	61	100
>= 4	28,206	284,109		39	

items number of articles and reviews from 2001 to 2015
 items_ch number of items with country identified as Switzerland by Scopus
 affils number of affiliation entries for these items
 affils uni1 number of unique affiliations after first level standardization
 affils uni2 number of unique affiliations after second level standardization
 affils ch number of affiliations with country code for Switzerland by Scopus
 affils != ch number of affiliations without country code for Switzerland by Scopus
 AFIDs number of affils with a Scopus affiliation identifier (AFID)
 AFID[%] coverage [%] of AFIDs (AFIDs/affils)
 AFID uni number of unique AFIDs

item per affil frequency distribution of the number of items per unique affiliation (affils_uni1)
 affiliations variants with more then 4 items each (representing 284,109 items, 39 %) have been checked intellectually

MPDL 2016 - journal publishing in Switzerland and gold open access

2016-10-19

tab 13 affiliations for postal code 8093 (ETH Zürich)

ctry	MPDL assignment		scopus records 1980-2016		
	subcat	assigned institution	affils uni1	items	
--	blacklist	NN	1	1	
--	eth_domain	NN	5	5	ETH Domain
--		ETH Zürich	276	434	
--		NN	13	22	
ch	blacklist	NN	3	3	
ch	eth_domain	NN	257	407	ETH Domain
ch	fh	NN	4	6	FH im String
ch	hosp	NN	7	10	Hospital
ch		ETH Zürich	16,621	42,829	
ch		NN	382	547	
ch		Universität Genf	1	1	
ch		Universität Zürich	113	137	
de		NN	32	48	
it		NN	1	2	
nl		NN	1	1	
total			17,717	44,453	
assigned to ETHZ			16,897	43,263	
intentionally blacklisted			277	432	
potential candidates			543	758	
ratio candidates / assigned [%]			3.2	1.8	

for subset of all affiliation strings from countries de, ch, kr, at, nl, it, lx, --
 check against regular expression **[^0-9]8093[^0-9]** against the full affiliation string

examples for candidates with >= 4 items

- 6 x che:8093 zurich:competence center for systems physiology and metabolic diseases;
- 5 x che:ch-8093 zurich:competence center for systems physiology and metabolic diseases;
- 4 x che:8093 zurich:department of materials;laboratory of crystallography;
- 4 x che:8093 zurich:hci;department of chemistry and applied biosciences;institute for chemical and bioengineering;
- 4 x che:ch 8093 zürich:wood physics group;institute for building materials;
- 4 x che:ch-8093 zurich:institute for chemical and bioengineering;
- 4 x che:ch-8093 zurich:competence center for systems physiology and metabolic diseases;
- 4 x deu:8093 zürich:eth hänggerberg;